

Determination of the State of Educational Research in Austria

Friedrich W. Hesse (Chair, IWM Tübingen)
Ina Matt, Falk Reckling, Thomas Völker (FWF)
Nikolaus Possanner (ÖWR)

in cooperation with
Manfred Prisching, Lisa Hönegger (ÖWR)
Mark Neijssel, Alfredo Yegros, Carole de Bordes (CWTS)
Maria del Carmen Calatrava Moreno, Brigitte Tiefenthaler, Katharina Warta
(Technopolis)

Vienna, 18.06.2019

This content is published under the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

Contents

1.	Introduction—Background and design of the study	1
2.	Austrian higher education at a glance	2
3.	Status and developments in higher education policy and teacher education	4
4.	Funding of educational research in Austria	7
4.1.	A comparative perspective on educational research funding.....	8
4.2.	Main results	10
5.	Performance of educational research in an international comparison	11
5.1.	Methodological approach and study design	11
5.2.	Outcomes and insights	12
5.2.1.	Publication output.....	13
5.2.2.	Citation impact analysis	14
5.3.	Main results	17
6.	Issues, strengths and challenges I: In-depth interviews.....	19
6.1.	Methodological approach and study design	19
6.2.	Outcomes and insights	20
6.2.1.	Strengths.....	20
6.2.2.	Challenges and weaknesses	21
6.2.3.	Key players.....	24
6.2.4.	Potential for innovation.....	24
6.3.	Main results	25
7.	Issues, strengths and challenges II: Online survey	27
7.1.	Methodological approach and study design	27
7.2.	Outcomes and insights	28
7.2.1.	Funding and funding sources.....	28
7.2.2.	Output and dissemination	30
7.2.3.	Challenges and perspectives.....	32
7.3.	Main results	35
8.	Recommendations of the Panel.....	36
9.	Advisory Bodies	39
10.	Appendices	40

Tables

Table 1: Austrian higher education institutional landscape (Courtesy of Austrian Science Council)	2
Table 2: Institutions of educational research and teacher education (Courtesy of Austrian Science Council).....	5
Table 3: Higher education funding (Courtesy of Austrian Science Council)	7
Table 4: Overall funding for educational research in CH, DE and AT 2013-2015	8
Table 5: Approval rates 2013–2017 of educational research in CH, DE and AT	8
Table 6: Educational research funding at the ERC	10
Table 7: Publication output, the percentage of publications in educational research within the total scientific and scholarly output (%) and the internal coverage for the field Educational Sciences per country (2000–2016) (full counting).....	14
Table 8: Bibliometric indicators for the field educational research per country (2000-2016) (Courtesy of CWTS Leiden)	15
Table 9 Performance Indicators for the Top 5 universities in the field of educational research (Courtesy of CWTS Leiden)	16
Table 10: Bibliometric indicators for the field of educational research per country for English publications (EN) and publications in other languages (Other), (2000-2016)	17
Table 11: Quantitative criteria to ensure the right balance among the group of participants interviewed (Courtesy of Technopolis Group)	19

Figures

Figure 1: Output (P) and impact (MNCS) for the top 5 key players (2000-2016) in the field of educational research (Courtesy of CWTS Leiden).....	13
Figure 2: Proportion of recipients of third-party funding in the last five years (Courtesy of Technopolis Group).....	28
Figure 3: Opinion on research funding of respondents who have not received third-party research funding in the last five years (Courtesy of Technopolis Group)	29
Figure 4: Respondents' main source of third-party funding in the last five years (Courtesy of Technopolis Group)	30
Figure 5: Publication activity of survey respondents in public universities and university colleges of teacher education (Courtesy of Technopolis Group)	31
Figure 6: Participants' share of publications in different languages	31
Figure 7: Formats of respondents' publications in the past five years (Courtesy of Technopolis Group)	32
Figure 8: Type of research activity of respondents in different kinds of institutions (Courtesy of Technopolis Group)	32
Figure 9: Participants' opinions on educational research in Austria (Courtesy of Technopolis Group)	33
Figure 10: Participants' opinions on the importance of measures for the positive development and strengthening of educational research in Austria (Courtesy of Technopolis Group).....	34
Figure 11: Participants' opinion on the importance of measures to strengthen the link between educational research and practice (Courtesy of Technopolis Group)	34

Abbreviations

ABBR.	NAME
BMBWF	Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research
DFG	German Research Foundation
FFG	Austrian Research Promotion Agency
FWF	Austrian Science Fund
IHS	Institute for Advanced Studies
ISB	Innovation Foundation for Education
ÖWR	Austrian Science Council
SNSF	Swiss National Science Foundation
WIFO	Austrian Institute of Economic Research

Executive Summary

Der Wissenschaftsfonds (FWF) wurde von der Innovationsstiftung für Bildung mit der Durchführung einer Standortbestimmung der österreichischen Bildungsforschung beauftragt. Im Zentrum der Studie steht eine Darstellung der institutionellen Struktur und der Leistungsfähigkeit der österreichischen Bildungsforschung im internationalen Vergleich. Der FWF führte diese Studie in Zusammenarbeit mit dem Österreichischen Wissenschaftsrat (ÖWR) durch.

Zentrale Ergebnisse

Die in dieser Studie präsentierten Daten und Analysen zeigen, dass die Bildungswissenschaft in Österreich einerseits Herausforderungen gegenübersteht, andererseits aber auch positive Charakteristika aufweist, die eine gute Ausgangslage für eine Weiterentwicklung darstellen.

Stärken: Die Studie identifiziert eine Reihe exzellenter Forschungsgruppen, die an Themen wie Bildungspsychologie, Lehr- und Lerntechnologien, Dyslexie oder Phoniatrie arbeiten. Auffällig, ist hingegen, dass diese Gruppen vorwiegend in ‚Randbereichen‘ der Bildungswissenschaft tätig sind.

Als eine weitere Stärke werden von den Teilnehmern und Teilnehmerinnen an der vorliegenden Studie vorhandene Kompetenz im Bereich methodischer Ansätze wie partizipativer Forschung und Aktionsforschung („action research“) angeführt. Diese Methoden gelangen vorwiegend in Projekten auf Bundesländer-Ebene zur Anwendung. Eine zusätzliche Schwerpunktsetzung besteht in den Bereichen LehrerInnenbildung und Didaktik.

Schwächen: Die größte Herausforderung für Bildungsforschung in Österreich stellt das geringe Ausmaß an Drittmittelförderung im Bereich der Grundlagenforschung dar. Verglichen mit Ländern wie Deutschland oder der Schweiz sind die Ressourcen, die in die Förderung von Bildungsforschung fließen, gering. Eng damit verbunden ist auch eine geringe Zahl an eingereichten Forschungsanträgen beim Wissenschaftsfonds FWF. Die Teilnehmer und Teilnehmerinnen an den Interviews und an der Online-Umfrage geben an, weder ausreichend Zeit noch anderweitige Ressourcen zur Verfügung zu haben, die für das Erstellen von qualitativ hochwertigen Forschungsanträgen notwendig wäre.

Die bibliometrische Analyse zeigt, dass der wissenschaftliche Output in internationalen und qualitätsgeprüften (*peer review*) Zeitschriften vergleichsweise niedrig ist. Jene Artikel, die international publiziert werden, stammen von einigen wenigen Forschungsgruppen, die jeweils in Randbereichen der Bildungsforschung anzusiedeln sind. So stammen 44% aller Fachartikel von nur 5 Forschungsgruppen.

Bildungsforschung in Österreich ist institutionell fragmentiert und auf unterschiedliche Universitäten, Fakultäten und Institute verteilt. Das führt dazu, dass es äußerst herausfordernd ist, kohärente Strukturen für die Ausbildung von Bildungsforschern und -forscherinnen zu etablieren.

Chancen: Die Bildungsforschung in Österreich agiert dennoch auf einem Niveau, auf dem durchaus aufgebaut werden kann. Das wird in der bibliometrischen Analyse sichtbar, aber auch in der Tatsache, dass Forscher und Forscherinnen in Feldern tätig sind, die hohes Potenzial zeigen. Um dieses Potenzial bestmöglich ausschöpfen zu können, wird es notwendig sein, handlungsanleitende Schlussfolgerungen aus dieser Standortbestimmung zu ziehen. Diese müssen auf den bereits vorhandenen Stärken aufbauen und darüber hinaus ein sich gegenwärtig öffnendes ‚Zeitfenster‘ nutzen (u. a. neue Fördermöglichkeiten im Rahmen einer Exzellenzinitiative).

Die Pädagogischen Hochschulen haben das Potenzial, sich zu forschungsintensiveren Institutionen zu entwickeln und den Link zwischen Forschung und Praxis zu stärken (Transfer und Anwendung).

Risiken: Das internationale Panel der Standortbestimmung identifiziert ‚Untätigkeit‘ als ein wesentliches Risiko. Keine Maßnahmen zu ergreifen, würde dazu führen, ein gegenwärtig bestehendes ‚Zeitfenster‘ verstreichen zu lassen. Die aktuell vorhandene Abhängigkeit von einigen wenigen dominierenden Leistungsträgern und Leistungsträgerinnen kann dann problematisch werden, wenn diese das System verlassen, während zugleich keine kohärenten und strukturierten Karrierepfade für Nachwuchsforscher und -forscherinnen vorhanden sind.

Empfehlungen

Basierend auf der Evaluierung der spezifischen Stärken, Schwächen, Chancen und Risiken der Bildungsforschung in Österreich spricht das internationale Panel eine Reihe von Empfehlungen aus. Diese Empfehlungen adressieren unterschiedliche Ebenen des Bildungsforschungssystems: die Policy-Ebene, die institutionelle Ebene sowie die Ebene der Forschenden. Darüber hinaus sind die Empfehlungen anhand verschiedener Aktivitätsfelder gegliedert.

Konkret empfiehlt das Panel die Entwicklung einer Policy-Strategie auf deren Basis spezifische Förderprogramme entworfen und implementiert werden können, gemeinsam mit adäquaten Formen von Monitoring und Evaluierung. Diese Struktur erlaubt aus Sicht des Panels (1) eine erhöhte Transparenz und (2) ein Sichtbarmachen der schon existierenden Stärken und Kapazitäten der österreichischen Bildungsforschung.

Das vorrangige Ziel in der Entwicklung einer derartigen nationalen Strategie ist die Festlegung spezifischer Fokusbereiche und Prioritäten. Der vorliegende Bericht dient als empirische Basis für die Entwicklung dieser Strategie, die folgende Fragen beantworten sollte:

- a. Was ist bereits vorhanden und wo gibt es blinde Flecken und Lücken?
- b. Welche Bereiche der Bildungsforschung sollten gefördert und weiterentwickelt werden? Welche Bereiche sind weniger bedeutsam?
- c. Wohin entwickelt sich die Bildungswissenschaft international?

Während partizipative Forschungsmethoden und „Action Research“ als Stärken der österreichischen Bildungsforschung wahrgenommen werden (siehe Interviews und Umfrage), empfiehlt das Panel, auch andere Ansätze zu fördern, um die bereits vorhandenen Stärken zu ergänzen. Quantitative Forschungsmethoden sowie „Mixed-Methods“ Ansätze sollten in Zukunft priorisiert werden, um das Feld zu erweitern und zu stärken. Insbesondere Längsschnittstudien haben in anderen Ländern große politische Bedeutung erlangt, so zum Beispiel die „Millenium Cohort Study“ in Großbritannien oder die Studien des „Nationalen Bildungspanels“ (NEPS) in Deutschland. Derartige Studien sollten in Beziehung zu breiteren Themen wie Gesundheit, sozio-emotionale Entwicklung sowie kognitive und akademische Leistungen stehen.

Eine derartige Strategie sollte weiters erfolgreiche Modelle aus anderen Ländern heranziehen: Welche Förderinstrumente existieren in anderen Ländern? Was funktioniert und was kann für Österreich umgesetzt werden? Eine Möglichkeit, Bildungsforschung zu stärken, sind spezifische Förderprogramme. Angelehnt an den Schweizerischen Nationalfonds (SNF) könnten vier bis fünf Exzellenzzentren eingerichtet werden, die jeweils einem bestimmten Thema oder Bereich gewidmet wären und österreichische Universitäten mit kleinen Netzwerken von Pädagogischen Hochschulen zusammenbringen.

Bildungsforschung spielt aktuell eine untergeordnete Rolle in der österreichischen Forschungslandschaft und auch im Vergleich mit anderen Ländern. Es besteht demnach Bedarf, die gegenwärtig bestehende Gelegenheit zu nutzen und dies zu ändern:

- Bildungswissenschaft muss in Zukunft vermehrt interdisziplinär orientiert sein, um auf neue Anforderungen wie beispielsweise die Anwendung von Data Science für erziehungsbezogene Fragestellungen eingehen zu können;
- Bildungswissenschaft muss im Rahmen einer nationalen Strategie entwickelt werden, um der gegenwärtig bestehenden Fragmentierung des Feldes entgegenzuwirken;
- Spezifische Förderangebote sollen Anreize zu mehr interdisziplinärer und Mixed-Methods-Forschung setzen;
- Bildungswissenschaft soll eine wichtigere Rolle in einer evidenz-basierten Steuerung und Entwicklung des Bildungssektors in Österreich spielen.

Executive Summary

The Austrian Science Fund (FWF) was commissioned by the Innovation Foundation for Education (ISB) to determine the status of Austrian educational research and its institutional structure, performance and international standing. The FWF conducted this study in collaboration with the Austrian Science Council (ÖWR).

Main results

The evidence gathered for this report shows that educational research in Austria, while facing considerable challenges is also characterized by a number of positive features that can be built upon:

Strengths: Austria already has a number of excellent research groups working on topics such as educational psychology, educational technology, dyslexia or phoniatrics. These groups, however, mostly operate at the 'margins' of educational research.

Apart from that, the participants in this study described (only) a few methodological approaches such as participatory research methods and action research as particular strong points with a clear focus on practical application predominantly on a local/federal state level. There appears to be a focus on teacher education and didactics, too.

Weakness: The main challenge identified by the various reports is a lack of funding of basic research. Compared to countries like Germany or Switzerland, the resources invested into educational research are quite small. This also goes hand in hand with very few proposals for FWF funding from educational researchers. The participants in the interview study and online survey stated that they did neither have the time nor the resources to produce high-quality proposals.

The bibliometric study shows that the output in terms of international peer-reviewed journal articles is comparatively low. In addition, the journal articles are mainly produced by a small number of research groups that operate at the margins of educational research: 44% of all publications came from five groups in Austria.

Educational research is fragmented and spread over different universities and departments. As a consequence, it is a challenge to develop coherent structures for the training of educational researchers.

Opportunities: There is a basic level of educational research in Austria that can be built upon. This is visible in the bibliometric study as well as in the fact that there are several researchers active in Austrian educational research who show high potential. What is needed is to draw the actionable conclusions from the evaluation of what is already there and take advantage of the current 'window of opportunity' (new funding through an excellence initiative).

The university colleges of teacher education have the potential of becoming more research-intensive institutions that cooperate to strengthen the link between research and practice (transfer and application).

Threats: One of the main threats identified by the international panel is ‘doing nothing’ as this would mean letting this particular ‘window of opportunity’ close again. The current trend towards a dependency on a few ‘high-potential’ individuals dominating the research landscape could become problematic if they left the system and if this were not accompanied by coherent and structured career paths for early-stage researchers.

Recommendations

Based on the evaluation of distinct strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats of and for educational research in Austria, the panel has developed a set of recommendations. These recommendations address different levels of the educational research system: the policy level, the institutional level and the level of the individual researchers. Furthermore, they are structured along different areas of activity, specifically the development of policy strategy, on the basis of which dedicated funding programmes should be designed and implemented that go along with fitting concepts and modes of monitoring and evaluation. This structure, in the view of the panel, would allow for (1) more transparency and (2) for making visible the already existing strengths and capacities of educational research in Austria.

The primary goal would be to develop a strategy for educational research that defines particular focus areas and priorities. The report at hand can function as the empirical basis for developing such a strategy, which should address the following questions:

- a. What is already there, and where are the blind spots or gaps?
- b. Which areas of educational research should be funded and further developed? Which areas are less significant?
- c. Where is educational research headed on an international level?

While participatory research methods and action research are considered to be strengths of the Austrian educational research system (according to the interviews and survey), it would be appropriate to encourage and fund other approaches to extend the current strengths. For example, quantitative and mixed methods research approaches could be given some priority in future to broaden and strengthen the field of enquiry. Longitudinal studies, in particular, have been shown to have much policy significance and value in other countries, e.g., the Millennium Birth Cohort study in the UK and the National Educational Panel (NEPS) study in Germany. This could be related to broader topics such as health, equity, socio-emotional development as well as cognitive and academic outcomes. Such a strategy should also consider ‘best practices’ from other countries: which funding instruments exist in other countries? What works, and what can be adapted for Austria? One possibility of building capacity is to create dedicated funding opportunities for educational research. Like the Swiss SNSF, one could move in the direction of creating 4 to 5 centres of excellence, each devoted to a specific topic and hosted by one of the top Austrian research universities, including a

small network of other researchers, for instance, in the best university colleges of teacher education.

As educational research in sum plays a minor role in the Austrian research landscape in total and in comparison to other countries, there is a need and a promising opportunity to change it now:

- future educational research must become more interdisciplinary due to new demands, e.g., the application of data science for education;
- it must be developed under a nationwide strategic perspective to overcome fragmentation;
- it needs to be encouraged by motivating funding offers which include an appreciation of more interdisciplinary research and the use of mixed methods;
- it needs to be part of a political interest in an evidence-based development of the educational system in Austria guided by educational research to inform the development.

1. Introduction—Background and design of the study

The Austrian Science Fund (FWF) was commissioned by the Innovation Foundation for Education (ISB) to determine the status of Austrian educational research. The foundation was established on 1 January 2017 with the aim of “[p]romoting innovation in the classroom, breaking new ground in education and raising the level of education in Austria.”¹ As part of this mandate, ISB tasked the FWF with coordinating a study on the current status of Austrian educational research.

The FWF conducted this study in collaboration with the Austrian Science Council (Wissenschaftsrat, ÖWR). A “Sounding Board” was set-up to give the educational research community in Austria a possibility to advise on the different parts of the study and to check for factual mistakes in the final report. FWF, ÖWR and the scientific advisory board of the ISB each nominated representatives to the Sounding Board.

The study was conducted as an informed peer review, a process in which an international panel of experts in the area of educational science discussed and assessed the different parts of the study and formulated recommendations for the future development of Austrian educational research. This evaluation commission consisted of international experts who represent the disciplinary breadth of the field and was supported in its work by qualitative and quantitative background materials on educational research in Austria. These materials were produced using a range of different approaches and methodologies with the aim of providing a balanced and nuanced assessment of the educational research field in Austria. These materials included an overview report of the institutional landscape of educational research within the broader Austrian higher education landscape, a bibliometric study that focuses on the performance of Austrian educational research in an international comparison, as well as an interview study and online survey, which made it possible to include the perspective of educational researchers working in Austria.

This report brings together the main insights from these different sources and aims at giving a concise overview of the current status of Austrian educational research. It starts out by providing an overview of the Austrian higher education system and the place of educational research within this system and proceeds with a brief analysis of funding for educational research in Austria and the main outcomes of the bibliometric study. To add more depth to these quantitative representations of educational research, the report then contextualises these insights with results from 22 in-depth interviews with professionals working in educational research as well as from an online survey. The report concludes with recommendations from the international evaluation panel.

¹ <https://oead.at/en/news/article/2018/01/innovation-foundation-for-education/>. Accessed 19 February 2019.

2. Austrian higher education at a glance²

Austrian higher education comprises a broad variety of institutions and legal foundations: 22 public universities composed of comprehensive universities, technical universities, medical universities and art universities. In addition, there are specialised university institutions such as the Montanuniversität Leoben and the University of Veterinary Medicine, Vienna. Furthermore, there exist 21 universities of applied sciences, 14 colleges of teacher education and 14 private universities. Compared with the universities of applied sciences and private universities, public universities account for the major part of post-secondary education in Austria. Altogether, 60% of students are enrolled at public universities in Austria.

Table 1: Austrian higher education institutional landscape (Courtesy of Austrian Science Council)

Public universities	Universities of applied sciences	Private universities	Colleges of teacher education
22	21	14	14
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Comprehensive universities • Technical universities • Medical universities • Art universities • Specialised universities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economics • Engineering • Health sciences • Social sciences • Sciences • Security & risk studies • Art and design 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social sciences • Economics • Legal studies • Health sciences • Theology • Philosophy • Arts and design • Music 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Primary school teaching profession • Secondary level teaching profession (in cooperation with universities) • Secondary level vocational education teaching profession

Austrian universities are governed by the University Act 2002, are established as independent entities and are therefore granted autonomy. They operate with a global budget, which is negotiated for three years as part of performance agreements (Leistungsvereinbarung).

It was not until the mid-1990s, thereby later than in other European countries, that the sector of **universities of applied sciences** (Fachhochschule) was introduced in Austria. Today, there are about 40,000 publicly funded university places; about 10,000 university places are privately funded. For the future, it is planned to further expand the sector by 450 university places a year, the focus being on STEM fields and extra-occupational degree programmes.

Over the next years, it is expected that the number of students will increase moderately. The main objective, though, is a gradual shift of the number of students towards universities of applied sciences (medium-term: 30%; long-term: 60%), following the example of the Netherlands. In this context, particular attention is paid to the development of dual degree programmes, extra-occupational degree programmes, and joint degree programmes.

² This chapter is based on the background report: Prisching, M. (2018): Skizze der österreichischen Hochschulforschung. Austrian Science Council.

In 2007, federal pedagogic academies were converted into **colleges of teacher education** (Pädagogische Hochschulen). To date, the colleges are lower-level departments of the Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research (BMBWF). The educational offer at the colleges includes primary school teaching profession, secondary level teaching profession (in cooperation with universities) and secondary level vocational education teaching profession. However, they are not entitled to award doctorates. In addition to teacher education, colleges of teacher education are tasked with conducting applied research, given their brief history necessary research capacities are still in development.

The reorganisation of the training of educators represents a core educational project of recent years. The new education of teachers includes the education and training of all persons who want to take up a pedagogical profession and was regulated by law in 2013. The implementation of the new pedagogical education has been taking place since the 2016/17 academic year. The newly established **university colleges of teacher education** will endeavour in the coming years to build up their academic competence in order to approach the internationally valid standards of university education. In order to ensure a high-quality implementation of the new teacher education, different university departments and teacher training colleges were merged to form four regional development networks. Within the networks, the curricula will be standardised, and collaborative teacher studies will be offered for the secondary level.

The most recent additions to the Austrian higher education landscape are **private universities** as laid down by law in 1999. The private universities first have to receive an accreditation of institution and of programmes. The 14 private universities offer more than 150 degree programmes, particularly in the areas of social sciences, economics, legal studies, health sciences, theology, philosophy, arts and design, and music. In recent years, the sector has recorded the highest growth rates. In 2018/2019, 14,446 students were enrolled at private universities in Austria (a mere three percent of all students).

After describing the state of the higher education system in broad strokes, we will now take a look at educational research in Austria.

3. Status and developments in higher education policy and teacher education

Providing an accurate picture of the Austrian educational research and teacher education landscape proved to be no easy task as there are no current surveys on the state of educational research available. To give a first overview, we will thus draw on a report published by the Institute for Advanced Studies (IHS) back in 2008,³ which to our knowledge provides the most comprehensive and recent report on educational research and teacher education. While this study starts by identifying a lack of systematic overviews, it calls attention to a number of activities in this area⁴ as well as a publication on educational research that highlights some important issues and challenges.⁵ Furthermore, the study includes a list of research activities in vocational and business education.^{6,7} The IHS report notes that there are some connections between "political priorities and research"⁸ via departmental research; however, practical implementation was almost non-existent or very slow.⁹

"[F]or the most part, research is rather too weak to give real impulses and the practical knowledge, including points of interest, is therefore stronger in the implementation—professional knowledge is in practice only very conditionally perceived as a value and authority over traditions, ideologies, points of interest and political day-to-day trends."

The study estimates that **about 800 researchers** are active in educational research while also acknowledging that the available data on staffing are not comprehensive. This means

³ Lassnig, L. (2008): Bildungsforschung in Österreich als Ressource wissenschaftlicher Bildungspolitik und Schulentwicklung: Ist-Stand und Perspektiven für eine verbesserte Nutzung. IHS Input-Papier für NBB-2009-AutorInnengruppe, June 2008.

⁴ Reisinger, L. (1972): Arbeitsmarkt- und Bildungsforschung in Österreich. Mitteilungen aus der Arbeitsmarkt- und Berufsforschung. 5. Jg./1972, 147.156
Lassnig, L., Pechar, H., Huber, M. (1994): Bildungsforschung in Österreich. Österreichischer Länderbericht und 3. Internationales OECD Seminar zur Bildungsforschung und Entwicklung, Wien.
Altrichter, H., Mayr, J. (1999): Zum Stand der Bildungsforschung in Österreich. In: Bildungsforschung für Schulentwicklung. Tagungsdokumentation. Universität Linz 1999, 2-15.

⁵ Hackl, B., Pechar, H. (Hrsg.) (2007): Bildungspolitische Aufklärung. Um- und Irrwege der Österreichischen Schulreform. Festschrift für Karl Heinz Gruber. Innsbruck: Studienverlag.

⁶ Gramlinger, F., Schlögl, P., Stock M. (2008): Berufs- und Wirtschaftspädagogik in Österreich. Oder: Wer „macht“ die berufliche Bildung in AT? <http://www.bwpat.de/ATspezial/>. Accessed 27 Mai 2019.

⁷ The introduction of educational standards in the Austrian education system was implemented in 2009 by a corresponding ordinance (BGBl. II No. 1/2009). In 2011, an amendment entered into force (BGBl. II No. 282/2011). Ibid., pp. 10-11.

⁸ Lassnig, L. (2008): p. 19

⁹ The current work programme of the Austrian Federal Government includes projects such as the further development of pedagogy education, the creation of tertiary programmes for the education of elementary teachers, new working-time models for educators as well as obligatory regular training for teachers during lesson-free times: <https://www.bundeskanzleramt.gv.at/regierungsdokumente>, p.59f. Accessed 12 March 2019.

that only a rough picture can be compiled.¹⁰

*"The ratio between researchers in universities and PHs was about 2:1, about half of them were academic staff, about 10% were ordinary university professors and a further 15% were professors and about 20% were mainly in teaching or in management positions."*¹¹

Overall, the proportion of women among the total staff was 50%, in colleges of teacher education a bit higher, and significantly lower in non-university institutions (the data on this is, however, incomplete).¹²

Table 2: Institutions of educational research and teacher education (Courtesy of Austrian Science Council)

University Research Institutes	University Colleges of Teacher Education (TE)	Universities of Applied Science	Non-university Research Institutes
Alpen-Adria-University of Klagenfurt <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inst. for Educational Research • Inst. of Instructional and School Dev. Danube University Krems <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Department for Continuing Education Research and Educational Management University of Graz <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inst. of Educational Sciences • Inst. for Professional Dev. in Education Technical University of Graz <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Department of Educational Technology Medical University of Graz <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Division of Phoniatics University of Innsbruck <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Department of Educational Research • Department of Subject-Specific Education • Department of Teacher Education and School Research University of Linz <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Linz School of Education. • Department of Educational Research University of Salzburg <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Department of Educational Science • School of Education • Centre for Cognitive Neuroscience University of Vienna <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Department of Education • Department of Applied Psychology • Centre for Teacher Education Vienna University of Economics and Business <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Education Sciences Group 	Network North-East <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Univ. Coll. of TE Vienna • Univ. Coll. of TE Lower Austria • Univ. Coll. for Agrarian and Environmental Pedagogy • Univ. College of TE of Christian Churches Vienna / Krems Network South-East <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Univ. Coll. of TE Styria • Univ. Coll. of TE Carinthia • Univ. Coll. of TE Burgenland • Private Univ. Coll. of TE Network Center <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Private Univ. of Education, Diocese of Linz • Univ. Coll. of TE Upper Austria • Salzburg University of Education Stefan Zweig Network West <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pedagogical University Tyrol • Univ. Coll. of TE Vorarlberg • Univ. Coll. of TE Edith Stein 	UAS Upper Austria – Science Field Educational Research UAS Campus Vienna – Educational Research	BIFIE – Federal Institute for Educational Research, Innovation and Development of the Austrian School System IBW - Institute for Educational Research in Economics ÖIBF – Austrian Institute for Vocational Education and Training IHS – Institute for Advanced Studies IBE – Research Institute for Vocational Training and Adult Education oieb – Austrian Institute for Adult Education WIAB – Viennese Institute for Labour Market and Education Research

¹⁰ "Research at universities and colleges of education, supplemented by the members of the Austrian Society for Research and Development in Education (OEFEB) and the Educational Research Documentation 2006 (BIFODOC 06), shows a total of over 800 people active in educational research at that time." (Lassnig 2008, p. 20)

¹¹ Ibid., p. 21.

¹² "There was a similar pattern in individual institutions: in the Universities of Salzburg and Linz, the proportion of women is lower, in the PHs Vienna and Styria significantly higher. The characteristic differences are visible by function: among scientific staff, the majority are women (62%), the higher the position in the hierarchy, the more dominated by men, with 72% amongst professors." (Lassnig 2008, p. 21)

In the field of vocational and adult education research, non-university institutions make up a larger part (see Table 2). The Federal Institute for Educational Research (BIFIE), established in 2008, is responsible for coordinating student assessment surveys such as PISA or TALIS, publishing the National Education Report (NBB) and for evaluation policy programmes in the field of education. Other research institutions provide input on vocational education and training, adult education (IBW, OIEB, IBE) and higher education (IHS).

These institutions, however, do not play a significant role both in FWF project funding and in terms of international journal publications listed in Web of Science (see Section 5).

4. Funding of educational research in Austria

Federal higher education expenditure totals €4.1 billion in 2016 (€3.5 billion go to universities). The proportion of third-party funds is steadily increasing, whereas private donations and foundations are, in effect, hardly significant in Austria. The national research quota of 3.19% of GDP (slightly more than €12 billion) is above the EU target of 3% by 2020 and the second highest after Sweden in Europe. The quota comprises the economic sector (about 50%), federal funds (one-third), federal provinces' funds 4%), municipalities, and about €2 billion (16%) from abroad.

Almost all universities of applied sciences charge tuition fees (only three institutions waive fees). The amount is regulated at €363.36 per semester. Universities do not charge tuition fees. However, they may charge fees for students who have studied longer than the standard period of study. Private universities are not limited in any way regarding the amount of tuition fees.

Research funding is mainly covered by two institutions:

- The Austrian Science Fund (FWF): The FWF is the most important institution for supporting bottom-up basic research. The total budget for 2018 was €239.5 million.
- The Austrian Research Promotion Agency (FFG) is owned by the Republic of Austria. Its objective is to support industry-oriented research. The total budget for 2018 was €833 million.¹³

Table 3: Higher education funding (Courtesy of Austrian Science Council)

Sources of funding	National research quota	Research funding	
Federal higher education expenditure totals €4.1 billion in 2016 (€3.5 billion go to universities).	The national research quota of 3.2% of GDP (slightly more than €12 billion) is over the EU target of 3% by 2020.	Austrian Science Fund (FWF)	Austrian Research Promotion Agency (FFG)
The proportion of third-party funds is steadily increasing.	The quota comprises the economic sector (about 50%), federal funds (one-third), federal provinces' funds (€500 million), municipalities, and about €2 billion from abroad.	Budget 2018: €239.5 million	Budget 2018: €833 million
Donations and foundations are, in effect, hardly significant in Austria.		Most important institution for supporting bottom-up basic research	Objective is to support industry-oriented research

After this brief overview of the Austrian higher education system and the funding of educational research, we will now take a closer look at the situation of educational research and teacher education.

¹³ This is the total budget of the FFG including funding for broadband internet infrastructure development. The total funding without broadband amounts to €618 million (cash value is €506 million).

4.1. A comparative perspective on educational research funding

The table below shows the amounts of overall funding for educational research in Switzerland, Germany and Austria over the last 5 years (2013 to 2017). First of all, the absolute numbers already show a massive difference between the three funding agencies. What is also immediately visible is that the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)—even in relation to its total budget—devotes three times as much money to educational research as the German Research Foundation (DFG), and five times as much as the Austrian Science Fund (FWF).

Table 4: Overall funding for educational research in CH, DE and AT 2013-2015¹⁴

Funding Agency	Approved Funding (€ million)	Share of Total Budget
SNSF – Swiss National Science Fund	35.7	1.00%
DFG – German Research Foundation	50.3	0.34%
FWF – Austrian Science Fund	1.88	0.19%

These differences in funding, however, must also be understood in terms of the overall budget of the funding agencies: weighted by population, the SNSF has four times and the DFG one and a half times the budget of the FWF. Therefore, it makes sense to look at approval rates.¹⁵ The picture only changes slightly. The approval rates of educational research projects are significantly below the average approval rate for all disciplines in all three funding agencies.

Table 5: Approval rates 2013–2017 of educational research in CH, DE and AT

Funding Agency	Educational Research	All Disciplines
SNSF – Swiss National Science Foundation	37%	48%
DFG – German Research Foundation	24%	32%
FWF – Austrian Science Fund	15%	26%

While these results seem quite straightforward, there are several difficulties in interpreting these numbers that need to be mentioned: first, educational research is often only a minor part of research projects whose focus is in a different field. Additionally, there are many projects in programmes with comparatively small amounts of funding, such as Publication Costs, Citizen Science or Science Communication (see Appendix). And importantly, at the FWF, there are neither applications nor funding in programmes with high funding amounts such as Special Research Programmes (SFB), Doctoral Schools or the START Programme.

¹⁴ Source: SNSF, DFG and FWF

¹⁵ It should be noted here that this can only be compared for standard research projects. However, this is by far the largest funding programme of all three funding agencies.

Still, these numbers make it possible to construct a rough picture of the funding situation of educational research and in so doing show that the share and approval rates of educational research at funding agencies for basic research in Switzerland, Germany and Austria are comparatively low. And second, there are strong indications, at least for Austria and Germany, that a large part of the research funding in educational research comes from state ministries, local ministries and the EU.¹⁶

For the period 2013 to 2017, seven projects of the Anniversary Fund of the Austrian National Bank¹⁷ and 24 projects of the EU programmes FP7 and Horizon 2020 with the participation of Austrian institutions¹⁸ could be roughly assigned to educational research.

The Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research (BMBWF) publishes data on its funding activities in a public database. From 2008 to 2017, around €105 million were spent on educational research. The largest percentage of this money (around 80%) goes into the BIFIE.¹⁹ There is no data available on research funding in the federal states or municipalities.

Funding data of the Anniversary Fund of the Austrian National Bank, the EU programmes, the federal ministries as well as the federal states and municipalities will not be further analysed at this point, as either no data are available, the data do not permit a clear assignment to educational research, no approval probabilities can be calculated or no funding amounts are given. However, in order to take account of the significance of these funding resources, they were included in the survey.

The funding data from the DFG, the SNSF and the FWF, together with those from the European Research Council (ERC), suggest that the share of educational research in competitive basic research fund at national and European level is comparatively low.

¹⁶ For Germany, see: Weishaupt, Horst; Rittberger, Marc (Hrsg.): Bildungsforschung in Deutschland – eine Situationsanalyse. Berlin : BMBF (2012). No consistent data is available for Austria.

¹⁷ <https://www.oenb.at/jublfonds/jublfonds/projectsearch>. Accessed 17 June 2019.

¹⁸ These are projects that were assigned to the sub-disciplines "Education Systems", "Curriculum and Pedagogy", "Specialist Studies in Education" and "Other Education, see: the database DIMENSIONS,

¹⁹ Bundesforschungsdatenbank: <https://oravm13.noc-science.at/apex/f?p=115:1:16231283765927>
It needs to be noted that there has been a significant drop in funding since 2014, which cannot be explained entirely.

Table 6: Educational research funding at the ERC²⁰

Country Affiliation	Number of Grants Title/Keywords
UK	4
NL	3
DE, ES	2
BE, FI, IT, SE	1
Total	15
% of all ERC Grants	0.17%

4.2. Main results

- These numbers show that the funding levels for educational research are comparatively low.
- The resources that go into educational research are low compared to countries like Germany or Switzerland.
- There are very few proposals for FWF funding from educational researchers. If projects are funded, the research focus is often in a different field, and educational research is often only a minor part of the research project.
- There are many projects in programmes with rather small funding amounts such as Publication Costs, Citizen Science or Science Communication.
- There is no funding in programmes with high funding amounts such as Special Research Programmes (SFB), Doctoral Schools or the START Programme.

In a next step, we will consider how this translates into the research performance of educational researchers in Austria.

²⁰ <https://erc.europa.eu/projects-figures/erc-funded-projects>. Accessed 17 June 2019.

5. Performance of educational research in an international comparison

The Centre for Science and Technology Studies (CWTS) of Leiden University was commissioned by the Austrian Science Council (ÖWR) to conduct a bibliometric analysis of the performance of educational researchers in Austria.²¹ This analysis provided the evaluation panel with information on how Austria performs in the field of educational research compared to other European countries.

5.1. Methodological approach and study design

The study used data from the CWTS citation index system, which is an extended version of the Web of Science database of Clarivate Analytics. This database covers about 12,000 journals in the sciences, the social sciences, the arts and the humanities. What makes the CWTS database special is that CWTS researchers verify publication-based affiliations, use an improved method for matching cited article references to targeted articles and, importantly, draw on their own classification system that clusters publications into research fields and subfields based on citation relations.

For the analysis, CWTS considered the publication output and the citation impact. Publication output refers to the total number of publications (2000-2016) covered by the CI system, while citation impact focuses on how often publications have been cited. The analysis focused on articles and reviews, meaning that output like book reviews, editorials or letters were not included.

For the present study, CWTS looked at articles and reviews in international journals listed in Web of Science from 2000–2016, compared 10 European countries that are generally regarded as strong in research in terms of international journal publications (AT, BE, CH, DE, DK, FI, NL, NO, SE, UK), and analysed research articles and reviews in >300 journals covering the following areas:

- Education & Educational Research
- Education, Scientific Disciplines
- Education, Special
- Psychology, Educational

The analysis used size-independent indicators to allow for comparing countries that have significantly different volumes of publication output. The main indicators used are:

“Mean Normalized Citation Score (MNCS): an average normalized citation score above (below) one indicates that on average publications are cited more (or less)

²¹ Neijssel, M, Yegros, A., de Bordes, C. (2018): Research performance and benchmark analysis of Educational Sciences in Austria. CWTS Leiden

frequently than the average publication in the same field and published the same year.

Mean Normalized Journal Score (MNJS): Average normalized citation score of the journals in which a unit of analysis has published. The MNJS indicator is closely related to the MNCS indicator. The only difference is that instead of the actual number of citations of a publication, the MNJS used the number of citations of all the publications published in a particular journal. The interpretation of the MNJS indicator is analogous to the interpretation of the MNCS indicator.

Percentage top 10% publications (PP(top 10%)): if the percentage top 10% publications is above (below) 10%, this indicates an above (or below) average number of publications that belong to the top 10% in the same field and published the same year.” (Neijssel, Yegros, de Bordes (2018), 9)

What is important to note for this kind of analysis is the issue of ‘internal coverage.’ Internal coverage is a measure that “equals the percentage of cited references by a unit of analysis that points to publications covered by the WoS” (CWTS, 12) and is used to estimate how likely it is that a given research unit produces outputs that are covered by the WoS. If this value is very low, then it can be expected that a research unit is producing outputs that are not covered by the WoS. As a consequence, insights gained in the analysis would have limited value.

The internal coverage for Austria is at 46%, meaning that 46% of the references in educational research publications from Austria are covered by the WoS. This is not too low, but also not very high and needs to be considered in the interpretation of the results.

As CWTS puts it:

“it can be considered that the internal coverage is sufficiently good to perform this bibliometric analysis and it can provide important insights on the research performance in the field of Educational Sciences as well as it brings the opportunity of comparing the performance of the various countries. However, bearing in mind the internal coverage, it is also important to consider that some important research developments in this scientific domain are probably not fully captured by our study.” (ibid. 12)

5.2. Outcomes and insights

Overall, the output numbers when counted in total publications are rather low. However, the size-independent indicators draw a somewhat more positive picture, although Austrian educational research is still outperformed by most other countries. The Netherlands, in particular, performs very well according to these indicators.

The CWTS study identifies five key players in the Austrian educational research community based on the number of scientific and scholarly publications. These are the University of Vienna, the University of Graz, the University of Salzburg, Johannes Kepler University of Linz and the University of Innsbruck.

While the University of Vienna produced the most publications ($P=144$), the University of Salzburg had the highest number of publications in the top 10% most cited publications worldwide (22%). All the others are slightly below 10% of publications among the top 10% most cited publications worldwide. When it comes to normalised indicators, the University of Salzburg (MNCS = 1.56) and the University of Graz (MNCS = 1.09) are performing above world average (1.00). The fact that all the five key players identified by the study are universities shows that a substantial part of educational research in Austria (as visible through such performance indicators) is conducted by universities.

Figure 1: Output (P) and impact (MNCS) for the top 5 key players (2000-2016) in the field of educational research (Courtesy of CWTS Leiden)

5.2.1. Publication output

The overall publication count (full counting) for Austrian educational research shows 522 publications from 2000-2016. In comparison, Germany had 6,557 publications and the United Kingdom had 21,650 publications during the same time period.

Table 7: Publication output, the percentage of publications in educational research within the total scientific and scholarly output (%) and the internal coverage for the field Educational Sciences per country (2000–2016) (full counting)

Country	Publications	Publications per Million Population	% of Country's Total Publications
Austria	522	59	0.28%
Belgium	2,043	180	0.74%
Denmark	778	135	0.38%
Finland	1,891	344	1.12%
Germany	6,557	79	0.45%
Netherlands	5,912	345	1.19%
Norway	1,622	305	1.08%
Sweden	2,423	239	0.71%
Switzerland	1,210	143	0.34%
United Kingdom	21,650	328	1.39%

Since output numbers as such are not very meaningful, the study also looked at the relative output of educational research units, i.e., the share of educational research output in the total scientific and scholarly output of a country.

Here, we can see that in Austria, educational research represents 0.28% of the total publication output in the period from 2000-2016. This is the lowest percentage of all the countries covered by CWTS. In comparison, the Netherlands have a share of 1.19% and the United Kingdom (again with the highest number) a share of 1.39%.

5.2.2. Citation impact analysis

When we move from total output numbers to size-independent indicators (MNCS, MNJS and PP (top 10%)), the picture changes.

When it comes to the Mean Normalized Citation Score (MNCS), Austria's score is slightly below world average (1.00). The Netherlands perform better (1.26) than the other countries according to this indicator, and Germany and Switzerland slightly below Austria. The picture drawn by the MNJS is quite similar. Again, Austria's performance is a bit below world average, but slightly better than that of Germany and Switzerland. The Netherlands, Belgium and the UK score best.

The share of publications of Austrian educational research units that are among the top 10% most cited publications is at 9% and thus again quite similar to Germany and Switzerland (9% each).

Table 8 gives an overview of these indicators in the field of educational research for the different countries.

Table 8: Bibliometric indicators for the field educational research per country (2000-2016) (Courtesy of CWTS Leiden)

Unit	P	MNCS	MNJS	PP (top 10%)
Austria	522	0,9	0,86	9%
Belgium	2043	1,1	1,06	11%
Denmark	778	0,9	0,93	7%
Finland	1891	0,97	0,97	9%
Germany	6557	0,84	0,81	8%
Netherlands	5912	1,26	1,19	14%
Norway	1622	1	0,97	9%
Sweden	2423	0,96	0,96	7%
Switzerland	1210	0,87	0,85	8%
United Kingdom	21650	1,05	1,02	10%

What can be seen from this analysis is that Austria scores low in terms of overall publication output compared to the other benchmark countries, but has similar scores as Denmark, Finland, Germany, Sweden and Switzerland when it comes to the citation indicators. Austria has, as most of the benchmark countries, a MNCS close to 1 (i.e., world average).

Looking at Austria's numbers in terms of thematic and personnel clusters, the following picture emerges:

- 522 publications received 5,360 citations (on average, 10.8 per publication) with 15% self-citations
- 16% of the papers received no citations
- 56% of the citations came from various authors/groups that have very few publications. This means that no specific thematic priorities can be identified.
- 44% of all citations came from five groups in Austria. These are research groups from the University of Salzburg (Dyslexia, Reading Abilities, Child Development), the University of Vienna (Educational Psychology and Evaluation) the University of Graz (Educational Psychology), the Medical University of Graz (Phoniatrics) and the Technical University of Graz (Educational Technology).
- Of these 44%, 62% of the citations were obtained from a research group of the psychology department of the University of Salzburg.

The table below summarizes the results for five 'key players' along the different performance indicators.

Table 9 Performance Indicators for the Top 5 universities in the field of educational research (Courtesy of CWTS Leiden)

Key Players	P	MNCS	MNJS	PP(top 10%)
University of Vienna	144	0,69	0,80	7%
University of Graz	68	1,09	0,90	9%
University of Salzburg	49	1,56	1,11	22%
Johannes Kepler University of Linz	40	0,74	0,76	6%
University of Innsbruck	31	0,53	0,71	6%

In regard to the number of publications among the top 10% most cited publications worldwide, the University of Salzburg reached the highest score (22%). The other institutions all score slightly below 10% of publications among the top 10% most cited publications worldwide. In terms of MNCS, the University of Salzburg and the University of Graz perform above world average.

What becomes visible here is that the performance of educational research in Austria in terms of citations tends in international journals to concentrate on a few internationally visible research groups and a small number of specialised fields such as educational psychology.

In addition to the analysis of the main bibliometric indicators, CWTS also performed some extra analysis to provide some context to the previous findings. In particular, they looked into the issue of publications in languages other than English.

Table 10: Bibliometric indicators for the field of educational research per country for English publications (EN) and publications in other languages (Other), (2000-2016)

Country	Language	P	MNCS	PP (top 10%)	MNJS
Austria	EN	446	1.02	10%	0.96
Austria	Other	76	0.32	2%	0.35
Belgium	EN	1,967	1.13	11%	1.10
Belgium	Other	76	0.21	2%	0.25
Denmark	EN	775	0.90	7%	0.94
Denmark	Other	3	0.00	0%	0.04
Finland	EN	1,883	0.97	9%	0.97
Finland	Other	8	0.61	13%	0.73
Germany	EN	4,119	1.20	13%	1.15
Germany	Other	2,438	0.33	2%	0.33
Netherlands	EN	5,741	1.29	14%	1.23
Netherlands	Other	171	0.11	0%	0.11
Norway	EN	1,611	1.00	9%	0.98
Norway	Other	11	0.43	0%	0.37
Sweden	EN	2,415	0.96	7%	0.96
Sweden	Other	8	0.09	0%	0.09
Switzerland	EN	935	1.09	10%	1.05
Switzerland	Other	275	0.30	1%	0.33
United Kingdom	EN	21,584	1.05	10%	1.02
United Kingdom	Other	66	0.20	3%	0.18

This table shows that there is a significant number of non-English publications in Austria, Germany and Switzerland. Furthermore, if only the English publications from those countries were included, the citation impact would increase for all countries, but especially for Germany. This result points to a publication culture that values German-speaking research output and has a smaller share of English-language publications.

5.3. Main results

The main results from the bibliometric study can be summarised as follows:

- Educational research in Austria is underrepresented in international journals compared to other disciplines in Austria as well as compared to other countries.
- The citation impact of the publications from Austria is good, roughly at the level of most other countries, but well below the level of NL, BEL and UK.

- Researchers from Austria, Germany and Switzerland publish far more frequently in non-English, mostly German-language journals than researchers in other countries. This reduces the international citation impact significantly.²²
- The University of Salzburg has by far the highest impact in Austria. This is due to the strong internationally oriented cognitive and developmental psychology department in Salzburg.²³

²² Note: Due to the size of the German-speaking area, it is much more likely that German-language journals are listed in Web of Science than journals from small countries with small language groups.

²³ While some articles of the Salzburg Group are indexed in educational research journals, these researchers often assign their research projects exclusively to the field of psychology and not to educational research (see Appendix).

6. Issues, strengths and challenges I: In-depth interviews

To add a more contextualised perspective to the bibliometric analysis and in order to integrate the views of educational researchers on the strengths and weaknesses of their field, an interview study²⁴ and an online survey were conducted. Of course, one has to take into account that interviews, in particular, refer to the self-perception of the interviewed persons. The Technopolis Group Austria was commissioned to conduct interviews and an online survey.

6.1. Methodological approach and study design

Technopolis Austria conducted 22 in-depth interviews with professionals working in educational research in Austria. The interviews were guided by lead questions, whereas the order of questions varied depending on the interview dynamic. The interviews were between one and two hours long and were held in person, by Skype or by telephone.

The content of this study includes 22 in-depth interviews with participants from the area of educational research on their observations and thoughts on educational research in Austria. In contrast to standardised interviews, in-depth interviews enable the specific situation of those interviewed to be addressed flexibly by inviting the interviewee to reflect on his or her own experiences instead of simply giving information. They can also focus on key issues themselves, and the interviewer can ask in detail about topics that only come up during the interview. The FWF provided Technopolis with a list of potential interviewees, which covered the different thematic areas of educational research in Austria as well as its geographical and institutional landscape. The table below shows the intended targets and how they were met.

Table 11: Quantitative criteria to ensure the right balance among the group of participants interviewed (Courtesy of Technopolis Group)

Criterion	Values achieved	Goal achievement and comment
At least 40% women and men	12 women (55%), 10 men (45%)	Target value achieved
Age: Approx. 25% <45 years old	3 participants under 45 (14%)	Target value not achieved The selection list included 7 persons under 45. Of these, two persons declined because of time reasons, and two could not be reached despite several attempts to do so.
Region: Approx. 50% outside of Vienna	6 participants in Vienna (27%), 14 participants outside of Vienna (64%), 2 people abroad (9%)	Target value achieved
Approx. 1/3 not from universities	14 participants from universities (64%), 8 participants from Univ. Coll. of TE, non-university research institutes, ministries (36%)	Target value achieved

²⁴ Tiefenthaler B., Warta, K. (2018): Determining the Status of Austrian Education Research. Background Report: Interviews. Technopolis Group.

6.2. Outcomes and insights

Overall, educational researchers were keen to participate in the discourse about their field. The working conditions for educational research in Austria are perceived as complicated; interviewees spoke more about difficulties than about strong points and achievements. In that sense, “more weak points than strong points” was the general opinion in most interviews. However, some of the weak points can also be understood to have dormant potential or be on the way to improvement through ongoing developments (e.g., with the university colleges of teacher education).

Educational research in Austria is described as small, fragmented and shaped largely by innovative, dedicated individuals:

“I get the impression that individual, very dedicated people work here, under framework conditions that make it difficult to be competitive in the international comparison.”

Some of these researchers are recognised on an international level, but they are mostly older. The development of educational research in recent years is regarded positively; however, there are hardly any thematic areas that are institutionally well-anchored areas. In general, the interviews suggest that from the perspective of educational researchers there are few specific strong points in Austrian educational research compared to other countries.

6.2.1. Strengths

The interviewees do, however, indicate several strong points of the Austrian educational research landscape.

On a national policy level, the new research orientation of the university colleges of teacher education was mentioned as a strong point together with the “axiomatic access to and connection with practical application.”²⁵ This shows that the role of university colleges of teacher education within the Austrian educational research landscape is a topic of debate.

Research-wise, the interviewees also talked about larger projects that have been conducted more recently. These projects, so they argue, have provided Austrian educational research with a development impetus while at the same time bolstering cooperation. These projects included development projects, participation in major international studies and the national education report (NBB), published by BIFIE.

More generally, good relations between research and the education administration were mentioned as a strength of Austrian educational research.

²⁵ Tiefenthaler B., Warta, K. (2018): Determining the Status of Austrian Education Research. Background Report: Interviews. Technopolis Group, p. 5

Overall, there is a sense that empirical educational research has developed positively in recent years and the research orientation has increased on the whole. In this regard, the reform of the university colleges of teacher education is considered to have played an important role. When talking about the institutional structure of educational research, the interviewees mentioned the Austrian Association of Research and Development in Education (ÖFEB – Österreichische Gesellschaft für Forschung und Entwicklung im Bildungswesen) as a positive aspect. According to them, this institution allows for good networking opportunities.

Additionally, university research has developed positively in the last 20 years. In particular, the interviewees mentioned application-oriented contract research and the demand-side at universities, thus bringing their research closer to advisory and consulting activities. Parts of the administration played an important role in the positive development here.

In terms of publication venues, the “Zeitschrift für Bildungsforschung” (established in 2011 and published by Springer) was mentioned as it has added another option for scholarly publication.

In the area of non-university research institutions, the establishment of the BIFIE was rated positively. It was seen as playing a key role and performing important tasks, especially in terms of conducting major international studies, generating the data associated with them and producing the national education report:

“I think the national education reports are strong points. They bring key researchers together in teams time and again and provide a very good overview. At the same time and despite its quality, the report has no effect on practice or policy.”

This quote shows nicely how the interviewees shifted between the strengths and the challenges of Austrian educational research. While the NBB is described as a ‘strong point’ and an opportunity for sparking collaboration, the seeming lack of impact is criticised at the same time.

On an individual level, the interviewees acknowledged a high level of know-how and commitment on the part of individual researchers. This is considered especially noteworthy given the difficult framework conditions. When it came to particular areas in which Austrian researchers have been able to increase their profiles nationally and internationally, the participants especially mentioned participatory research methods and action research as well as school development research.

6.2.2. Challenges and weaknesses

Somewhat in contrast to these more positive assessments, educational research in Austria is described as being weakly structured on a national scale. The interviewees stated—and this mirrors to some extent the results of the bibliometric study—that Austrian educational research is not well-connected internationally and therefore its participation in the international discourse in terms of publications is also weak. One explanation that pops up in

the interviews is that there seems to be a particular publication culture in educational research focusing on monographs or edited volumes and in German: *“edited versions and compendium culture”*.

Additionally, there is a strong orientation towards the German-speaking area, i.e., Germany and Switzerland. There are few researchers with an international focus (e.g., the Netherlands, Scandinavia, the Balkans or the British-Anglo-American sphere). One interviewee put this perceived lack of international activity in quite dramatic terms stating: *“I don’t meet many other Austrians at conferences.”*

Some statements in the interviews also hint at the possibility that interesting work is sometimes not published at all in internationally visible journals or presented at conferences.

While the bibliometric analysis draws a similar picture, the interviews provide an insight into some of the reasoning from within the Austrian educational research community.

The main explanation on a national level refers to the funding structure in Austria. The interviewees underscored that there are few third-party funding sources available for educational research. The situation was often compared to Germany or Switzerland, where specific funding is available. Additionally, they pointed to the limited institutional funds for international activities when talking about difficulties in setting up and maintaining international contacts.

Taken together, this makes it particularly difficult to establish long-term projects that aim at building up the research infrastructure, develop junior staff and engage in application-oriented (collaborative) research or international projects. One interviewee stated:

“The insufficient breadth is a big problem. This is linked with the country’s small scale, but especially with the fact that there are no large, specific research programmes. In Germany, for example, there are these large-scale education research programmes with numerous tenders for researchers and support for junior staff—there is no equivalent in Austria”.

In addition, there is a perception that public funds for contract research have decreased sharply in recent years. The awarding of funds is criticised as not being transparent: these funds often appear to be awarded on the basis of personal relationships, and rarely on the basis of clear, competitive procedures according to comprehensible criteria and expertise. This discriminates against young research talents, as this type of contract awarding almost always favours established individuals.

In sum, these framework conditions on a national level are considered to make it hard to have ‘path-finder’ projects or to create particular stimuli for educational research in Austria.

When it comes to the institutional structure of educational research, the interviewees stated that in contrast to other countries, there are no big, visible, powerful groups or units; for the most part, only the above-mentioned excellent individuals are visible, which means that there

is little institutional profiling. In relation to that, the interviewees also talked about a lack of structures for research groups and little systemic collaboration on research projects.

This leads to a number of problematic issues: first, the development of junior staff and talent becomes difficult since there is a lack of qualified researchers to support them; and second, research topics are at risk of being neglected when certain individuals retire, which again is problematic for developing particular focus areas in Austrian educational research.

The research capacities of university colleges of teacher education and their connections with the scientific and scholarly community have grown, but, on the whole, are still relatively weak. Their legal form as a lower-level agency of the Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research is no advantage for their development as research institutions, particularly due to the legally specified structures and employment legislation. The resources available for research are low, while teaching responsibilities are high. The development of research capacities is a request that comes up in the interviews; however, there is an awareness (coming from experience) that such a process will take time:

“After ten years development work, we now have the first international publications and appearances at international conferences.”

Universities face the challenge that there are few long-term research priorities in education research. Furthermore, staffing numbers are low, and the career prospects for junior staff scientists are often unattractive, i.e., lots of researchers working under precarious conditions:

“It is increasingly more difficult for researchers. Stress limits are exceeded with many researchers. There are increasingly more students, but university staff is not increasing appropriately.”

Almost all the interviewees believe the transfer of scientific and scholarly findings to practical application, both to the educational institutions and players in educational practice and to the administrative and political decision-makers, is difficult for different reasons: in the interviews, limited transfer possibilities are mentioned, current government policy is described as problematic and finally the low importance seemingly attributed to transfer on the academic side in contrast to the focus on science. There are, however, positive transfer experiences, especially with researchers that (also) work in an application-oriented way and at a regional level.

One of the fundamental issues that came up in the interviews is the low appreciation for educational research among politicians, public administration and in public debates on education-related issues. This is considered problematic with regard to the long-term development and institutionalisation of educational research.

“Transfer is only promoted at the normative level but receives practically no appreciation! This is clearly different in Germany, for example.”

“Oh yeah ..., EVERYONE is an expert in the public debate!”

6.2.3. Key players

The assessment of the interviewees about who are the key players in the field of educational research in Austria largely overlaps with the results from the bibliometric study: the Universities of Vienna, Salzburg, Graz, Innsbruck, Linz and Klagenfurt are mentioned.

Institutions with unique structural features are also understood as key players (not necessarily captured by the bibliometric indicators), especially BIFIE, the four development networks, the Austrian Association for Education Research and Development (ÖFEB) and the Austrian Educational Competence Centres (AECC). There is also a series of mostly non-university players, who are established in sub-areas of education research, often in a predominantly advisory capacity: the “Institut für Höhere Studien” (IHS), the “Wirtschaftsforschungsinstitut” (WIFO) and the “Institut für Bildungsforschung der Wirtschaft” (ibw). The report states that “[i]ndividual interviewees also said that players that do not perform research themselves play or have played a decisive role, especially as principals or business partners, which include players from federal or state level education administration.”²⁶

And finally, the interviewees also talked about the university colleges of teacher education, whereby their contribution to educational research is still rather small. They are regarded as key in the sense that they could provide valuable input in terms of ‘transfer’ and applied research.

6.2.4. Potential for innovation

The main element or measure that was proposed throughout the interviews was specific funding. This, in the view of the interviewees, would allow for the further development of educational research.

“Specific funding!”

“Stimuli must be provided to unite the people that were previously battling away alone, to address problems, where it can only be done together.”

More concretely, such funding should

- enable the setting of long-term key priorities;
- promote and support cooperation, especially across and beyond the various institution types and locations and between science and practical application;
- be awarded in competition via a fair and transparent selection process;
- offer possibilities for specific and structured junior staff support;
- include applied research, structured promotion of junior staff and stronger international connections;

²⁶ Tiefenthaler B., Warta, K. (2018): Determining the Status of Austrian Education Research. Background Report: Interviews. Technopolis Group, p. 12

- be awarded both for thematically open projects with structural goals and in tenders with core priorities, especially for current research requirements;
- support both the participation in the international discourse and the work on specific problem solutions;
- and enable research and development projects over their different phases and over longer periods of time.

The future development of the university colleges of teacher education towards becoming actual research-active universities was an issue throughout the interviews. Despite clear weak points of the current situation, the interviewees felt that there was major innovation potential here, especially for development-oriented educational research. The current legal framework as a lower-level agency (“nachgeordnete Dienststelle”) of the Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research (BMBWF) was considered a disadvantage and should thus be reformed to allow for increased research activity.

The access to and use of available data should also be further improved. This includes better access to available data and its more systematic use. This primarily applies to data from the major studies such as PISA, TIMSS, etc., but other data as well. There is also much potential for research in a more systematic, collaborative establishment of good cohorts and data records and the use of existing data.

Finally, almost all those interviewed suggested concentrating more specific work on the connection between research and practical application. They suggested that activities of this kind should be made an explicit part of the range of tasks of university researchers, and many therefore also called for a rethinking of how scientific and scholarly work can be combined with an orientation towards societal relevance:

“How can we make the theory-practice transfer more feasible? How can we motivate teachers more for research? There’s no use being at the international top if society doesn’t benefit. Studies that no one can read have never been any use.”

6.3. Main results

- Educational research in Austria is small and fragmented and shaped largely by innovative, dedicated individuals.
- There is no specific funding from the responsible Federal Ministry in Austria. This is perceived as a contrast to Germany and Switzerland, and alternative funding options are scarce. Consequently, it is difficult to conduct infrastructure-forming, long-term projects, to invest in the systematic promotion of junior staff, and to develop application-oriented (cooperative) research and international collaborations.
- At the universities, there are few long-term research priorities in educational research, and staffing numbers are low in some areas, such as teaching methodology, elementary and primary level, and university research, for example.
- Strengths mentioned in the interviews include good networking via the Austrian Association for Education Research and Development (ÖFEB) and between research

and the education administration as well as the new research orientation of the university colleges of teacher education.

- A fundamental weakness according to the interviewees is the low level of appreciation of educational research. Structural weaknesses and problems with the development of junior staff are regarded as a consequence of this.
- The framework conditions for research for the university colleges of teacher education (i.e., their legal form as a lower-level agency of the Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research) are considered to be obstructive and should be reformed.
- The most important measures mentioned in the interviews are:
 - Specific competitive funding dedicated to educational research (including applied research), which would allow for the setting of long-term key priorities.
 - The systematic promotion of junior staff and stronger international connections.
 - The access to and use of available data should be further improved.
 - The connection between research and practical application is considered a particular feature of educational research and needs to be improved.

7. Issues, strengths and challenges II: Online survey

Building on the insights gained in the interview study, Technopolis also conducted an online survey.²⁷ The survey was constructed in collaboration with the FWF and ÖWR and conducted between December 2018 and February 2019.

7.1. Methodological approach and study design

The online survey was distributed using a snowball system, i.e., it was e-mailed to 120 persons in leading positions at their institutions (e.g., heads of university departments, rectors of university colleges of teacher education and directors of research institutes), who were asked to complete the questionnaire and to forward it to other researchers in their teams or at partner institutions. The aim of this procedure was to cover the whole spectrum of thematic and institutional diversity.

The survey addressed a range of different questions, ranging from funding sources, thematic foci, their own research and dissemination practices, their views on educational research in Austria and recommendations for improving the current state. It does not claim to be representative, as the population of educational researchers in Austria cannot be determined. Together with the other data and interviews, however, the survey provides a sound basis for assessing the status and potentials for development of educational research in Austria.

Overall, the questionnaire was completed by 253 persons in total, 115 (55.3%) of which are based at a university college of teacher education, 78 (37.5%) are researchers at public universities and 4 persons (1.9%) are employed at universities and non-university research organisations respectively. The most common form of employment among the respondents was a permanent contract (up to 67.1%), and 30% stated that they have a fixed-term contract.

²⁷ Calatrava Moreno, M.C., Tiefenthaler, B. (2019): Determining the Status of Austrian Education Research. Background Report: Online Survey. Technopolis Group.

7.2. Outcomes and insights

7.2.1. Funding and funding sources

46% of the respondents indicated that they have received third-party research funding in the last 5 years, while 48% stated that they have not received third-party funding (see Figure 2). A look at the different institutional backgrounds shows that 56% of the respondents who work at public universities and 45% of the individuals working at university colleges of teacher education have received third-party funding. 6% of the respondents either did not know or did not provide an answer.

Figure 2: Proportion of recipients of third-party funding in the last five years (Courtesy of Technopolis Group)

Among those that did not receive third-party research funding, 64% did not apply for any grants, and 8% had their proposals rejected. 13% stated that there were other reasons for not receiving third-party funding.

As shown in Figure 3 below, the respondents were also asked to indicate potential reasons for not receiving third-party funding or for not applying. Not enough time (73%), not enough experience (66%) and too much effort in relation to the potential gain given a high risk of rejection (58%) were important reasons selected by the participants.

Figure 3: Opinion on research funding of respondents who have not received third-party research funding in the last five years (Courtesy of Technopolis Group)

Six participants further elaborated on the reasons that make third-party research funding unattractive stating that they had not received sufficient information or had felt they did not meet the requirements, that there are no proper opportunities for certain subjects (e.g., applied didactics), or that support channels were terminated (e.g., the Sparkling Science programme). Three of these respondents stated that third-party funding is not attractive for researchers working at university colleges of teacher education as it is not possible to hire project-specific personnel. This issue had already been mentioned in the in-depth interviews.

The main sources of third-party funding are the Federal Ministry of Education, which was named by 38.3% of the respondents as one of their most important sources in the last five years, and federal state authorities, which were selected by 31.3% of the survey participants.

Looking at the funding sources in relation to the hosting institution (i.e., public university or university college of teacher education) of the responding individuals draws an interesting picture.

The Federal Ministry of Education is named as the main source of funding by individuals working at public universities. And while the respondents working at university colleges of teacher education also receive funding from the Federal Ministry of Education, they seem to have a significantly higher share of projects funded by federal state authorities. This might be explained by the educational competencies of the Austrian provinces. Additionally, the European Framework Programme for Research and the Austrian Science Fund are each mentioned by 25% of the respondents affiliated to public universities, and by 12% of the respondents from university colleges of teacher education as funding sources. One

explanation for this discrepancy might be that the research mission of the latter is relatively young and hence they are not yet fully competitive with regard to basic research.

Figure 4: Respondents' main source of third-party funding in the last five years (Courtesy of Technopolis Group)

7.2.2. Output and dissemination

90.5% of the respondents stated that they had been published within the last five years. A comparison of responses by type of institution shows that 86% of the respondents working at public universities and 95% of those working at university colleges of teacher education have published research results in the last five years (Figure 6).

Figure 5: Publication activity of survey respondents in public universities and university colleges of teacher education (Courtesy of Technopolis Group)

These results can be further qualified by looking at the type of publication language and format. The main publication language is German: more than 120 respondents indicated that they publish 80-100% of their publications in German while around 60 respondents (the majority in this language group) stated that up to 20% of their output is published in English. This self-assessment resonates with the findings of the bibliometric study presented in Section 4, which indicated a publication culture valuing German-language research outputs.

Figure 6: Participants' share of publications in different languages

The most common forms of publication are peer-reviewed journals and edited volumes. The majority of participants have published in such a format and most participants did so several times. In contrast, while more than half of the respondents have also written monographs, this was done only on a few occasions (e.g. theses).

Figure 7: Formats of respondents' publications in the past five years (Courtesy of Technopolis Group)

What's interesting to note is that the respondents from both public universities and university colleges of teacher education stated that their main field of activity was applied research, while only a few saw their work as basic research.

Figure 8: Type of research activity of respondents in different kinds of institutions (Courtesy of Technopolis Group)

7.2.3. Challenges and perspectives

The participants were also asked to share their view on the overall situation of educational research in Austria by assessing their degree of agreement with a number of statements.

Implementing infrastructure-forming, long-term projects is seen as one of the core challenges for educational research in Austria. 74.3% fully or rather agreed with this statement. Furthermore, funding was identified as a core challenge with 71.5% agreeing that educational research is lacking funding. Related to that, the possibilities for supporting early-stage researchers were also considered problematic. Other issues that the respondents

tended to agree with were research transfer and the overall appreciation of educational research in Austria with 71.5% of respondents fully or rather agreeing with this statement.

Figure 9: Participants' opinions on educational research in Austria (Courtesy of Technopolis Group)

The participants were also asked to assess some of the options and potential strategies for the future development of educational research in Austria.

The survey respondents agreed with most of the strategies. However, the statements that received the highest rates of approval referred to funding: 91.6% considered 'better conditions for education research within the existing framework' very or rather important, and 91.1% of the respondents tended to agree with the option 'special research funding for education research.' The foundation of large, non-university institutes (e.g., modelled on the examples of the Max Planck Society or the Leibniz Association in Germany), on the other hand, did not receive much approval. The respondents disagreed on whether such an institution would strengthen Austrian educational research (45.6% agreed—33.6% disagreed).

Figure 10: Participants' opinions on the importance of measures for the positive development and strengthening of educational research in Austria (Courtesy of Technopolis Group)

When it comes to measures for strengthening the link between education and practice (Figure 10), more funding for different activities was the top priority. Statements about funding for knowledge transfer, research cooperation and educational research itself were considered very or rather important by more than 86%. Communication training as a measure did not receive high approval and was thus considered as less important compared to the other measures proposed.

Figure 11: Participants' opinion on the importance of measures to strengthen the link between educational research and practice (Courtesy of Technopolis Group)

7.3. Main results

The views expressed on the state and development of educational research in Austria confirm the findings from the interviews with regard to:

- Struggles to implement structure-forming long-term projects in educational research
- A lack of funding for the development of educational research and for proper support of young researchers
- Difficulties with the transfer of research results into the education administration and politics
- Low appreciation and reputation of educational research in politics and society.

Some issues were considered to be more controversial:

- Reasons for lack of competitiveness, e.g., whether educational research in Austria is too small and fragmented to be internationally competitive
- With regard to the networking activities of educational professionals and whether this is a strength
- Concerning the transfer of research results into educational institutions

8. Recommendations of the Panel

Building on the different reports (see the Appendix), the international evaluation panel developed the following recommendations during two workshop meetings in Vienna that have taken place on 10 October 2018 and 4 April 2019. These recommendations address different levels of the educational research system: the policy level, the institutional level and the level of the individual researcher. Furthermore, they are structured along different areas of activity.

First and foremost, the panel recommends the development of a policy strategy, on the basis of which dedicated funding programmes should be designed and implemented that go along with fitting concepts and modes of monitoring and evaluation. This structure would allow for (1) more transparency and (2) for making visible the already existing strengths and capacities of educational research in Austria.

On a **national level**, the panel recommends the implementation of a steering group consisting of both national and international experts. Members should be recruited at least from the BMBWF, FWF, ÖWR, and Universities Austria (uniko) together with leading international experts. This steering committee would have both national and international legitimacy and could continue the work started by this panel.

The primary goal of this committee would be to develop a strategy for educational research that defines particular focus areas and priorities.

The report at hand can function as the empirical basis for developing such a strategy, which should address the following questions:

- d. What is already there, and where are the blind spots or gaps?
- e. Which areas of educational research should be funded and further developed? Which areas are less significant?
- f. Where is educational research headed on an international level? The trend towards more interdisciplinary research on education is also noticeable in Germany, e.g., the LEAD Graduate School & Research Network or the Institute for Educational Quality Improvement at the Humboldt University of Berlin.

One strategy for improving the capacities of educational research could be to further invest in longitudinal studies of children's progress and development across educational phases. While participatory research methods and action research are considered to be strengths of the Austrian educational research system, it would be appropriate to encourage and fund other approaches to extend the current strengths. For example, quantitative and mixed methods research approaches could be given some priority in future to broaden and strengthen the field of enquiry. Longitudinal studies, in particular, have been shown to have much policy significance and value in other countries, e.g., the Millennium Cohort Study (MCS) in the UK and the National Educational Panel Study (NEPS) in Germany. This could be related to broader topics such as health, equity, socio-emotional development as well as cognitive and academic outcomes. In light of current developments such as the climate crisis and the rise of populist movements in Europe, the role of education in developing and

nurturing 'democratic citizenship,' 'critical education' and not least education for 'sustainable development' is worth considering. The panel thus recommends considering the more normative discussion of education, going beyond an 'evidence-based' understanding.

The panel recommends the further development of national data sets, such as the National Pupil Database (NDP) in England, that could facilitate research on topics of particular relevance to schools. This could also address the current interest in equity linked to ethnicity, language, gender and social disadvantage. However, the panel recommends taking into account the education system as a whole from pre-school and general upper secondary/vocational education and training to universities and adult and popular education.

Such a strategy should also consider examples from other countries: which funding instruments exist in other countries? What works, and what can be adapted for Austria?

One possibility of building capacity is to create dedicated funding opportunities for educational research. Another option could be 'seed money' to give an impetus to educational research. Further steps could then involve moving towards creating 4 to 5 centres of excellence, each devoted to a specific topic and hosted by one of the top Austrian research universities. To avoid a devastating impact on the current educational professionals, every centre could have a small network of other researchers, for instance, in the best university colleges of teacher education. Universities hosting such a centre would have to commit to creating new chairs on the themes concerned.

Furthermore, the panel recommends counteracting the fragmentation of educational research funding and merging all resources of educational research into a single funding channel. The panel does not see a need to separate basic research from applied research (innovation), since educational research is per se an applied science.

In addition, the use of private funding through foundations or companies is recommended.

On the basis of this report, the panel acknowledges the strong ties between applied research and educational practice and recommends placing an emphasis on applied research while at the same time making efforts to strengthen the capacities for basic research in Austrian educational research.

The **research institutions** need to develop their own strategies of how to best develop the current window of opportunity.

- a. The expert panel explicitly recommends setting up collaborations between research groups both nationally and internationally. Educational research groups could take on the role as a junior partner or as the partner responsible for the application of results. In Vienna, for example, the "Institut für Bildungswissenschaft" has a clear educational pedigree (although some faculty come from other disciplines), but the Faculty of Psychology also houses a department for "Bildungspsychologie und Evaluation". It would be worthwhile elaborating on whether that would be a viable option for the future in supporting a transdisciplinary approach.

Education would then be regarded as the research subject in projects on educational

psychology, artificial intelligence, health sciences, computer sciences or sociology, for example.

- b. This goes hand in hand with developing strategies to build capacity for future funding opportunities such as an excellence initiative, which is currently in development. These strategies should include setting up research consortia or aiming for participating in already existing consortia and clusters. Capacity building also involves nurturing a new generation of educational researchers. This could involve launching ambitious doctoral programmes together with related postdoctoral positions and tenure track positions. The panel recommends focusing on candidates that are very young but have international experience.

On an **individual level**, the panel recommends focusing on both publication and collaboration strategies. The survey data shows that educational researchers still focus on books and reports. While this is a worthwhile endeavour in terms of policy impact on a local level, it should be accompanied by journal publications (peer-reviewed publications) that link Austrian educational research to international debates.²⁸

²⁸ In order to achieve the dual goal of high scholarly quality and wide dissemination outside the scientific and scholarly community, the FWF recommends publishing open access. The Austrian research institutions and the FWF provide a number of funds for this purpose, such as agreements with publishers and the coverage of publication costs.

9. Advisory Bodies

International Panel

Panel Chair - Professor Friedrich W. Hesse, IWM Tuebingen (Germany)

Professor Pia Cort, Aarhus University (Denmark)

Professor Bert Creemers, University of Groningen (Netherlands)

Professor Pam Sammons, University of Oxford (United Kingdom)

Professor Pierre Dillenbourg, EPF Lausanne (Switzerland)

Professor Daniel Muijs, Office for Standards in Education (United Kingdom)

Professor Kai Schnabel Cortina, University of Michigan (USA)

Professor Olga Zlatkin-Troitschanskaia, University of Mainz (Germany)

National Sounding Board

Professor Barbara Herzog-Punzenberger, University of Innsbruck

Professor Konrad Krainer, University Klagenfurt

Professor Jean-Luc Patry, University of Salzburg

Professor Manfred Prisching, University of Graz

Dr. Sybille Reichert, Reichert Consulting (Germany)

Professor Michael Schratz, University of Innsbruck

Professor Ilse Schrittmesser, University of Vienna

Professor Alan Scott, University of Innsbruck

10. Appendices

- Appendix 1: FWF funded projects from 2013-2017 in Educational Research
- Appendix 2: Possanner, N. (2018): Austrian higher education at a glance. Austrian Science Council.
- Appendix 3: Possanner, N. (2018): Common definitions—relevant numbers and data—developments in higher education policy in teacher education. Austrian Science Council.
- Appendix 4: Neijssel, M, Yegros, A., de Bordes, C. (2018): Research performance and benchmark analysis of Educational Sciences in Austria. CWTS Leiden
- Appendix 5: Tiefenthaler B., Warta, K. (2018): Determining the Status of Austrian Education Research. Background Report: Interviews. Technopolis Group
- Appendix 6: Calatrava Moreno, M.C., Tiefenthaler, B. (2019): Determining the Status of Austrian Education Research. Background Report: Online Survey. Technopolis Group.

FWF-funded projects from 2013 - 2017 in Educational Research

Annette KRAUSS	Art as Unlearning - Arts-based Research and Transcultural Education	Richter Programme	Academy of Fine Arts - Institute for Arts and Cultural Studies	€349,954	65.0% Arts, 25.0% Other Humanities, 10.0% Educational Research
Iris Elisabeth LANER	Aesthetic Practice and the Critical Faculty: Examining the Educational Conditions of Aesthetic Experience	Firnberg Programme	Academy of Fine Arts - Institute for Arts and Cultural Studies	€228,720	65.0% Philosophy, Ethics, Religion, 35.0% Educational Research
Sigrid EYB-GREEN	Leopold Kupelwieser's Fresco Series	Publication Costs	Academy of Fine Arts - Institute for Restoration and Conservation	€14,000	60.0% Arts, 30.0% History, Archaeology, 10.0% Educational Research
Matthew Raymond GARDINER	ORI* on aesthetics and language of folding and technology	Arts-based Research	Ars Electronica Linz GmbH	€246,068	50.0% Arts, 45.0% Other Technical Research, 5.0% Educational Research
Katharina FELLNHOFER	E-Ship-Stories: Initiative for Teaching Entrepreneurship	Schrödinger Programme	Lappeenranta University of Technology - School of Business and Management	€94,950	90.0% Economics, 10.0% Educational Research
Peter MARSCHIK	ICon-E: Initial Concerns Extended. Lessons from Fragile X Syndrome.	Top Citizen Science	Medical University Graz - Institute of Physiology	€48,097	70.0% Clinical Medicine, 20.0% Psychology, 10.0% Educational Research
Roland BERNHARD	Luther/the Reformation in international historical cultures	Publication Costs	Salzburg University of Education - Centre for History Didactics and Political Education	€10,000	35.0% Educational Research, 25.0% Philosophy, Ethics, Religion, 20.0% Other Humanities, 20.0% History, Archaeology
Sieglinde KLETTENHAMMER	South Tyrolian Literature: Zoderer in Focus. Research Transfer at the Literary Archive	Science Communication	University of Salzburg - Institute for German Studies	€49,560	50.0% Educational Research, 30.0% Linguistics and Literature, 20.0% Other Humanities
Christoph KÜHBERGER	Competence and Academic Orientation in History Textbooks	Stand Alone Project	University of Salzburg - History Department	€286,937	100.0% Educational Research
Michael WALLNER	Hanging Out with Mites - Allergy Research in Schools	Science Communication	University Salzburg - Institute of Molecular Biology	€40,587	60.0% Educational Research, 30.0% Clinical Medicine, 10.0% Media and

					Communication Research
Petra H. STEINER	The Subcultures and Social Worlds of Adult Education	Publication Costs	private	€10,000	85.0% Educational Research, 15.0% Sociology
Dietrich ALBERT	Facing the Threats of Virtual Echo Chambers in Schools!	Top Citizen Science	Technical University Graz - Institute for Knowledge Technologies	€50,293	50.0% Educational Research, 30.0% Psychology, 20.0% Computer Research
Natalia ARDILA-MANTILLA	Recognizing, Acknowledging. A Designing Music Learning Worlds	Publication Costs	University of Music and Performing Arts Vienna - Institute for Music Pedagogy	€16,000	90.0% Educational Research, 10.0% Sociology
Gianna HESSEL	Investigating learning among returning ERASMUS students	Meitner Programme	University of Graz - Institute for English Studies	€153,340	70.0% Linguistics and Literature, 15.0% Media and Communication Research, 15.0% Educational Research
Daniela HOLZER	Reading resistance to education negative-dialectically	Publication Costs	University of Graz -Institute for Education and Training Research	€18,000	75.0% Educational Research, 20.0% Philosophy, Ethics, Religion, 5.0% Sociology
Roland BERNHARD	Historical Myths about Hispanic America	Publication Costs	University Graz - History Department	€16,000	50.0% History, Archaeology, 25.0% Educational Research, 25.0% Other Humanities
Roland BERNHARD	Myths in German-Language History Textbooks	Publication Costs	University Graz - History Department	€10,000	50.0% Other Humanities, 50.0% Educational Research
Wolfgang WEIRER	Narrative Exegesis and Subject-oriented Biblical Didactics	Stand Alone Project	University of Graz - Institute for Catechetics and Religious Education	€332,537	50.0% Educational Research, 40.0% Philosophy, Ethics, Religion, 10.0% Linguistics and Literature
Reinhold ESTERBAUER	Bodytime - An interdisciplinary inquiry on regular body rhythm and its dysfunctions	Stand Alone Project	University of Graz Institute of Philosophy at the Faculty of Catholic Theology	€295,348	50.0% Philosophy, Ethics, Religion, 50.0% Educational Research
Andrea SCHIAVIO	Making Music Together	Meitner	University of Graz - Center for	€148,480	50.0% Educational Research, 50.0%

		Programme	Systematic Musicology		Psychology
Stefan MAYR	Plant Stories	Science Communication	University of Innsbruck - Institute of Botany	€49,329	60.0% Biology, 40.0% Educational Research
Erol YILDIZ	Political Literacy in Migration Society	International Project	University of Innsbruck - Institute for Educational Research	€289,201	50.0% Educational Research, 50.0% Sociology
Christof AICHNER	The reforms of the Austrian educational systems 1849-1860	Publication Costs	University of Innsbruck - Institute of History and European Ethnology	€18,000	50.0% History, Archaeology, 25.0% Educational Research, 25.0% Philosophy, Ethics, Religion
Pamela VRABL	Race against superbugs - when antibiotics stop working	Science Communication	University of Innsbruck - Institute of Microbiology	€49,916	60.0% Biology, 40.0% Educational Research
Ulrike TAPPEINER	EEcoS - Experiencing Ecosystem Services	Science Communication	University of Innsbruck - Institute for Ecology	€49,489	50.0% GeoResearch, 30.0% Biology, 20.0% Educational Research
Jean Luc PATRY	Pedagogical Tact	Stand Alone Project	Universität Salzburg - Institute for Educational Research	€264,285	80.0% Educational Research, 20.0% Psychology
Helga FASCHING	Cooperation for Inclusion in Educational Transitions	Stand Alone Project	University of Vienna - Institute for Educational Research	€285,379	100.0% Educational Research
Christian SWERTZ	Praxeologies and Homeostasis	Stand Alone Project	University of Vienna - Institute for Educational Research	€117,579	100.0% Educational Research
Margarita SCHIEMER	Education for children with Disabilities in Addis Ababa	Publication Costs	University of Vienna - Institute for Educational Research	€7,000	80.0% Educational Research, 10.0% Other Social Research, 10.0% Sociology
Machteld VENKEN	Talking borders. From Local Expertise to Global Exchange	Top Citizen Science	University of Vienna - Institute for Eastern European History	€50,094	40.0% Other Humanities, 30.0% History, Archaeology, 30.0% Educational Research
Thomas WEIß	Students arguments to creation and	Publication Costs	University of Vienna - Institute for	€14,000	60.0% Educational Research, 35.0%

	evolution		Religious Education		Sociology, 5.0% Biology
Philipp KLUTZ	The Discourse on Religious Education in Schools	Publication Costs	University of Vienna - Institute for Practical Theology	€16,000	100.0% Educational Research
Lana IVANJEK	Development of graph inventory	Meitner Programme	University of Vienna - Austrian Competence Center for Didactics of Physics	€102,708	100.0% Educational Research
Markus ARNDT	Simulated Interactive Research Experiments - Quantum@School	Science Communication	University of Vienna - Quantum Optics, Quantum Nanophysics, Quantum Information	€48,897	70.0% Educational Research, 30.0% Physics, Astronomy
Neda FORGHANI-ARANI	Learning to Teach in Uncertainty: A Phenomenological Study	Richter Programme	University of Vienna - Center for Teacher Education	€75,694	100.0% Educational Research
EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH				€1,880,000	

Austrian higher education at a glance¹

Austrian higher education comprises a broad variety of institutions and legal foundations: 22 public universities composed of comprehensive universities, technical universities, medical universities, and art universities; in addition to these there are specialised university institutions such as the technical university Leoben (Montanuniversität) and the University of Veterinary Medicine, Vienna. Furthermore, there exist 21 universities of applied sciences, 14 colleges of teacher education and 13 private universities. Compared with the universities of applied sciences and private universities, public universities account for the major part of post-secondary education in Austria. Altogether, 60 % of students are enrolled at public universities in Austria.

The most sought-after degree programmes at universities are: legal studies, economics and social sciences, business law, pedagogy, English and American Studies, computer sciences, biology, German Studies/philology, psychology and history. About two thirds of students attend 20 degree programmes.

Public universities

The number of students increased from about 200.000 (2002) to some 280.000 in 2016/2017. In recent years, the number of graduates is approximately 36.000 per year. The average expenditure per student is 12.000 €, per graduate 96.000 €. The share of higher education in GDP accounts for 1, 2% (about 5, 4% of federal expenditure), showing above-OECD-average expenditure (cf. University Report 2017).

Universities of applied sciences

It was not until in the mid 1990s, thereby later than in other European countries, that the sector of universities of applied sciences (Fachhochschule) was introduced in Austria. Today, there are about 40.000 publicly funded study places; about 10.000 study places are privately funded. For the future it is planned to further expand the sector by 450 study places a year; the focus being on STEM fields and extra-occupational degree programmes.

The most popular fields of study are economics and engineering (with about 20.000 students each), followed by health sciences (about 6.000 students) and social sciences (about 4.000 students). The rest is spread over sciences, security and risk studies, and art and design.

The amount of federal subsidies per study place is 7.000 - 9.000 €. Many institutions receive further grants from the respective sponsors, most of which are state governments.

Colleges of teacher education

In 2007, federal pedagogic academies were converted into colleges of teacher education (Pädagogische Hochschulen). To date, the colleges are subordinate departments of the Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research. The educational offer at the colleges includes primary school teaching profession, secondary level teaching profession (in cooperation with universities), and secondary level vocational education teaching profession. The reorganization of the training of educators represents a core educational project of recent years.

The new education of teachers includes the education and training of all persons who want to take up a pedagogical profession and was regulated by law in 2013. The implementation of the new pedagogical education has been taking place since the academic year 2016/17. The newly established universities of teacher education will endeavour in the coming years

¹ This text is a summary, prepared by Nikolaus Possanner (Office of the Austrian Science Board), based on the text "Skizze der österreichischen Hochschullandschaft" by Manfred Prisching (Austrian Science Board).

ÖSTERREICHISCHER WISSENSCHAFTSRAT

to build up their scientific competence in order to approach the internationally valid criteria of university formality. In order to ensure a high quality implementation of the new teacher education, mergers of universities and teacher training colleges took the form of four regional development networks. Within the networks, a standardization of curricula will be carried out and co-ed teacher studies will be offered for the secondary level.

Private universities

The newest sector of Austrian higher education is private universities laid down by law in 1999. The respective private university has to receive in the first place an accreditation of institution and of programmes. The 13 private universities offer more than 150 degree programmes, especially in the areas of social sciences, economics, legal studies, health sciences, theology, philosophy, arts and design, and music. In recent years, the sector recorded the highest growth rates. In 2017/2018 about 14.000 students are enrolled at private universities in Austria (a mere three percent of all students).

Distinctive profiles: universities and universities of applied sciences

In contrast to Germany, upon the establishment of universities of applied sciences applied research was an allocated task of the respective institutions. Through the years, this has resulted in some overlappings between both sectors of higher education. The anticipated idea of distinction along educational profiles has not yet materialised.

Therefore, the legislature is planning to facilitate collaboration among the two sectors and set up the project “The future of higher education institutions” (Zukunft Hochschule) issuing the range of tertiary education: 1) where possible, distinctive profiles shall lead to mutual cooperation in fields of programmes and research; though ensured by law, permeability should be facilitated by reducing administrative barriers; 3) universities and universities of applied sciences are allowed to set up joint studies (at BA and MA levels).

“Academization”

As about 30% of the Austrian population have a third level education (ISCED level 5-8) Austria is on European average; the inclusion of vocational colleges (berufsbildende höhere Schulen) in the statistics the share increases by nine percent. The OECD recommends that Austria seek to improve education opportunities to, therefore, increase the number of graduates.

Future Student Numbers

Over the next years, it is expected that the number of students will increase moderately. The main objective, though, is a gradual shift of number of students towards universities of applied sciences (medium-term: 30 percent; long-term: 60 percent), following the example of the Netherlands.

In this context, particular attention is paid to the development of dual degree programmes, extra-occupational degree programmes, and joint degree programmes.

Doctoral programmes

There are no particular access restrictions on doctoral programmes. Except for studies in scientific or technical fields, and medicine, the “classic” individual doctorate still is the common praxis. In recent years, structured doctoral programmes (“doctoral schools”) were introduced (in collaboration with other (international) universities).

Who studied and studies?

Degree programmes address the so called “normal student”: male, higher education entrance qualification, full-time studies, no professional activities, not having a family, career start after graduation. Having said this, the exception proves the rule: by now employed

ÖSTERREICHISCHER WISSENSCHAFTSRAT

persons, parents, senior students, students with non-formal education make up the majority at higher education institutions. While supporting measures exist, models for part-time studies do not exist, so far.

Higher education funding

Federal higher education expenditure totals 4.1 billion € in 2016 (3.5 billion euros go to universities). The proportion of third-party funds is steadily increasing, whereas donations and foundations are, in effect, hardly significant in Austria.

The national research quota of 3.2% of GDP (slightly more than 12 billion €) is over the EU-target of 3% by 2020. The quota comprises economic sector (about 50%) federal funds (one-third), federal provinces' funds (500 million €), municipalities, and about 2 billion € from abroad.

Tuition fees

Almost all universities of applied sciences charge tuition fees; only three institutions waive fees. The amount is regulated is 363.36 € per semester. Universities do not charge tuition fees. However, universities may charge fees for students who have studied longer than standard period of study. Private universities are not limited in any regarding the amount of tuition fees.

Research funding

In contrast to Germany, research funding is covered by two institutions:

The Austrian Science Fund (FWF): The FWF is the most important institution to support bottom-up basic research. The total budget for 2017 was 223 million €.

The Austrian Research Promotion Agency (FFG) is owned by Republic of Austria. The objective is to support industry-oriented research. The total budget for 2017 was 685 million €.

Governance

By the University Act 2002 Austrian universities were divested as independent entities and, therefore, were granted autonomy. They operate with a global budget, negotiated each three years as part of the performance agreements.

Project „Determination of the State of Educational Research in Austria“

Common definitions – relevant numbers and data – developments in higher education policy in teacher education

Office of the Austrian Science Board, February 2018

1. Definitions

Still today, publications in the field of educational research in the German-speaking world refer to the definition of the German Education Council from 1974. According to this definition, educational research is "the study of the prerequisites and possibilities of education and development processes in the institutional and social context". "One can interpret educational research in a broader and narrower sense. In the narrower sense, it has always existed as teaching research. In a broader sense, it can refer to whole education systems and its reform in the context of state and society, including out-of-school education processes." The definition of the Education Council was accompanied and shaped by efforts to reform education.

For Austria, there are no current surveys on the state of educational research. The most comprehensive and recent report is still the one from the Institute for Advanced Studies (IHS) from 2008. This report, in its definition of educational research, refers to the one used by the OECD in 1995. According to the authors, this definition is an open definition of educational research that takes into account the interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary aspects and acknowledges the interplay of basic research and application orientated research in the context of newer research in innovation studies.

The cited definition reads as follows: "*Educational research and development is a systematic, original investigation or inquiry and associated development activities concerning the social, cultural, economic and political contexts within which educational systems operate and learning takes place; the purposes of education; the processes of teaching, learning and personal development of children, youth and adults; the work of educators; the resources and organisational arrangements to support educational work; the policies and strategies to achieve educational objectives; and the social, cultural, political and economic outcomes of education.*"¹

A more detailed conceptual definition of the field occurs with the IHS study by the examination of the disciplines dealing with educational research (pedagogy and educational science, psychology, sociology, political science, economics, statistics, organizational and management studies, law, scientific didactics, etc.), through scientific and methodological goals, through the presentation of institutional contexts and the topics specifically dealt with by educational research.

The scientific and methodological objectives range from basic disciplinary research to various aspects of applied or application-oriented research and development to evaluation and implementation research. Institutionally, education sciences can be incorporated into universities and colleges,

¹ OECD (1995): Educational research and development: trends, issues and challenges, Paris 1995, p. 37.

state-controlled and funded agencies and into various types of non-university research organizations.²

2. Thematic Areas

Following the definition of the OECD itself, educational research is differentiated between seven thematic areas: social, cultural, economic and political contexts; objectives and purposes; processes of teaching, learning and personal development of children, adolescents and adults; the work of educators; resources and organizational arrangements; goal oriented policies and strategies; and social, cultural, economic and political results.³

The "classical" areas of educational research, such as those dealing with teaching, general didactics, subject didactics and learning, continue to be the most comprehensive areas of educational research. This is the result of a series of content analysis evaluations from 1998 to 2007 in German-speaking countries⁴.

In addition, vocational training, higher education and the education system are other focus areas. School research and pedagogy were also emphasized and furthermore the relevance of performance diagnostics, evaluation research and teaching-learning research was highlighted (in general areas that focus on improving the measurement of student performance, increased through the heightened educational policy interest in international comparisons)⁵.

Another survey conducted in 2010⁶, which set out to identify current trends and issues in educational research, concludes that the field of research has a great diversity and that a complete documentation of all aspects addressed in the context of educational research is not possible.

3. Educational Research in Austria – IHS Study 2008

The most current overview and assessment of achievements in educational research in Austria at the time of the study is illustrated by the IHS. The "newer developments" formulated at that time related to:

- International comparisons through Large Scale Assessments (LSA)
- Conversion of teacher education - in Austria there is a long controversial discussion about a science-oriented teacher education and educational universities with a research mandate (which should also act as a pillar of educational research)⁷

² See Lassnig, L. (2008): Bildungsforschung in Österreich als Ressource wissenschaftlicher Bildungspolitik und Schulentwicklung: Ist-Stand und Perspektiven für eine verbesserte Nutzung. IHS Input-Papier für NBB-2009-AutorInnengruppe, June 2008, p. 2f.

³ See OECD (1995): Educational research and development: trends, issues and challenges, Paris 1995.

⁴ See Botte, A. et al. (2015): Monitoring Bildungsforschung. Befunde aus dem Forschungsprojekt „Entwicklung und Veränderungsdynamik eines heterogenen sozialwissenschaftlichen Feldes am Beispiel der Bildungsforschung“. Klinkhardt: Bad Heilbronn.

⁵ Ibid., p. 8, 15.

⁶ Achatz, M. et al. (2010): Dokumentation von Forschungseinrichtungen. In: Tippelt, R. et al. (ed.): Handbuch Bildungsforschung. VS Verlag für Sozialwissenschaften: Wiesbaden.

⁷ With the entry into force of the Federal Framework Law on the introduction of new training for teachers in July 2013, the implementation phase for the new teacher training in Austria has begun. The sponsors of this training are the colleges of education and universities. Further information on teacher education NEW in chapter 6.

- Educational standards as objectified methodology of recording results and formalized models of quality assurance and quality development⁸

According to the IHS, Austria has no overview of the status quo and priorities in educational research. There have been some activities in this area in the past (Reisinger 1972, Machold/Posch/Thonhauser 1978, Lassnigg/Pechar/Huber 1994, Altrichter/Mayr 1999), as well as a publication on education research in general, which does not claim an inventory, but draws attention to important problems (Hackl/Pechar 2007) and an inventory for research in vocational and business education (Gramlinger/Schlögl/Stock 2007).⁹

The IHS report noted that through departmental research there are some connections between "political priorities and research."¹⁰ However, implementation in practice was almost non-existent or very slow¹¹. In addition, cumulative developments were rather not visible.

The connection between research and practice was then judged to be only partially given, "for the most part, research is rather too weak to give real impulses and the practical knowledge including points of interest is therefore stronger in the implementation - professional knowledge is in practice only very conditionally perceived as a value and authority over traditions, ideologies, points of interest and political day-to-day trends."¹²

Furthermore, it was found that the impulses from the LSA (Large Scale Assessments) so far were weak. The reasons given are the low level of participation in the projects and inadequate exploitation of opportunities due to a lack of accessibility, resources and competences.¹³

⁸ The introduction of educational standards in the Austrian education system was implemented in 2009 by a corresponding ordinance (BGBl. II No. 1/2009). In 2011, an amendment entered into force (BGBl. II No. 282/2011). See Lassnigg, L. (2008): Bildungsforschung in Österreich als Ressource wissenschaftlich gestützter Bildungspolitik und Schulentwicklung: Ist-Stand und Perspektiven für eine verbesserte Nutzung. IHS Input-Papier für NBB-2009-AutorInnengruppe, June 2008, pp. 10-11.

⁹ Ibid. p. 17.

¹⁰ Ibid. p.19.

¹¹ The current work program of the Austrian Federal Government includes projects such as the further development of pedagogy education, the creation of tertiary programs for the education of elementary teachers, new working time models for educators as well as obligatory regular training for teachers in lesson free times. See: <https://www.bundeskanzleramt.gv.at/regierungsdokumente>, p.59f (Access 15.2.2018).

¹² Ibid. p.19.

¹³ Ibid. p.19.

4. Institutions and Study Range in Educational Research and Educational Sciences¹⁴

Teaching and Research Institutions

University Research Institutes	Colleges of Teacher Education	Universities of Applied Science	Non-university Research Institutes (Selection)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alpen-Adria-University of Klagenfurt: Institute for Educational research • Danube University Krems – Department for Continuing Education Research and Educational Management • University of Graz – Institute of Educational Sciences • University of Innsbruck – Institute of Educational Sciences • University of Linz – Linz School of Education. Departement of Educational Research • University of Salzburg – Department of Educational Science • University of Wien – Department of Education • Vienna University of Economics and Business – Education Sciences Group 	<p>Network North-East</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • University College of Teacher Education Vienna • Pädagogische Hochschule Lower Austria • University College for Agrarian and Environmental Pedagogy • KPH Vienna/Krems <p>Network South-East</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • University College of Teacher Education Styria • Pädagogische Hochschule Kärnten • PH Burgenland • KPH Graz <p>Network Center</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Private University of Education, Diocese of Linz • PH Upper Austria • Salzburg University of Education Stefan Zweig <p>Network West</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pedagogical University Tyrol • PH Vorarlberg • KPH Edith Stein 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UAS Upper Austria – Science Field Educational Research • UAS Campus Vienna – Educational Research 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BIFIE – Federal Institute for Educational Research, Innovation and Development of the Austrian School System • IBW - Institute for Educational Research in Economics • ÖIBF – Austrian Institute for Vocational Education and Training • IHS – Institute for Advanced Studies • IBE – Research Institute for Vocational Training and Adult Education • oeib – Austrian Institute for Adult Education • WIAB – Viennese Institute for Labour Market and Education Research

¹⁴ Sources: Homepages of the mentioned institutions, Access: February 2018.

Study Range in the Area of Educational Science/Pedagogy

Universities	
<p>University of Vienna:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Education Science (Bachelor + Master): • Catholic Religious Pedagogy (Bachelor +Master) • Ethics for School and Vocation (Master) • Philosophy and Education Science (Doctorate) <p>Vienna University of Economics and Business:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business Education (Master) <p>Alpen-Adria-University of Klagenfurt:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Education Science (Bachelor) • Adult and Vocation Education (Master) • School Pedagogy (Master) • Social- und Integration Pedagogy (Master) • Philosophy – Areas: Pedagogy, Education Science, Adult and Vocation Education, School Pedagogy, Social- und Integration Pedagogy (Doctorate) <p>University of Innsbruck:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Education Science (Bachelor) • Education Science (Master) • Business Education (Master) • Catholic Religious Pedagogy (Bachelor +Master) • Philosophy – Education Science (PhD) • Education (PhD) <p>University of Salzburg:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pedagogy (Bachelor) • Education Science (Master) • Catholic Religious Pedagogy (Bachelor +Master) • Elementary Education (Master) • Nutrition and Household (Master) • Education Science /Pedagogy (Doctorate) • Pädagog/innenbildung (Pedagogy) at the School of Education (Doctorate) 	<p>University of Graz:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pedagogy (Bachelor) • Business Education (Bachelor) • Social Pedagogy (Master) • Adult und Further Education (Master) • Inclusive Education (Master) • Catholic Religious Pedagogy (Bachelor +Master) • Interdisziplinäre Doctorate – Education Science (PhD) • Humanistic Doctorate – Education Science (Doctorate) <p>University of Linz:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business Education (Diploma) • Pedagogy (Doctorate) <p>Danube University Krems:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Education and Vocation Consultation (Master) • Education, Vocation and Career Consultation (Master) • Education Management (Master) • Business Education (Master) • Educational Leadership – School Management (Master) • eEducation - eLearning & Social Media Learning (Master) • Gifted Education and Coaching – Talent Promotion and Coaching in Practice and Research (Master) • Action-oriented Media Pedagogy – Game-based approach to Youth Media Work (Master) • Higher Education and Research Management (Master) • MediaPlayPedagogy (Master) • Political Education (Master) • Professional Teaching and Training (Master) • Provocation Pedagogy (Master) • Research and Innovation in Higher Education (Master) • Talent Management und Promotion (Master) • Waldorf Pedagogy (Master)
Colleges of Teacher Education	Universities of Applied Sciences
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Private PH Linz in Cooperation with TU Dresden: Graduiertenkolleg Education & Technology (Doctorate) • KPH Vienna/Krems: Trauma Pedagogy (Master); Geragogics (Master) • PH Lower Austria: Mentoring (Master) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UAS St. Pölten in Cooperation with Saxion University of Applied Sciences: Social Pedagogy (Bachelor) • UAS St. Pölten: Sozial Pedagogy (Master) • UAS Campus Vienna: Social Management in Elementary Education (Bachelor) • UAS Carinthia: Pedagogy for Health Professions (Master) • IMC UAS Krems: Music Pedagogy (Master)

4. Numbers, Data and Facts (about students and researchers in the area of Education Sciences)

5.1 Research/Scientific Work

The existing estimates of headcount (with the data from the IHS study 2008¹⁵) are already outdated, but still give an overview of the (then) staffing situation: According to the IHS study, all available information on staff numbers is incomplete, so that only an approximate picture can be compiled. "Research at universities and colleges of education, supplemented by the members of the Austrian Society for Research and Development in Education (OEFEB) and the Educational Research Documentation 2006 (BIFODOC 06) show a total of over 800 people active in educational research at that time."¹⁶ In the field of vocational and adult education research non-university institutions make up a larger part. "The ratio between researchers in universities and PHs was about 2:1, about half of them were academic staff, about 10% were ordinary university professors and a further 15% were professors, about 20% were mainly in teaching or in management positions."¹⁷ Overall, the proportion of women in total staff was 50%, in colleges of teacher education a bit higher, and significantly lower in non-university institutions (data here however is very incomplete). "There was a similar pattern in individual institutions, in the universities of Salzburg and Linz the proportion of women is lower, in the PHs Vienna and Styria significantly higher. The characteristic differences are visible by function: among scientific staff, the majority are women (62%), the higher the position in the hierarchy, the more dominated by men, with 72% amongst professors."¹⁸

¹⁵ Lassnig, L. (2008): Bildungsforschung in Österreich als Ressource wissenschaftlicher Bildungspolitik und Schulentwicklung: Ist-Stand und Perspektiven für eine verbesserte Nutzung. IHS Input-Papier für NBB-2009-AutorInnengruppe, June 2008, pp. 20-21.

¹⁶ Ibid. p. 20.

¹⁷ Ibid. p. 21.

¹⁸ Ibid. p. 21.

5.2 Regular University Studies in Educational Science and Teacher Education (Pedagogy)

Fig. 1: Regular university studies according to international groups of studies in education and teacher training. Source: Unidata, Table 3.3, Full University Studies by International Groups of Studies (IS-CED). (Without extension studies, only first-grade subject in compulsory studies until 2015/16)

5.3 Completion of Studies

More recent statements can be made on completed university degrees according to international groups of studies (ISCED) in the field of "Education and Teacher Education": in 2015/16, the total number of degrees issued was 3942 (including 3053 from women and 889 from men).

Fig. 2: Degrees at universities in the field of educational science and teacher training in Austria 2015/16. Source: Statistisches Taschenbuch, Table 4.5. Studienabschlüsse an Universitäten nach internationalen Gruppen von Studien (ISCED), p. 66.

Broken down into subject areas this means:

Fig. 3: Degrees broken down into subject categories, Study year 2015/16. Source: uni:data, Tabelle 4.5 Studienabschlüsse an Universitäten nach internationalen Gruppen von Studien (ISCED).

5.4 Numbers and Data about Colleges of Teacher Education

Number of students and degrees at teacher training colleges

	Students			(from that) Beginners		
	all	female	in %	all	female	in %
Public Colleges of Teacher Education	9505	6964	73,3	2546	1827	71,8
Colleges of Teacher Education Carinthia	545	422	77,4	140	104	74,3
Colleges of Teacher Education Lower Austria	763	641	84	216	179	82,9
Colleges of Teacher Education Upper Austria	1601	1166	72,8	393	278	70,7
Colleges of Teacher Education Salzburg	882	710	80,5	271	213	78,6
Colleges of Teacher Education Styria	1345	918	67,8	381	272	71,4
Colleges of Teacher Education Tyrol	859	616	71,7	270	196	72,6
Colleges of Teacher Education Vorarlberg	462	370	80,1	139	105	75,5
Colleges of Teacher Education Vienna	2571	1834	71,3	590	401	68
University College for Agrarian and Environmental Pedagogy Vienna	468	287	61,3	146	79	54,1
Private Colleges of Teacher Education and Study Programs	5045	4161	82,5	1302	1077	82,7
Private Colleges of Teacher Education	4657	3912	84	1219	1020	83,7
Private College of Teacher Education Stiftung Burgenland	303	241	79,5	84	73	86,9
Private University of Education, Diocese of Linz	1207	1037	85,9	389	328	84,3
Private College of Teacher Education, Diocese Graz-Seckau	416	358	86,1	101	87	86,1
Private College of Teacher Education – Hochschulstiftung of the Diocese Innsbruck	394	309	78,4	11	84	75,7
Private College of Teacher Education – Hochschulstiftung Diocese Vienna	2337	1967	84,2	534	448	83,9

Source: Zahlenspiegel - Statistiken im Bereich Schule und Erwachsenenbildung Österreich, Bundesministerium für Bildung, p. 49.

Graduates of Colleges of Teacher Education in the academic year 2014/15

	all	female	in %
Public Colleges of Teacher Education	3336	2554	76,6
Colleges of Teacher Education Carinthia	223	176	78,9
Colleges of Teacher Education Lower Austria	385	332	86,2
Colleges of Teacher Education Upper Austria	603	459	76,1
Colleges of Teacher Education Salzburg	257	215	83,7
Colleges of Teacher Education Styria	467	327	70
Colleges of Teacher Education Tyrol	340	244	71,8
Colleges of Teacher Education Vorarlberg	156	138	88,5
Colleges of Teacher Education Vienna	760	569	74,9
University College for Agrarian and Environmental Pedagogy Vienna	145	94	64,8
Private Colleges of Teacher Education and Study Programs	1313	1131	86,1
Private Colleges of Teacher Education	1286	1109	86,2
Private College of Teacher Education Stiftung Burgenland	97	88	90,7
Private University of Education, Diocese of Linz	335	299	89,3
Private College of Teacher Education, Diocese Graz-Seckau	129	116	89,9
Private College of Teacher Education – Hochschulstiftung of the Diocese Innsbruck	116	92	79,3

Source: Zahlenspiegel – Statistiken im Bereich Schule und Erwachsenenbildung Österreich, Bundesministerium für Bildung, p. 50.

6. New Teacher Training Education and the establishment of Development Networks ("Entwicklungsverbünde")

The reorganization of the training of educators represents a core educational project of recent years. The new education of teachers includes the education and training of all persons who want to take up a pedagogical profession and was regulated by law in 2013. The Federal Framework Law for the introduction of a new training for teachers, BGBl. I Nr. 124/2013, the Higher Education Act 2005, the University Act 2002 and the Higher Education Quality Assurance Act and the employment law provisions for contract staff in the educational services by the "Service law amendment 2013 - Pedagogical service adapted to the introduction of a new teacher training. The new training is aimed at upgrading the course contents and further academizing of the teaching profession, the creation of competence-based training as well as the academic and career-related qualification of graduates.¹⁹ This was followed by a conversion of all study programs to Bachelor's and Master's degrees.²⁰ The newly established studies are oriented towards age ranges; the education is thus differentiated for the primary and the secondary level (and further in general education or vocational training at the secondary level). In addition, lateral entrants should be given the opportunity to take additional studies. Graduates of a teacher training course of one level (primary or secondary) can acquire the master degree for the other level through further study programs.²¹ In addition, an induction phase was introduced as part of the new training of Austrian teachers. During this time, junior teachers are supervised by experienced educators (as mentors). The aim is to allow for an easier career entry. The prerequisite for admission to a college of teacher education or a university is the completion of a multi-level admission procedure and the verification of suitability.²² This procedure corresponds to the already established procedure for teacher training colleges, compulsory admission tests at universities were introduced in the academic year 2016/17.

In order to ensure a high quality implementation of the new teacher education, mergers of universities and teacher training colleges took the form of four regional development networks. Within the networks, a standardization of curricula will be carried out and co-ed teacher studies will be offered for the secondary level.

In addition to the development of four development networks, new faculties were established at universities. This resulted in the foundation of Schools of Education at the University of Salzburg, Innsbruck and Klagenfurt as well as the establishment of centers for teacher education at the University of Vienna and the University of Graz.

6.1 Development Networks

¹⁹ See Universitätsbericht 2017 des Bundesministers für Bildung, Wissenschaft und Forschung. Online unter: https://www.parlament.gv.at/PAKT/VHG/XXVI/III/III_00091/imfname_679017.pdf, p. 157.

²⁰ All teacher training courses consist of a four-year Bachelor's degree program, a mandatory Master's program of 60 to 120 ECTS and a one to two-year induction phase.

²¹ See Universitätsbericht 2017 des Bundesministers für Bildung, Wissenschaft und Forschung. p. 157.

²² See Universitätsbericht 2017 des Bundesministers für Bildung, Wissenschaft und Forschung. p. 158.

The newly established teacher training studies were offered in all four regions from the academic year 2016/17 on:²³

Network South-East („Entwicklungsverbund Süd-Ost“)

In the fall of 2012, the University of Graz, the KPH Graz, the PH Burgenland and the PH Styria joined together to form the "Development Network Styria-Burgenland". On September 13, 2013, this development network was expanded with the PH Carinthia to become the South-East Development Network. The admission of the Alpen-Adria-University of Klagenfurt on 15 October 2013 completed the development network South-East. In addition, the Graz University of Art, the Graz University of Technology and the Catholic Pedagogical University of Carinthia were included for the joint development of new teacher training courses for primary and secondary school teachers.²⁴

In the field of primary education, two different curricula were created - one of the educational universities of Styria, Burgenland and Carinthia and one of the religious college of teacher training of the Diocese of Graz-Seckau.²⁵

Network West („LehrerInnenbildung West“)

The Religious College of Teacher Training Edith Stein, the University "Mozarteum", the College of Teacher Education Tyrol, the College of Teacher Education Vorarlberg and the University of Innsbruck cooperate in the design of studies for the training of teachers.

Each partner institution coordinates the development of the curriculum in a specific area:

KPH – Edith Stein	Inclusive Pedagogy
PH Tirol	Secondary Level Vocational Training
PH Vorarlberg	Primary Level
University of Innsbruck	Secondary Level General Education
University Mozarteum / PH Tyrol	Artistic School Subjects of Secondary Level General Education

Network Center („Entwicklungsverbund Cluster Mitte“)

The Network Center consists of the following institutions: Anton Bruckner Private University (ABPU), Johannes Kepler University Linz (JKU), Catholic Private University Linz (KUL), University of

²³ See *ibid.* p.158

²⁴ <http://www.lehramt-so.at/ev-sued-ost/> (Access: 05.09.17).

²⁵ Source: Comparison of both Curricula.

Teacher Education Upper Austria (PH-OÖ), Salzburg University of Teacher Education (PH. S), Paris-Lodron-University Salzburg (PLUS), Private University of Education of the Diocese of Linz (PH-Linz), Private University of Education - University Foundation Innsbruck (KPH-Edith Stein), University of Art and Industrial Design - University of Art Linz (UFG) and the University Mozarteum Salzburg (MOZ).

Network North-East ("Entwicklungsverbund Nord-Ost)

As the last network in the new teacher training, the Network North-East has officially formed. The University of Vienna, the colleges of teacher training of Vienna and Lower Austria, the College of Teacher Training Vienna/Krems and the University College for Agrarian and Environmental Pedagogy offer a joint teacher training course for the secondary level.

After lengthy discrepancies between the universities of art (Academy of Fine Arts, University of Applied Arts) and the colleges of teacher education (PH Vienna, PH Lower Austria and PH Vienna/Krems) in the Development Network North-East, the institutions agreed on a joint training of arts and crafts teachers from the academic year 2017/18 on.

The universities have concluded individual cooperation agreements in which the organizational and study law cooperation and a joint further development of the study plans are regulated.²⁶

6.2 Quality assurance of the new pedagogical education

In July 2013, a "Quality Assurance Council for Pedagogy Education" was set up jointly by the then Federal Ministry of Science and Research (BMWF) and the then Federal Ministry for Education, Arts and Culture (BMUKK). It consists of six experts from the national and international higher education sector.

The focus of its duties is on the one hand the counseling and guidance of the development of teacher education in Austria, on the other hand the quality assurance of the new teacher training courses. Its tasks include, above all, the study-specific examination of the academic and professorial prerequisites for the provision of services by colleges of teacher education, as well as the review of the framework of the curricula assessment procedures for the curricula of the teacher training studies. The Quality Assurance Council has to publish an annual report on the current state of teacher education in Austria.²⁷

²⁶ <http://noe.orf.at/m/news/stories/2819544/> (Access: 13.02.2018)

²⁷ BMWFW (2014): Universitätsbericht 2014. https://www.bmfwf.gv.at/Presse/AktuellePresseMeldungen/Documents/Universit%C3%A4tsbericht_2014.pdf, pp.154f (Zugriff: 6.11.17).

7. BIFODOK – Documentation of Educational Research

This database contains educational research projects relating to Austria from 1999 onwards and is updated continuously. The ongoing collection and editing of data on educational research in Austria is carried out on behalf of the ministry responsible for education (currently the Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research BMBWF) by the Association of Austrian Adult Education Centers (VÖV).

Since 1976, activities in the field of educational research in Austria (school research and school development, empirical pedagogical research, teacher training, social education, vocational and adult education) have been continuously documented by the responsible ministry. Until 1999, the project data were documented exclusively in the printed edition "Bildungsforschung in Österreich" (bifodok). For the years 2000 to 2008, information on the projects from the Education Research Documentation database of the Ministry of Education can be requested electronically. Up-to-date data from projects in the field of educational research are available at www.adulteducation.at/bifodok/.

Included are projects of educational research in Austria or with Austrian participation since about the end of the 1990s up to the present. There are projects in the field of colleges of teacher training, the university institutes involved in educational research, but also from private research institutions, and can be used to get an overview of activities in the field of educational research.²⁸

²⁸ <http://www.adulteducation.at/de/bifodok/> (Access: 07.11.17).

CWTS BIBLIOMETRIC REPORT

Meaningful metrics

Research performance and benchmark analysis of Educational Sciences in Austria

30th July 2018

Universiteit
Leiden

Research performance and benchmark analysis of Educational Sciences in Austria

For: Austrian Science Board (ASB)

Nikolaus Possanner

Head of Office

Tel. +43/1/319 49 99-20

E-mail nikolaus.possanner@wissenschaftsrat.ac.at

From: CWTS B.V.

Project Team

Mark Neijssel

Alfredo Yegros

Carole de Bordes

CWTS B.V.

P.O. Box 905

2300 AX Leiden, The Netherlands

Tel. +31 71 527 3909

Fax +31 71 527 3911

E-mail info@cwts.leidenuniv.nl

Table of contents

1. Introduction	5
1.1. Objective of the study	5
1.2. Method of analysis	5
1.3. Structure of report.....	6
2. Data and Methods	7
2.2. Database Structure	7
2.3. Data acquisition.....	7
2.4. Bibliometric Indicators	8
2.4.1. Publication output indicator	8
2.4.2. Citation impact indicators.....	8
2.4.3. Counting Method	9
2.5. Term map.....	10
3. Overall results	12
3.2. Publication output and internal coverage analysis	12
3.3. Impact analysis for Austria and its benchmarks	14
3.4. Trend analysis of the output and impact of Austria and its benchmarks....	16
3.4.1. Trend analysis of the output (P) per country	17
3.4.2. Citation impact indicators	19
3.5. Identification of key players	20
4. Topic orientation analysis by science mapping.....	23
4.1. Term-map of the field of Educational Sciences for all benchmark countries	23
4.2. Term-maps of the field of Educational Sciences per country.....	24
4. Conclusions and discussions	31
Bibliography	34
Annex A: CWTS Publication-Based Classification.....	35

date
CWTS B.V.
Centre for Science and
Technology Studies,
Leiden University

Annex B: Background information	36
Bibliometric indicators of scientific impact	36
Responsible use of bibliometrics	43
Annex C: The impact of language.....	46

1. Introduction

1.1. Objective of the study

This report has been commissioned by the Austrian Science Board (ASB) who is the main advisory body to the Federal Minister of sciences and higher education, parliament and the universities, in all university-related matters in Austria.

This research is part of a project led by the Austrian Science Fund (FWF). The FWF is the most important Austrian funding organization for basic research. The self-governed organization is based in Vienna and financed by the Austrian federal government.

In this context, the purpose of the report is to evaluate the field of Educational Sciences in Austria between 2000 and 2016. By means of a comprehensive benchmark analysis, this study aims to reveal how Austria performs in the field of Educational Sciences and how Austria is positioned, from a bibliometric perspective, compared to other European countries.

This report provides findings related to the internal coverage, publication output and citation impact in the field 'Educational Sciences', for Austria and its benchmark countries.

Furthermore, this report also presents by means of a term-map the research topics covered in the field of Educational Sciences by showing the important terms extracted from the titles and abstracts of the publications comprising this field.

1.2. Method of analysis

The bibliometric impact indicators we employ in this report can be summarized by the following parameters. These parameters are described in more details in the data and methods, section 2.3 of the report and in Annex B.

<i>Database:</i>	All publications in Web of Science core collection (WoS)
<i>Classification system:</i>	Publication-level classification system (about 4000 fields)
<i>Publication window:</i>	2000-2016
<i>Output analysis:</i>	Articles and Reviews; full counting
<i>Self-citations:</i>	Excluded
<i>Main indicators:</i>	P, MNCS, PP(top 10 %) and MNJS
<i>Normalization:</i>	Fractional counting at the level of country
<i>Trend analysis:</i>	P, MNCS, PP(top 10%) and MNJS

1.3. Structure of report

This report is divided into four sections. The first section gives an overview of the empirical setting and methodology. The second section presents the results divided in four parts. Firstly, part 3.1. provides an analysis of the overall publication output and the internal coverage for the aggregated field of Educational Sciences for Austria and its benchmarks. Then, in part 3.2. the main indicators for all units of analysis are calculated and presented. Next, part 3.3. displays a trend analysis of the output and impact of Austria and its benchmarks and finally, part 3.4. identifies the top 5 key players in Austria within the field of Educational Sciences. The third section shows a term-map of the field Educational Sciences for all benchmark countries using the VOSviewer visualizations. In the final section of the report, conclusions are drawn.

2. Data and Methods

In this chapter, we present and discuss the methods underlying the bibliometric analysis presented in this report.

2.2. Database Structure

At CWTS, we calculate our indicators based on our CWTS Citation Index system (CWTS CI-system). This is our in-house enhanced version of the Web of Science core collection (WoS) database of Clarivate Analytics. WoS is a bibliographic database that covers the publications of about 12,000 journals in the sciences, the social sciences, and the arts and humanities. Each journal in WoS is assigned to one or more scientific field(s), i.e. journal subject categories. These journal subject categories construct a classification system of science. Our database also supports a hierarchically organized field classification system on top of the WoS journal subject categories (see Annex A).

We note that our CWTS CI-system includes a number of improvements over the original WoS database. The main improvements concern the systematic verification of publication-based addresses which results in a more accurate match of organization names (e.g. unification of university names). Another enhancement concerns the improved matching of cited references to targeted articles. Additionally, the CI-system implements a publication-based classification system of science as opposed to the journal based classification system. This system clusters publications into research fields and sub-fields based on citation relations (Waltman & van Eck, 2012). One important advantage of this classification system is that it allows for a classification of science that is more detailed and better matches the current structure of scientific research. This not only reduces classification bias, but also, it is essential for calculating field-normalized indicators (Ruiz-Castillo & Waltman, 2014).

2.3. Data acquisition

Publication data of the units of analysis and bibliometric data were collected to form the dataset. To conduct the benchmark analysis, these data have been collected for Austria and for nine additional countries:

- 1) Austria (AT)
- 2) Switzerland (CH)
- 3) United Kingdom (UK)

- 4) Germany (DE)
- 5) The Netherlands (NL)
- 6) Belgium (BE)
- 7) Denmark (DK)
- 8) Sweden (SE)
- 9) Finland (FI)
- 10) Norway (NO)

The field 'Educational Sciences' has been delineated according to the WoS journal subject categories. Accordingly, the field 'Educational Sciences' results from the aggregation of these four WoS journal subject categories:

- EDUCATION & EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH
- EDUCATION, SCIENTIFIC DISCIPLINES
- EDUCATION, SPECIAL
- PSYCHOLOGY, EDUCATIONAL

2.4. Bibliometric Indicators

Two key aspects of research performance are considered in our benchmark analysis: publication output and citation impact.

2.4.1. Publication output indicator

Publication output (P) is about the number of publications and the scientific/scholarly fields to which these publications belong. It is calculated by counting the number of publications covered by CI-system in the period 2000-2016.

2.4.2. Citation impact indicators

Citation impact focuses on the number of times the publications have been cited. Citation impact does not necessarily reflect the scientific quality of the work, but it can be regarded as a proxy for the scientific impact of this work.

In this part of the analysis, only publications of the WoS document types 'article' and 'review' are taken into account. Hence, book reviews, editorials, letters to the editor, and all the other remaining document types are not included in the analysis.

Since our analysis is based on WoS data, only citations from WoS indexed publications are counted. We do not count author self-citations. A citation is considered an author self-citation if the citing and the cited publication have at least one author name in

common. For each publication, all citations received until the end of 2017 are taken into account. This means that older publications have had more time to receive citations and may therefore be expected to have higher citation counts than more recent publications. Please note carefully that the sophisticated normalized citation impact indicators used by CWTS correct for this, i.e. normalization for publication age.

For the sake of this research, given the important differences in terms of the volume of publication output between the different benchmark countries, size-independent indicators (MNCS, MNJS and PP(top 10%)) are more interesting to compare the performance of the various countries. The indicators on the average citation impact calculated in this project are:

- **Mean Normalized Citation Score (MNCS):** an average normalized citation score above (below) one indicates that on average publications are cited more (or less) frequently than the average publication in the same field and published the same year.
- **Mean Normalized Journal Score (MNJS):** Average normalized citation score of the journals in which a unit of analysis has published. The MNJS indicator is closely related to the MNCS indicator. The only difference is that instead of the actual number of citations of a publication, the MNJS used the number of citations of all the publications published in a particular journal. The interpretation of the MNJS indicator is analogous to the interpretation of the MNCS indicator.
- **Percentage top 10% publications (PP(top 10%)):** if the percentage top 10% publications is above (below) 10%, this indicates an above (or below) average number of publications that belong to the top 10% in the same field and published the same year.

2.4.3. Counting Method

In computing impact indicators, we can use the full counting method and/or the fractional counting method. The full counting method consists of fully allocating the credits of a publication to the involved research units, regardless of the number of units involved. This is different from the fractional counting method, where depending on the number of units in the study, only a fraction of the publication is assigned to the unit being evaluated. Hence, impact indicators calculated using full counting tends to have higher value scores than impact indicators calculated using fractional counting.

The main advantage of full counting over fractional counting is that, full counting is usually perceived as more intuitive and easier to interpret. There is, however, some risk that full counting gives results in which certain scientific/scholarly fields are favored over others. Furthermore, full counting does not reflect the actual contribution of a research unit to a set of publications. To correct for these biases, a fractional counting approach is suitable. Altogether, the fractional counting method leads to a more accurate field normalization of impact indicators than the full counting method and thus allows for an unbiased comparison between countries or universities that are active in different fields.

In this study, we used the fractional counting method for normalized impact indicators (e.g. MNCS, MNJS, and Top indicators), but we used the full counting approach for direct counts of the total publication output (P).

All the indicators of citation impact have been calculated applying fractional counting at the level of country. This means that each country listed in the address list of a publication has equal weight, for instance in a joint publication between Austria and the Netherlands, for these two countries a weight of $1/2 = 0.5$ is assigned. In the case of an affiliation between two different universities from Austria and one university from the Netherlands, the fractional counting is applied in the same way: each country listed in the address list of a publication has equal weight; meaning that each country receives a weight of $1/2 = 0.5$.

2.5. Term map

We also delivered two term maps which have been created by using VOSviewer software (Waltman & van Eck, 2010, www.vosviewer.com). This software is useful to interactively visualize research areas where Austria and its benchmark countries are active. The term maps were delivered for all countries as well as for Austria only.

We selected all the publications in the field Educational Sciences for Austria and all benchmark countries published between 2000 to 2016, and conducted an analysis of the relevant/most prominent terms used in the abstracts and titles.

The next step was the construction of the so-called term maps. A term map is a two-dimensional visualization in which the terms are located in such a way that the distance between any two terms reflects the relatedness of the terms as accurately as possible. In general, the larger the number of co-occurrences of two terms, the smaller the distance between them. In this way, a term map provides a visual overview of important topics discussed in the literature and how these topics relate to each other.

The larger the number of articles and reviews in which a term occurs (in the title or abstract), the more prominently the term is displayed in a term map. Frequently occurring terms are for instance presented using a larger font size (Flis & van Eck, 2017).

3. Overall results

3.2. Publication output and internal coverage analysis

This part of the report is devoted to the analysis of the overall publication output and the internal coverage of the 'Educational Sciences' field, for Austria and the benchmark countries.

We calculated the internal coverage indicator for each of the countries in the project, based on our in-house version of the WoS database. Based on the aggregated dataset, we computed the internal coverage indicator. The value of this indicator equals to the percentage of cited references by a unit of analysis that points to publications covered by the WoS.

This indicator is used to estimate the volume of research outputs produced by the units of analysis that would be covered by the WoS. A high internal coverage indicates that scientific publications in the WoS are representative of the research conducted by the unit. A low internal coverage indicates that most likely the unit is producing to a relatively large extent research outputs that are not covered by the WoS and therefore the insights gained through a bibliometric analysis would be of a somewhat more limited value.

The results presented in table 1 reflect the publication output and the internal coverage for Austria and the benchmark countries in the field of Educational Sciences.

The output indicator (P) shows that a total of 522 WoS publications (articles and reviews) have been produced by Austria. As seen in Table 1, the highest publication output is reached by the United Kingdom (P = 21650).

Table 1. Publication output, the percentage of publications in Educational Sciences within the total scientific output (%) and the internal coverage for the field Educational Sciences per country (2000 - 2016) (full counting)

Country	P	%	Internal Coverage
Austria	522	0,28%	46%
Belgium	2043	0,74%	52%
Denmark	778	0,38%	40%
Finland	1891	1,12%	44%
Germany	6557	0,45%	43%
Netherlands	5912	1,19%	55%
Norway	1622	1,08%	41%
Sweden	2423	0,71%	40%
Switzerland	1210	0,34%	44%
United Kingdom	21650	1,39%	36%

In order to contextualize the volume of publication output in each country, Figure 1 shows the relative output in the field of Educational Sciences per country within the total scientific output in that country. In Austria, the field of Educational Sciences represents 0.28% of the total publication output in the period 2000-2016. Compared to other countries considered in this study, this is the lowest percentage, much lower for instance than the case of the Netherlands (1.19%) or the United Kingdom (1.39%).

Figure 1. Publication output and percentage within the total scientific output per country (%) for the field Educational Sciences (2000 – 2016) (full counting)

Furthermore, the Table 1 shows that the internal coverage of Austrian publications is about 46%. This means that 46% of the references in this set of publications are also covered by the WoS.

Regarding the other units of analysis, internal coverage values are very similar to that of Austria, ranging between 36% (United Kingdom) and 52% (Belgium).

The value of the internal coverage indicator for the various countries is not very high but also not very low. Therefore, it can be considered that the internal coverage is sufficiently good to perform this bibliometric analysis and it can provide important insights on the research performance in the field of Educational Sciences as well as it brings the opportunity of comparing the performance of the various countries. However, bearing in mind the internal coverage, it is also important to consider that some important research developments in this scientific domain are probably not fully captured by our study.

3.3. Impact analysis for Austria and its benchmarks

Table 2 shows the main bibliometric indicators in the field of Educational Sciences for the different countries. Given the important differences in terms of the volume of publication output in these countries, size-independent indicators (MNCS, MNJS and

PP(top 10%)) are more interesting to compare the performance of the various countries. According to the MNCS, Austria (MNCS = 0.90) is performing slightly below the world average (1.00). The highest score within this group of countries is the Netherlands with a score of 26% above world average.

Austria achieved almost the same value in the Mean Normalized Journal Score (MNJS) (0.86) compared to its MNCS, outperformed by all countries except Germany (0.81) and Switzerland (0.85).

Among all Austrian publications, 9% are among the top 10% most cited publications worldwide, very similar as Germany (8%) and Switzerland (8%).

Table 2. Bibliometric indicators for the field Educational Sciences per country (2000 - 2016)

<i>Unit</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>MNCS</i>	<i>MNJS</i>	<i>PP (top 10%)</i>
<i>Austria</i>	522	0,9	0,86	9%
<i>Belgium</i>	2043	1,1	1,06	11%
<i>Denmark</i>	778	0,9	0,93	7%
<i>Finland</i>	1891	0,97	0,97	9%
<i>Germany</i>	6557	0,84	0,81	8%
<i>Netherlands</i>	5912	1,26	1,19	14%
<i>Norway</i>	1622	1	0,97	9%
<i>Sweden</i>	2423	0,96	0,96	7%
<i>Switzerland</i>	1210	0,87	0,85	8%
<i>United Kingdom</i>	21650	1,05	1,02	10%

Figure 2 illustrates the relationship between the total amount of publications and MNCS for Austria and the benchmark countries. From this figure, we can see that Austria has a rather low publication output but a MNCS similar to countries like Denmark, Switzerland or Finland. Actually, Austria has, as most of the benchmark countries, a MNCS close to 1 (i.e. world average) and a publication output ranging between 1000 and 2000.

The country with the highest MNCS is the Netherlands (1,26) and a relatively high output (5912) in comparison with other countries. Other relevant countries that stand out from this graph are Germany and UK. In the case of Germany, the number of

publication output is very similar to the Netherlands, however, the MNCS is the lowest of all countries. Comparable situation is noticeable for UK which ranks first in terms of publication output with 21650 papers published but its MNCS is relatively average with only 1,05.

Figure 2. Output (P) and impact (MNCS) for all benchmark countries, 2000-2016

In addition to the analysis of the main bibliometric indicators, we have been doing some extra analysis to find out the reasons to possibly explain the rather weak performance of AUT, CH and GER (See Annex C).

3.4. Trend analysis of the output and impact of Austria and its benchmarks

In the previous chapter, CWTS presented the analysis of the impact for the entire period (2000-2016). In this section, we look into the development over time of the output and the impact dimensions based on the same indicators presented in Table 2. We use a five-year moving average to prevent having too few publications for reliable

statistics and also to dampen possible volatile fluctuations that might occur when using a single year timeframe. There are then in total thirteen time-blocks.

3.4.1. Trend analysis of the output (P) per country

We calculated here the publication output over time for Austria and its benchmarks. The trend analysis for the output (P) per country (see Table 3 and Figure 3) shows some relevant patterns.

In the table 3, we can see that the production of publications (P) in all countries have shown a steady increase of annual production during the whole period.

In the case of Austria, there was also a substantial increase in research output over time, from 66 publications in 2000-2004 to 288 publications in the 2012-2016 period. This increase in output may reflect, for example, an increase in the number of research staff and/or an increasing productivity.

Table 3. Trend analysis of the publication output in the field of Educational Sciences per country, 2000-2016

	2000 - 2004	2001 - 2005	2002 - 2006	2003 - 2007	2004 - 2008	2005 - 2009	2006 - 2010	2007 - 2011	2008 - 2012	2009 - 2013	2010 - 2014	2011 - 2015	2012 - 2016
Austria	66	67	75	68	76	85	113	141	173	211	241	258	288
Belgium	162	188	216	256	320	411	517	628	783	923	1007	1088	1139
Denmark	54	59	66	81	105	153	191	233	279	334	344	389	463
Finland	220	228	235	273	318	384	477	563	634	747	832	906	1012
Germany	832	884	1013	1162	1378	1568	1836	2074	2254	2501	2784	2986	3184
Norway	146	157	182	225	286	367	470	565	617	685	742	759	831
Netherlands	741	832	916	998	1168	1362	1581	1860	2117	2429	2613	2774	2875
Sweden	192	227	272	307	415	544	693	816	926	1020	1113	1169	1275
Switzerland	137	150	176	205	242	281	330	365	417	462	524	553	608
UK	4078	4069	4202	4537	5054	5702	6392	7136	7737	8289	8520	8620	8662

In Figure 3, below, we show the trend of the growth in the publication output over the thirteen time-blocks. It can be observed that Austrian publication output has grown steadily until 2006, and after that year the publication output has experienced a more

pronounced growth. Most of the benchmark countries show similar patterns, but with different intensity of growth. UK has been the exception, experiencing the lowest growth in the period of analysis.

Additionally, the analysis shows that the kick-off period in growth for all countries occurred in the block period 2004 - 2008.

Figure 3. Growth of the publication output between 2000 and 2016 per country.

Overall, the development of Austrian output is considered as high since they increased their production output by about 4 times between the first block period and the last block period. Compared to other countries, the growth of Austrian publications is very similar to that of Finland, Switzerland, the Netherlands and Germany. Only Norway, Sweden, Belgium and Denmark experienced a higher growth in the publication output. In the context of this study, the steeper curve of Denmark, Belgium, Sweden and Norway can hardly be explained since we lack background information on the resources assigned to research per country.

3.4.2. Citation impact indicators

In this part of the report we focus specifically on the results of the citation scores of Austria according to various indicators, over the thirteen time-blocks analyzed.

In Table 4 and Figure 4, we summarize the results of the MNCS, MNJS and PP(Top 10%) indicators. MNCS, MNJS and PP(top 10%) present similar trends. Altogether, Austria's MNCS has remained relatively low for the whole period, with values ranging between 0.65 and 1.15, while the MNJS values ranged between 0.74 and 0.93. This means that Austria's performance in terms of MNCS is close to the worldwide average (1.00) and are published in journals in which publications performed slightly below worldwide average.

Specifically, Austria reaped the highest research impact for publications in the periods of 2005-2009, 2006-2010, 2007-2011 and 2008-2012, with respectively a MNCS of 1.03, 1.15, 1.13, and 1.10. Furthermore, the proportion of Austrian's publications in the top 10% follows the same trend as the MNCS, showing a relatively low score in the first four block periods with about 6% to 9% of their publications. The PP(top 10%) indicator shows that Austria has reached its highest score in the block period 2007-2011(14% of publication in the top 10% most cited worldwide).

Additionally, it is worth to mention the slight decrease in citation impact in the last four blocks. Therefore, the values of MNCS, MNJS and PP(top 10%) declined and became more or less the same as the ones in the first block period.

Table 4. The overall performance of Austria over time (2000-2016)

Year	P	MNCS	MNJS	PP(top 10%)
2000 - 2004	66	0,82	0,89	9%
2001 - 2005	67	0,65	0,79	7%
2002 - 2006	75	0,65	0,81	7%
2003 - 2007	68	0,67	0,76	6%
2004 - 2008	76	0,90	0,74	8%
2005 - 2009	85	1,03	0,80	11%
2006 - 2010	113	1,15	0,88	13%
2007 - 2011	141	1,13	0,90	14%
2008 - 2012	173	1,10	0,93	13%
2009 - 2013	211	0,98	0,92	11%

2010 - 2014	241	0,89	0,89	9%
2011 - 2015	258	0,81	0,84	7%
2012 - 2016	288	0,85	0,84	7%

Figure 4. The development of the Field Normalized Impact Indicators (MNCS, MNJS, and PP (top 10%)) over time (2000-2016) for Austria.

3.5. Identification of key players

In this section, we have identified the top 5 key players (i.e. universities) in Austria within the field of Educational Sciences based on the amount of scientific publications:

- University of Vienna
- University of Graz
- University of Salzburg
- Johannes Kepler University of Linz
- University of Innsbruck

We provide then an analysis of the main indicators as shown in figure 6 and table 6. The results reveal which organizations produced a higher number of publications in the field of Educational Sciences in Austria and, among them, which ones reached the highest citation impact.

In Table 5, we see that the number of publications produced by these 5 key players ranges between 30 and 150. The University of Vienna is the organization that produced the highest number of publications (P = 144) while the University of Innsbruck is placed at the fifth position (P = 31).

In terms of the amount of publications among the top 10% most cited publications worldwide, the University of Salzburg reached the highest score (22%). It is worth to mention that all the others are slightly below 10% of publications among the top 10% most cited publications worldwide.

Table 5. Performance indicators for the Top5 universities in the field of Educational Sciences

Key Players	P	MNCS	MNJS	PP(top 10%)
University of Vienna	144	0,69	0,80	7%
University of Graz	68	1,09	0,90	9%
University of Salzburg	49	1,56	1,11	22%
Johannes Kepler University of Linz	40	0,74	0,76	6%
University of Innsbruck	31	0,53	0,71	6%

In terms of MNCS, the figure 5 shows that only the University of Salzburg (MNCS = 1.56) and the University of Graz (MNCS = 1.09) are performing above world average.

Figure 5. Output (P) and impact (MNCS) for the Top5 key players (2000-2016) in the field of Educational Sciences

4. Topic orientation analysis by science mapping

Science maps have been created using VOSviewer. VOSviewer software and two ready-to-use files (i.e. 'map.txt' and 'network.txt') can be found in attached files. They contain the necessary data to create the same term maps shown in this report.

We constructed 10 term maps for the period 2000-2016. To get a general impression of the subdivision of the field of Educational Sciences into topics, and how these topics relate to each other, we constructed an overall term map based on all articles in our data set (as described in section 4.1). To identify the specific topical focus of each country in the field, we also constructed term maps based on the articles published by each of the nine benchmark countries considered in our study (i.e. section 4.2).

The threshold for the minimum number of occurrences of a term to be included in the map has been set to 50, so that the maps are easy to read. Additionally, we have removed the term 'article' - which is in general the most occurring term in publications - to prevent biases in the analysis of the term map and thus to concentrate more on the terms that are relevant for the field under study.

4.1. Term-map of the field of Educational Sciences for all benchmark countries

With the VOSviewer software we constructed a network visualization term map in which the distance between any pair of terms provides an approximate indication of the relatedness of the terms as measured by co-occurrences. Each term in a term map also has a color. Colors are used to indicate the clustering of terms into topics. Terms that have the same color belong to the same cluster and tend to be more closely related than terms having different colors. In other words, terms that have the same color tend to co-occur with each other more frequently than terms having different colors.

In this network visualization (Figure 7), the various clusters reveal different sub-areas within the field Educational Sciences. We have identified 4 main clusters. The Red cluster represents terms about educational policy, such as "reform", "policy", "concept" or "community"; the Green cluster deals with general research on educational sciences patterns, such as "performance", "age", "effect" and "child"; the Yellow cluster presents

Finland

Figure 11. Term map of the field of Educational Sciences (2000-2016) for Finland

Germany

Figure 12. Term map of the field of Educational Sciences (2000-2016) for Germany

4. Conclusions and discussions

In this report, we have analyzed the performance of Austria's research activity and its benchmarks in the aggregated field of Educational Sciences. Specifically, we examined Austria's performance according to various bibliometric indicators including trend analyses. We also identified the top 5 key players in Austria in terms of the amount of publication output. The analysis of specific areas of research within the field of Educational Sciences has been done on the basis of term maps extracted from publications in the period 2000-2016. Austria's outputs have been compared with the scientific publications produced by Switzerland, UK, Germany, The Netherlands, Belgium, Denmark, Sweden, Finland and Norway in the field of Educational Sciences. Austria has produced a total of 522 publications covered by the WoS between the years 2000 and 2016.

The internal coverage (46%) can be regarded as reasonable, indicating that these bibliometric indicators can be considered reliable and informative of the Austrian publication output in Educational Sciences. Indeed, regarding the other units of analysis, internal coverage values are very similar to that of Austria, ranging between 36% (United Kingdom) and 52% (Belgium). However, this rather low number also means that the bibliometric indicators must be interpreted with caution.

The set of Austrian scientific publications in Educational Sciences achieved an average score (i.e. just below or about world average) in the indicators of citation impact, compared to the other nine countries included in the study. For instance, their MNCS (0.90) or their percentage of publications among the top 10% most cited publications (9%), both score comparable with the impact achieved by Finland or Norway. However, in terms of the percentage of the publication outputs in Educational Sciences relative to the total scientific publications produced in Austria in the period 2000-2016, Austria (0.28%) show a lower value compared to most of benchmark countries.

Furthermore, the trend analyses have shown that there is a steady increase in publication pattern for Austria and all benchmark countries. While Denmark accounts for the highest growth in terms of publication output, Austria is rather average with a moderate and constant increase from 2006 onwards. In terms of the field normalized citation impact indicators, MNCS and MNJS, the scores of Austria over time remained

around world average. Austria reaped the highest research impact in the periods of 2006-2010, 2007-2011, and 2008-2012, with respectively a MNCS of 1.15, 1.13, and 1.10.

With regards to the top 5 key players in Austria (i.e. University of Vienna, University of Graz, University of Salzburg, Johannes Kepler University of Linz and University of Innsbruck), the University of Vienna accounts for the highest publication output with $P = 144$. However, in terms of MNCS, the findings show that only the University of Salzburg and the University of Graz are performing above world average.

Additionally, it was found in the results section that all the top 5 players are universities. Thus, it seems that an important part of the research in the field of Educational Sciences in Austria is carried out by universities.

Finally, the term map visualization allowed to examine the specific topics and areas of research within the field of Education Sciences, based on the co-occurrence of terms extracted from the set of abstracts and titles of published literature in the field of Educational Sciences for all benchmark countries (2000-2016). In the overall term map, 4 main clusters were identified: (1) the Red cluster about educational policy, (2) the Green cluster about general research on educational sciences patterns, (3) the Yellow cluster about specific educational needs and (4) the Blue cluster about clinical measurements and methods used. Additionally, nine overlay term maps were created to display the intensity of activities in the field of Educational Sciences for Austria and each benchmark country.

All combined, these maps might help understand in which research areas Austria and its benchmark countries are active. Specifically, we can see from the map that Austria seems to have a more intense activity in the research areas displayed by the terms 'effect', 'age', 'child', 'accuracy' while, for example, UK scores a higher intensity of activity in the research areas concerned with 'community', 'agenda', 'service', 'politic' and 'policy'.

In sum, we may conclude that a combination of bibliometric term mapping and performance analysis provides a good basis for the ASB to discuss and think of effective policy to increase the impact of Austria in the field of Educational Sciences. Furthermore, the ASB can identify gaps, subfields in Educational Sciences where Austria currently shows limited activity. Being aware of such roles in these processes will help the ASB to compare the position of Austria among other countries and

contribute effectively to new developments in the field of Educational Sciences at the national level but also internationally.

However, once again, bearing in mind the rather low internal coverage, it is important to consider that some important research developments in this scientific domain are probably not fully captured by our study.

As a final remark, it is critical to realize that citation impact and scientific quality are different concepts, and citation impact indicators do not always reflect scientific quality. To properly interpret bibliometric indicators, background knowledge is needed on their foundations and limitations, on the research units that are being evaluated as well as on the subfields in which the research units are active. Therefore, we suggest the use of the results presented in this report in combination with experts and peers with sufficient knowledge on the Educational Sciences field in Austria.

Bibliography

Flis, I. & van Eck, N.J. (2017). Framing Psychology as a Discipline (1950–1999): A Large-Scale Term Co-Occurrence Analysis of Scientific Literature in Psychology.

Ruiz-Castillo, J. & Waltman, L. (2014). Field-normalized citation impact indicators using algorithmically constructed classification systems of science *Journal of Informetrics*, Volume 9, Issue 1, January 2015, 102-117.

Waltman, L., & van Eck, N.J. (2012). A new methodology for constructing a publication-level classification system of science. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 63(12), 2378-2392.

Annex A: CWTS Publication-Based Classification.

An alternative to the WoS subject categories is to define fields at the level of individual publications instead of journals. Accordingly, the CWTS publication based classification was developed algorithmically with the purpose to cluster publications into research fields based on citation relations. A publication-level classification system is not perfect, but it is more fine-grained and transparent than a journal-level classification system. In the former, each individual publication is assigned to a field based on the citation relations with cited publications, while, in the latter case, it is the journal that is assigned to a field regardless of the heterogeneity of the publications within the journal.

Our classification approach can be summarized into three steps. First, we determine the relatedness of publications. This is done based on direct citation relations between all pairs of publications. Then, as a second step, we cluster publications into research areas and organize research areas in a hierarchical structure. The third step involves labeling the previously clustered research areas. Here, the labels are obtained by extracting terms from the titles and abstracts of publications within the clusters.

The main characteristics of each cluster are as follows. Clusters of publications are created on the basis of citations from one publication to another. The clusters contain publications from multiple years. Each publication is assigned to one cluster only. A cluster is considered, and in many cases, validated as representative for disciplines, research areas, fields or sub-fields. Furthermore, our classification scheme has three hierarchically levels:

A top level of 27 clusters (areas);

A second level of 817 clusters (meso-fields);

A third level of 4,113 clusters (micro-fields).

Annex B: Background information

Bibliometric indicators of scientific impact

Scientific impact is typically analyzed by counting the number of citations received by publications. There are many different impact indicators, with the journal impact factor and the h-index being the best-known examples. Citations are given for a variety of reasons. Some citations indicate that the citing publication builds on the citing publication. These citations may be seen as an acknowledgment of the importance of the cited publication for the citing one. Negative citations are of an opposite nature. They reflect a critical perspective of the citing publication on the cited publication. However, many citations are neither positive nor negative. These citations often reflect a more superficial connection between the citing and the cited publication. They are sometimes referred to as superficial citations. Given the diversity of citations, citation counts provide only an approximate indication of scientific impact. In some cases, citation counts are also interpreted as indicators of scientific quality, but this interpretation is of an even more approximate nature.

Types of impact indicators

Impact indicators can be classified in many different ways. An essential distinction is between size-dependent and size-independent impact indicators. Size-dependent impact indicators reflect the total scientific impact of the publications of a research unit, while size-independent impact indicators reflect the average scientific impact per publication. A further distinction that can be made is between impact indicators that directly count citations and impact indicators that first identify highly cited publications and then count these publications.

Table 1 summarizes the above classification of impact indicators. The different types of impact indicators are labeled based on the names that are used at CWTS. The simplest impact indicators are based directly on counting citations. These are the size-dependent total citation score and the size-independent mean citation score. The total citation score equals the total number of citations received by the publications of a research unit, while the mean citation score equals the average number of citations received per publication. Impact indicators based on counting highly cited publications first require the choice of the threshold n that determines whether a publication is classified as highly cited or not. A publication is classified as highly cited if it has received at least n citations. The value of n for instance could be 10, 20, 50, or 100,

depending on how strict one would like to be in classifying publications as highly cited. After the threshold n has been chosen, the number and the proportion of highly cited publications of a research unit can be calculated. These indicators provide respectively a size-dependent and a size-independent perspective on the scientific impact of the publications of a research unit.

Table 1. Classification of impact indicators.

	Size-dependent	Size-independent
Citations	Total citation score TCS	Mean citation score MCS
Highly cited publications	Number of highly cited pub. $P(\geq n \text{ cit.})$	Prop. of highly cited pub. $PP(\geq n \text{ cit.})$

Compared with impact indicators based on counting citations, impact indicators based on counting highly cited publications are less sensitive to publications with a very large number of citations. Impact indicators based on counting highly cited publications are therefore more robust, which is often seen as an advantage of these indicators.

The classification of impact indicators presented in Table 1 includes some of the most commonly used indicators, but many other indicators are not included. An example is the h-index. The h-index of a research unit equals the largest number h such that the research unit has h publications that have received at least h citations each. The h-index is a size-dependent impact indicator. Like the number of highly cited publications, it is relatively insensitive to publications with a very large number of citations. The h-index is normally not used by CWTS. This is because of its inconsistency. When two research units make the same improvement in terms of publications and citations, their ranking relative to each other according to the h-index may reverse. The inconsistency of the h-index is illustrated in Box 4.

Box 4. Inconsistency of the h-index

The above figures illustrate the inconsistency of the h-index. The solid and the dashed line indicate the number of citations received by the publications of, respectively, research unit A and research unit B. Publications are presented in decreasing order of their number of citations. The left figure shows the initial situation, in which the h-index of research units A and B equals, respectively, 5 and 4. The right figure shows the situation after research units A and B have both published 2 new publications, each with 8 citations. In the new situation, the h-index of research units A and B equals, respectively, 5 and 6. Hence, compared with the initial situation, the two research units have made the same improvement in terms of publications and citations, but their ranking relative to each other according to the h-index has reversed. This is an illustration of the inconsistency of the h-index.

Normalization for scientific field and publication age

Different scientific fields have different citation practices. Because of this, there are large differences between fields in citation density, that is, in the average number of citations received per publication. For instance, the average number of citations received by publications in mathematics is about an order of magnitude smaller than the average number of citations received by publications in some fields in the life sciences. When a bibliometric analysis of scientific impact covers multiple fields, one often wants to correct for differences between fields in citation density. Performing such a correction is called field normalization. Field normalization is usually carried out by comparing the number of citations of a publication with the number of citations of other publications in the same field.

Older publications have had more time to receive citations than more recent publications, and on average older publications therefore tend to have been cited more often than more recent publications. One may want to perform a normalization that corrects for this. Such a normalization can be carried out by comparing the number of

citations of a publication with the number of citations of other publications from the same year.

Table 2 presents the normalized counterparts of the unnormalized impact indicators listed in Table 1. The indicators are again labeled based on the names that are used at CWTS. The total and the mean normalized citation score equal, respectively, the total and the average normalized number of citations of the publications of a research unit. The normalized number of citations of a publication is calculated by dividing the number of citations of the publication by the average number of citations of all publications in the same field and from the same year. In the case of impact indicators based on counting highly cited publications, a publication is classified as highly cited if it belongs to the top $x\%$ most highly cited publications of its field and its year. One often focuses on the top 10% most highly cited publications, but it is for instance also possible to consider the top 1%, top 5%, or top 50% most highly cited publications.

Table 2. Classification of normalized impact indicators.

	Size-dependent	Size-independent
Citations	Total normalized citation score TNCS	Mean normalized citation score MNCS
Highly cited publications	Number of highly cited pub. P(top $x\%$)	Prop. of highly cited pub. PP(top $x\%$)

The use of normalized impact indicators involves some choices. Normalization for scientific field requires the choice of a field classification system. In practice, the journal categories in Web of Science and Scopus are often used as a field classification system. An alternative is to define fields algorithmically at the level of individual publications instead of journals. This can for instance be done by grouping publications into fields based on citation relations. Normalization based on an algorithmically constructed publication-level classification system can be expected to yield more accurate results, while normalization based on a journal-level classification system may be more transparent and easier to understand.

CWTS works preferably field its proprietary publication-level classification system. This is particularly relevant in our work for the ASB, because earlier studies have shown that citation analysis may underestimate the impact of, for instance, clinical research as compared to basic research (Van Eck [2013] PLoS ONE, 8(4), e62395).

Another choice that needs to be made relates to the minimum age of publications that are included in the calculation of normalized impact indicators. Very recent publications usually have received no or almost no citations. Normalization for publication age does not give meaningful results for these publications. Very recent publications are therefore often excluded from the calculation of normalized impact indicators. Typically, at least publications that are less than one-year-old are excluded.

Credit allocation

In most scientific fields, a large majority of the publications are co-authored by multiple researchers and often also by multiple research institutions or even by multiple countries. This leads to the problem of credit allocation. When a publication is co-authored by multiple research units, how should the credits of the publication be allocated to the different research units?

The two most commonly used approaches for dealing with the credit allocation problem are referred to as the full and the fractional counting approach. In the full counting approach, the credits of a publication are fully allocated to each of the co-authoring research units. In the fractional counting approach, the credits of a publication are fractionally allocated to each of the co-authoring research unit. Hence, in the case of a publication co-authored by three research units, each unit receives one-third of the credits of the publication.

Table 3 shows a simple example illustrating the full and the fractional counting approach in the calculation of the total and the mean citation score of a research unit. We are interested in research unit A. This research unit has authored three publications. It is the only author of publication 1, while it has co-authored publications 2 and 3 with other research units. For each publication, Table 1 reports the number of citations received by the publication. In the full counting approach, the three publications and their citations are fully assigned to research unit A (and to the other research units B and C). This results in a total and a mean citation score of, respectively, 17 and $17 / 3 = 5.67$ for research unit A. In the fractional counting approach, publications and citations are allocated fractionally to research unit A. Consider for instance publication 2. As can be seen in Table 3, this publication is co-authored by two research units, A and B, and therefore the publication is allocated to research unit A with a weight of $1 / 2 = 0.50$. The publication has received 3 citations, which are allocated to research unit A with a weight of 0.50, yielding $0.50 \times 3 = 1.50$ citations for research unit A. By performing these calculations for all three

publications, the fractional counting approach results in a total citation score of 10.17 and a mean citation score of $10.17 / 1.83 = 5.55$.

Table 3. Example illustrating the full and the fractional counting approach.

	Co-authoring research units	No. of citations	Fractional publication allocation	Fractional citation allocation
Publication 1	A	6	1.00	6.00
Publication 2	A, B	3	0.50	1.50
Publication 3	A, B, C	8	0.33	2.67
Total		17	1.83	10.17

The choice between the full and the fractional counting approach can be made based on which approach one considers more appropriate for a particular analysis. However, when working with normalized impact indicators, the fractional counting approach has an important advantage over the full counting approach. Using the fractional counting approach, normalized impact indicators correct not only for differences between fields in citation density but also for differences between fields in collaboration practices.

In addition to the full and the fractional counting approach, there are also other approaches that can be taken to deal with the credit allocation problem. Most of these approaches rely on the order of the authors in the author list of a publication. They for instance allocate the credits of a publication mostly, or even exclusively, to the first or the last author of a publication, or sometimes to the corresponding author. However, there are no universal norms that determine the order of the authors in the author list of a publication, and relying on this order therefore always involves some uncertainty. Most importantly, different fields have different practices for determining the order of authors. In some fields, in particular in economics, high energy physics, and mathematics, it is common practice to order authors alphabetically. Credit allocation clearly should not be based on the order of authors in these fields.

Author self-citations

Author self-citations are often excluded from the calculation of impact indicators. Many self-citations are given for perfectly valid reasons. Nevertheless, if self-citations are not excluded from the calculation of impact indicators, they can be used to

manipulate the indicators in a relatively easy way. To prevent such manipulation, CWTS excludes self-citations by default in its analyses.

Impact indicators for journals

Indicators of scientific impact can also be calculated for journals. The best-known example of an impact indicator for journals is the journal impact factor. The impact factor of a journal essentially equals the average number of citations received in a certain year by publications that appeared in the journal in the two preceding years. The journal impact factor, calculated by Clarivate Analytics based on Web of Science data, is published in the Journal Citation Reports. Other examples of impact indicators for journals are the 5-year impact factor and the article influence score, which are also published in the Journal Citation Reports, and CiteScore, SJR, and SNIP, which are made available by Elsevier based on Scopus data.

Journal impact indicators are often used not only for evaluating journals but also for evaluating individual publications in a journal, or the research units by which individual publications have been authored. This is a controversial way of using journal impact indicators. Within a journal, there are typically large differences between publications in the number of citations they receive, and therefore it is often considered inappropriate to use a journal impact indicator for evaluating individual publications in a journal. The San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (www.ascb.org/dora/), an influential statement that has been signed by a large number of individuals and organizations, for instance rejects the use of journal impact indicators at the level of individual publications.

CWTS does not reject the use of journal impact indicators for evaluating individual publications. Journals have different quality standards, and this is partly reflected by journal impact indicators. Hence, journal impact indicators can be used for evaluating individual publications because they provide information about the quality standards of the journals in which publications have appeared. In addition to the journal impact indicators mentioned above, other journal impact indicators can be used as well. For instance, the mean normalized citation score, discussed earlier in this chapter, can be calculated for journals, and the publications of a research unit can then be evaluated using the mean normalized citation scores of the journals in which they have appeared. This results in an indicator that is referred to as the mean normalized journal score at CWTS.

Responsible use of bibliometrics

Bibliometrics offers powerful tools to support research management and research evaluation. However, these tools should be used in a responsible way. The following eight principles can be used as guidelines for the responsible use of bibliometrics.

1 Be aware of the limited coverage of bibliometric data sources

Bibliometric data sources such as Web of Science and Scopus offer only a limited coverage of the scientific literature. International journals in the sciences are typically well covered, but coverage of national journals, journals in the social sciences and humanities, and conference proceedings and books is much more limited. One should be aware of the consequences of this for bibliometric analyses.

2 Acknowledge the importance of accurate data collection

Accurate data collection is essential for high-quality bibliometric analyses. Poor data collection may result in bibliometric analyses that provide incorrect or misleading conclusions. The efforts needed for accurate data collection should not be underestimated. In a research evaluation context, the units under evaluation should have the opportunity to verify the data collection.

3 Recognize that bibliometric analyses capture research performance only in a partial manner

It is essential to recognize that bibliometric analyses reflect only specific aspects of the performance of research units. For instance, citation statistics provide insight into the scientific impact of research units, but they do not capture the broader societal impact. Also, bibliometric analyses focus on the outputs of the research process and typically do not consider the inputs. This for instance means that bibliometric analyses provide no insight into the productivity of research units.

4 Account for differences between scientific fields in publication, authorship, and citation practices

Different scientific fields have different publication, authorship, and citation practices. Publications in the life sciences for instance tend to have more authors and tend to receive more citations than publications in the social sciences. In bibliometric analyses that extend over multiple fields, differences between fields should be carefully accounted for. This can be done by normalizing bibliometric indicators for field differences or by comparing research units with relevant benchmarks active in the same field.

5 Find an appropriate balance between transparency and analytical sophistication

Transparency of a bibliometric analysis helps to ensure that the analysis is interpreted correctly and facilitates a well-informed discussion about the outcomes of the analysis. Analytical sophistication, for instance the use of advanced field-normalized bibliometric indicators, has the potential to provide insights that are hard to obtain using more straightforward bibliometric approaches. Unfortunately, an increase in analytical sophistication often causes a decrease in transparency. Bibliometric analyses therefore require a careful trade-off between transparency and analytical sophistication.

6 Embrace the value of multidimensional and contextualized bibliometrics

Bibliometrics is sometimes used as a tool for making one-dimensional performance measurements. When bibliometrics is used in this way, its value is limited. To take full advantage of bibliometric information, a multidimensional and contextualized approach to bibliometrics needs to be adopted. Such an approach recognizes that research management and research evaluation benefit from being supported by diverse types of information. It also recognizes that bibliometric information needs to be contextualized (e.g., by explicitly linking the information to the underlying data) to enable in-depth interpretation of the information.

7 Use bibliometrics as part of a broader range of information sources

Bibliometrics offers just one source of information to support research management and research evaluation. There are other sources of information as well. In addition to quantitative sources, for instance data on research funding and research staff and altmetric data (e.g., data on Mendeley, Twitter, blogs, etc.), this also includes peer review by scientific experts. The use of bibliometrics should be considered within this broader context. The best way to support research management and research evaluation typically is to combine bibliometric information with other information sources.

8 Anticipate the effects of bibliometric analyses on the science system

The use of bibliometrics for research management and research evaluation purposes is likely to influence the behavior of researchers and other actors in the science system. These actors may change their behavior both in intended and in unintended ways. It is important to anticipate these effects of the use of bibliometrics and to be aware that

a strong reliance on bibliometrics may have undesirable consequences (e.g., researchers trying to improve their citation statistics in questionable ways).

Leiden Manifesto

The above principles for the responsible use of bibliometrics have partly been derived from the Leiden Manifesto, an influential statement presenting best practice guidelines for the proper use of numerical indicators in research evaluations. The Leiden Manifesto is available at www.leidenmanifesto.org.

Annex C: The impact of language

Some extra analysis have been conducted to find out the reasons to possibly explain the rather weak performance of AUT, CH and GER.

- (1) Regarding the format of publications, since this study only focusses on articles and reviews covered by the WoS core collection, we do not have that information about other type of scientific/scholarly output (e.g. books).
- (2) However, an interesting finding was found regarding the language used for the set of publications. The two tables – Table 1 and Table 2 – presented in the attached document called ‘Specific_question_ASB’ show the results in more details. As seen in Table1, the share of Non-English publication output within the field of Educational Sciences for Austria, Germany and Switzerland is much higher than the other benchmark countries; their percentage is respectively 14,6%, 37,2% and 22,7%. Besides, the Table 2 shows that the impact indicators (MNCS, MNJS and PP(top 10%)) score higher in the case of publications written English for all benchmark countries. Indeed, by default, our impact indicators are based on publications published in the WoS regardless the language. But English is the international scientific language and the WoS is a worldwide database. So in this international context, the chance to be cited, when a publication is in English, is higher.

Table 1. Total publication output and share of Non-English publications in the field of Educational Sciences per country, (2000 – 2016)

Country	P	Share of P (Non English)
Austria	522	14,6%
Belgium	2043	3,7%
Denmark	778	0,4%
Finland	1891	0,4%
Germany	6557	37,2%
Netherlands	5912	2,9%
Norway	1622	0,7%
Sweden	2423	0,3%
Switzerland	1210	22,7%
UK	21650	0,3%

Table 2. Bibliometric indicators for the field of Educational Sciences per country for English publications (EN) and publications in other languages (Other), (2000-2016)

Country	Language	P	MNCS	PP(top 10%)	MNJS
Austria	EN	446	1,02	10%	0,96
Austria	Other	76	0,32	2%	0,35
Belgium	EN	1967	1,13	11%	1,10
Belgium	Other	76	0,21	2%	0,25
Denmark	EN	775	0,90	7%	0,94
Denmark	Other	3	0,00	0%	0,04
Finland	EN	1883	0,97	9%	0,97
Finland	Other	8	0,61	13%	0,73
Germany	EN	4119	1,20	13%	1,15
Germany	Other	2438	0,33	2%	0,33
Netherlands	EN	5741	1,29	14%	1,23
Netherlands	Other	171	0,11	0%	0,11
Norway	EN	1611	1,00	9%	0,98
Norway	Other	11	0,43	0%	0,37
Sweden	EN	2415	0,96	7%	0,96
Sweden	Other	8	0,09	0%	0,09
Switzerland	EN	935	1,09	10%	1,05
Switzerland	Other	275	0,30	1%	0,33
UK	EN	21584	1,05	10%	1,02
UK	Other	66	0,20	3%	0,18

Version of September 7th, 2018

Determining the Status of Austrian Education Research

Background Report: Interviews

Brigitte Tiefenthaler, Katharina Warta

Determining the Status of Austrian Education Research

Background Report: Interviews

technopolis_{group} September 2018

Authors: Brigitte Tiefenthaler, Katharina Warta

Translation: Dr. Billaudelle & Partner

Contents

1	Introduction.....	1
2	Executive Summary.....	3
3	Strong points	5
4	Weak points	7
5	“Key players”	11
6	Innovation potential.....	12
7	Transfers	13
7.1	Transfer to educational institutions and educational practice	14
7.2	Transfer to politics and administration	15
8	Possible measures	17
	Appendix A Lead questions for the interviews	19

1 Introduction

Background

The FWF Science Fund was commissioned by the Innovation Foundation for Education with the coordination of determining the status of Austrian education research. This will be performed as part of an Informed Peer Review process by an evaluation commission consisting of international experts, who reflect the disciplinary breadth of the field. The commission will be supported in its work with qualitative and quantitative background materials on education research in Austria, which include interviews, an online survey, bibliometrics and various data materials. The Technopolis Group Austria was commissioned with performing the interviews and the online survey. In this report we summarise the results of the interviews, which were held by Brigitte Tiefenthaler and Katharina Warta.

Task

The content of this study includes 22 in-depth interviews with people from the area of education research on their observations and appraisals of education research in Austria. In contrast to standardised interviews, in-depth interviews enable the specific situation of those interviewed to be addressed flexibly by inviting the interviewee to reflect, instead of simply gathering information. They can also focus on key issues themselves and the interviewer can ask in detail about topics that only come up during the interview.

The lead questions for the interviews (see Appendix A) were set by the principal, and also formed the pattern for their analysis and for structuring this report. In each interview the depth and order of dealing with the questions was largely determined by the dynamic of the interview. The interviews lasted between one and two hours and were held in person, by Skype or by telephone.

For selecting the people to be interviewed, we received a list of possible interviewees from the FWF at the beginning of the study, including a reserve list in case any of those first asked were subsequently unavailable for an interview. 22 people were interviewed. In selecting the interviewees we ensured the core issues and the geographical and institutional breadth of education research was covered as much as possible. The targets for this specified by the principal were met here with one exception:

Table 1 Quantitative criteria to ensure the right balance with the group of people interviewed

Criterion	Values achieved	Goal achievement and comment
At least 40% women and men	12 women (55%), 10 men (45%)	Target value achieved
Age: Approx. 25% <45 years old	3 people under 45 (14%)	Target value not achieved The selection list included 7 people under 45. Of these, 2 people declined because of time reasons, 2 could not be reached despite several attempts to do so.
Region: Approx. 50% outside of Vienna	6 people in Vienna (27%), 14 people outside of Vienna (64%), 2 people abroad (9%)	Target value achieved
Approx. 1/3 not from universities	14 people from universities (64%), 8 people from TTCs, non-university research institutes, ministries (36%)	Target value achieved

Source: Target values FWF; real values Technopolis

Report

In the following chapters we outline the results of the 22 interviews, whereby we quote from the interviews by way of illustration. The statements of the interviewees converge significantly on the whole,

right across all specialist areas and institutional backgrounds. Where there are specifics, for the individual types of players or sub-areas in education research, for example, we refer to these in the text. We have added to the text at points with Internet addresses for sources that were named for us in interviews and which we last visited on 20 August 2018.

The report is part of the background materials for determining the status of Austrian education research. It is therefore not a complete portrayal of education research in Austria, but rather makes a contribution to it, that is the combined “inside view” of 22 experienced people.

We thank everyone that was kind enough to do an interview!

2 Executive Summary

The FWF Science Fund was commissioned by the Innovation Foundation for Education with the coordination of determining the status of Austrian education research, which will be performed by an evaluation commission as an Informed Peer Review. This report is part of the background materials for this. It is based on 22 in-depth interviews with people from the area of education research on their observations and appraisals of education research in Austria and therefore presents the combined “inside view” of the interviewees. Our interview experience shows that the researchers are keen to participate in the discourse and that the framework conditions for education research in Austria are not easy. As a result, on the whole, difficulties were mentioned more frequently than strong points and achievements.

Education research in Austria is small and fragmented and shaped largely by innovative, dedicated individual people. Some of them are also perceived on an international level, but they mostly belong to older generations. In recent years empirical education research has indeed developed positively, but there are scarcely any institutionally well-anchored areas. The interviewees believe there are very few specific strong points in education research in Austria, and especially in the international comparison.

Good networking via the Austrian Association for Education Research and Development (ÖFEB) and between research and education administration in general were named as strong points in Austria, as was the new research orientation of the university colleges of teacher education with parallel axiomatic access to and connection with practical application. Access to the field was also rated as good for the most part. Various larger projects have provided development impetus in Austrian education research’s recent past and bolstered cooperation. These included development projects, the national education report and participation in major international studies.

Many of those interviewed see the low appreciation for education research as a fundamental weak point. As a consequence of the structural weaknesses, there is only very little development of junior staff, and in some areas there is also a lack of young talent. Many of those we interviewed think Austrian education researchers are not well connected or visible in international terms and observe an (overly) strong orientation towards the German-speaking area.

Unlike Germany and Switzerland, in Austria there is no specific funding by the responsible federal ministry and alternative funding options are scarce. It is therefore difficult to realize structure-forming, long-term projects. The resources and stimuli for structured promotion of junior staff, application-oriented (cooperative) research and international cooperation are also frequently amiss. The available funds for contract research from the public sector have fallen sharply in recent years – award practice is criticized as intransparent.

The research skills of the university colleges of teacher education and their connections with the scientific community have grown, but on the whole are still relatively weak. Their legal form as a lower level agency of the Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research is no advantage for their development as research institutions, due in particular to the legally specified structures and employment legislation. The resources available for research are low, while teaching responsibilities are high.

At the universities there are only very few long-term research priorities in education research and staffing numbers are low in some areas, such as teaching methodology, elementary and primary level, and university research, for example. The multiple stressing of scientific staff is high, and the career prospects for junior staff scientists are often unattractive and there is a growing academic precariousness.

The universities with pedagogical and educational science institutes were mentioned as institutional “key players” of education research in Austria. The university colleges of teacher education are also key players, whereby their contribution to education research is still small. Institutions with unique structural features also apply as further key players, especially BIFIE, the four development networks, the

Austrian Association for Education Research and Development and the Austrian Educational Competence Centres (AECC). There is also a series of mostly non-university players, who are established in sub-areas of education research, often in a predominantly advisory capacity.

Almost all interviewees believe the transfer of scientific findings to practical application, both to the educational institutions and players in educational practice and to the administrative and political decision makers, is difficult for different reasons. This is due firstly to the fact that the transfer possibilities are basically limited, secondly to current government policy and thirdly to the low perceived importance that transfer is attributed on the academic side in contrast to the focus on science. There are, however, also positive transfer experiences, especially with people that work (also) application-oriented and at regional level.

Specific funding was proposed as an important measure for the further development of education research, which would enable the setting of long-term key priorities and would be awarded in competition via a fair and transparent selection process, which would also include applied research, structured promotion of junior staff and stronger international connections. The obstructive framework conditions for research should be reformed for the university colleges of teacher education. The access to and use of available data should also be further improved. Last but not least, almost all of those interviewed suggest more specific work on the connection between research and practical application. Activities of this kind should be made an explicit part of the range of tasks of university researchers, and many therefore also called for a rethinking of how scientific work can be combined with orientation towards societal relevance.

3 Strong points

“Where do you think Austrian education research’s strong points are in the international comparison? What research topics, programmes, institutions or people does this involve?”

The most important results of this survey include the fact that the interviewees believe there are scarcely any specific strong points in education research in Austria, and especially in the international comparison. Education research in Austria is **small and fragmented** and during the interviews, most of the features that were rated as positive were nonetheless accompanied by a “but”(for this see chapter, “Weak points”).

Education research is shaped by innovative individual people, who in part are also visible internationally, but who mostly belong to older generations. Our interviewees believe there are scarcely any institutionally well anchored areas of strength in Austria (i.e. staffed with appropriate numbers of professors or similarly qualified researchers and appropriate teams and for appropriately long periods).

In this context we also have the question as to what the educational sciences include, as some people who are also profiled with educational scientific topics, must actually be assigned to professionally adjacent disciplines, e.g. psychology, in which, however, other framework conditions and in some cases other research paradigms dominate.

From a domestic Austrian viewpoint various **structural conditions** are named as strong points in terms of positively rated features of education research, some of which still have much scope for expansion:

- The good networking via the Austrian Association for Education Research and Development (ÖFEB¹).
- The benefits of being small: Many players know one another, not only within research, but also between research and education administration. This fragmentation and these contacts also enable innovations, mostly as part of pilot projects.
- The new research orientation of the university colleges of teacher education with parallel axiomatic access to and connection with practical application.

Access to the field was rated as good for the most part, but differs regionally and depends in part on personal contacts in education administration. Some of those interviewed observed that this is different in other European countries, where highly formalised access is often the norm. But there are also difficulties with access to the field, especially with a current ordinance in Vienna, which only allows scientific surveys in schools outside of the curricula-based class and forbids video recordings².

Various **larger projects** have provided development impetus in Austrian education research’s recent past and bolstered cooperation. The interviewees therefore mostly consider them strong points (but there were also some points of criticism here, see chapter, “Weak points”):

- Major development projects at the “politics – science – practical application” interface, e.g. the “Innovations Make Schools Top – IMST” initiative, which supports innovations in the classroom for the STEM + German subjects³, the surveying of education standards and the school development activities connected with them, especially for those schools that got bad results with the sur-

¹ <https://www.oefeb.at/>

² Vienna Board of Education, “[Scientific Surveys at Schools](#)” ordinance, 29 May 2017

³ <https://www.imst.ac.at/>

vey (e. g. “Grundkompetenzen absichern (Ensuring basic skills)” project)⁴, or the Leadership Academy for qualifying managers in the school sector⁵. These were named as examples for how the cooperation between education research, administration and the schools can work.

- National education reports⁶: National education reports have been published every three years since 2009 under the auspices of BIFIE. Several interviewees positively emphasized both the information basis created here and the cooperation of experts from different institutions in compiling the individual chapters and the external quality controls in particular.
- The participation in major international studies (PISA, TIMSS, PIRLS, TALIS⁷) is mostly seen as positive, as it has created a data basis, which, however, many also believe could and should be used more in research. Some interviewees also fear that the significance of this data is overestimated by some players, especially in politics, and that abbreviated conclusions will be drawn, without the data actually being sufficiently understood and interpreted.

Some people named positive aspects with **specific topics**:

- Empirical education research has developed positively in recent years; research orientation has increased on the whole, and also with the reform of the university colleges of teacher education.
- There is a high level of know-how and commitment from individual people, even under difficult framework conditions.
- Austrian researchers have in particular profiled themselves (internationally as well) with participative research methods and action research. School development research is also internationally visible, especially case vignettes research.
- University research has developed positively in the last 20 years, particularly in application-oriented contract research and demand-side at the universities as well, so closer to consultation. Parts of administration played an important role in the positive development here with their demand. Key players can be found here at non-university institutions.
- The foundation and development of BIFIE was rated positively on the whole: It plays a key role and performs important tasks, particularly in the context of the major international studies and the data situation connected with them, as well as with the national education report (for criticism also expressed here see, “Weak points”).
- The foundation of the “Zeitschrift für Bildungsforschung” improved the options for scientific publication.

Selected quotes:

“We have good people, but no strong points in the international comparison.”

“I get the impression that individual, very dedicated people work here, under framework conditions that make it difficult to be competitive in the international comparison.”

“Know-how and motivation. Which, however, is only used very piecemeal.”

“Honestly, nothing good at all with regard to education at schools.”

⁴<https://bildung.bmbwf.gv.at/schulen/unterricht/ba/bildungsstandards.html>; <http://www.sqa.at/>

⁵<https://www.leadershipacademy.at/>

⁶<https://www.bifie.at/material/nationale-bildungsberichterstattung/>

⁷<https://www.bifie.at/material/internationale-studien/>

“I see very little institutional profiling, unlike in Germany where there are far more professorships, and it’s easier to develop strengths. In Austria and Switzerland we tend to diversify rather than concentrate, and with just one person and their group, one cannot have an impact on research.”

“In Austria I can think of people and their topics, but no programmes, especially none larger than FWF projects.”

“I think the national education reports are strong points. They bring key researchers together in teams time and again and provide a very good overview. At the same time and despite its quality the report has no effect on practice or policy.”

4 Weak points

“Where do you think Austrian education research’s weak points are in the international comparison? What’s missing in education research, and why?”

“More weak points than strong points” was the general opinion in most interviews. Some of the weak points described in the following are classified by the people interviewed as dormant potential or intermediate stages in ongoing developments (e.g. with the university colleges of teacher education).

Many of those interviewed see little **appreciation** for education research or for its specific work area and the expertise of education researchers is often not acknowledged by the body politic or the general public. The public debate goes on and on, often without any reference to empirical evidence. In the academic field other disciplines, e.g. psychology or linguistics, are better established and recognised as “more scientific”, even when specific projects cover the same research content.

Education research in Austria is weakly structured: In the international comparison there are **no bigger, visible, powerful units**; for the most part only individual excellent people are visible (including quite a few already retired or just about to retire), which means for the most part only a few people champion a cause and there is very little institutional profiling. The personalisation of research topics is even clearer in university colleges of teacher education, where there are essentially no structures for research groups. **Very little systematic research cooperation** in bigger projects is therefore evident.

It follows from the structural weaknesses and the resource scarcity connected with them that there is only **very little development of junior staff**; in some areas there is also a lack of young talent and therefore the danger that positions will remain unstaffed and topics neglected after their most important exponents retire or relocate. At some institutions and in some work areas there is a lack of sufficiently qualified people to support young scientists (e.g. young scientists are entrusted with the task of establishing a topic, but have no professors or similarly qualified people to help them there and then).

Many of those we interviewed believe Austrian education researchers are not **well connected or visible in international terms**. They think the participation in the international discourse is weak and find very few relevant international publications. Many interviewees believe this is due to a widespread preference in publication activity for the German language and formats that are not very international (“edited versions and compendium culture”). Some interviewees also believe even interesting work is sometimes not published at all in internationally visible journals or at conferences. There is a strong orientation towards the German-speaking area – Germany and Switzerland. Relatively few

people have a stronger international focus as well (e.g. the Netherlands, Scandinavia, the Balkans or the British-Anglo-American sphere). Many interviewees also indicated that it is difficult to finance setting up and maintaining international contacts, as firstly the institutional funds intended for this are low, and secondly very few third-party funding sources are available for education research.

Funding and contract research

Insufficient funding options and therefore very few development options are a very significant weak point of the framework conditions for education research in the international comparison (especially German-speaking). There is **no specific funding** by the responsible federal ministry (unlike in Germany or Switzerland⁸) and there are scarcely any alternative funding bodies either, like the various foundations in Germany, for example. The latter also functioned in the past as pathfinders and provided new stimuli in education research, earlier than the politicians.

The generally low approval rates at the FWF, which also impacts on projects with good ratings, are also criticised. Some interviewees have the impression that the specifics of education research are not always sufficiently taken into account with the selection of reviewers. Conversely there is also criticism for the quality of education research in Austria, e.g. in methodological approaches, which cannot hold their own in international competition.

The funding for application-oriented or applied research in Austria is also almost exclusively oriented towards natural sciences, technical sciences and industrial applications. Although education research also has a strong development reference, it is excluded from such programmes, with very few exceptions. The funding for international cooperation with non-European countries (e.g. African countries) is generally only possible via funding in development aid, which therefore is connected with unsuitable funding conditions for research cooperation on an equal basis.

As a result of this lack of funding options, potential, structure-forming and/or long-term projects that go beyond the typical research project are scarcely possible. The resources and stimuli for structured promotion of junior staff and for application-oriented cooperative research, as well as international cooperation, are also frequently amiss.

At public authorities the available funds for contract research have fallen sharply in recent years. Many interviewees also criticized the largely intransparent awarding of contract research and evaluations; these funds are often awarded on the basis of personal relationships, and rarely on the basis of clear, competitive procedures according to comprehensible criteria and expertise. This discriminates against scientific young talent, as this type of contract awarding almost always favours established individuals.

University colleges of teacher education

On the whole the research skills and connections of the university colleges of teacher education with the *scientific community* are still relatively weak, whereby the various colleges differ significantly. The situation of the university colleges of teacher education is difficult on several levels for their development into research universities:

- The legal form as a lower level agency (“nachgeordnete Dienststelle”) of the Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research (BMBWF) is no advantage for the organisation of research groups, due in particular to the legally specified structure and employment legislation.
- The provision of resources and staffing capacities for research are low⁹, the level of teaching responsibilities is high.

⁸ Germany: <https://www.foerderinfo.bund.de/de/empirische-bildungsforschung-207.php>

Switzerland: <https://www.swissuniversities.ch/de/organisation/projekte-und-programme/p-11/>

⁹ Statistik Austria’s most recent complete R&D survey shows that 74.4 full-time equivalents were employed for R&D at all university colleges of teacher education in 2015. See BMBWF, [Statistisches Taschenbuch 2017](#), table 8.

- Unlike institute directors at universities, those at university colleges of teacher education by law do not perform their own research. The crediting of previous periods of service by the responsible BMBWF is often perceived as formalistic, especially for newcomers. Added to this are the inability to bring on board third-party funding projects and the fact that the rector has no influence on remuneration and crediting. The university colleges of teacher education therefore are not very attractive as employers for highly qualified researchers, which makes recruiting for research more difficult.
- The usage possibilities and access to third-party funding are restricted or at least difficult, because of the partial legal capacity. For example, it is not possible to contribute matching funds required with many funding programmes with in-kind contributions based on the work of staff employed at a university college of teacher education, as their participation in third-party funding projects is not allowed during their service period; nor are there any employment opportunities for third-party funded staff in fixed-term contracts, and the rector is personally liable.
- University colleges of teacher education have no right to award doctorates and therefore only limited options for training their own scientific junior staff. This is especially seen as problematic in research fields where the universities have no or only a very recent research tradition (e. g. on the primary level, “Primarstufe”). For qualified university lecturers this reduces the motivation to change to a university college of teacher education.

Several interviewees essentially question the current legal form of university colleges of teacher education and call for full autonomy, but there is also the view that the conditions within the existing partial legal capacity could be improved by, for example, achieving the required flexibility by amending the laws (employment legislation in particular) and a research-appropriate interpretation (with the crediting of previous periods of service for example). In this context it was indicated that the university colleges of teacher education as research institutions essentially have the character of departmental research institutions.

Universities

Concerning education research at universities, the following weak points were named:

- Long-term research priorities in education research are rare. Some important areas in university research are also weak or insufficiently staffed – named here were teaching methodology, elementary and primary level, and university research. There is catch-up requirement here, whereby the positive development in teaching methodology was also referred to, not least of all with the setting up of the Austrian Educational Competence Centres (AECC)¹⁰.
- The multiple stressing of scientific staff is high in the international comparison, especially with high teaching obligations and the partially very high student numbers per professor and the low number of assistants per professor, especially in teacher training¹¹.
- The career prospects for junior staff scientists are often unattractive and there is a growing academic precariousness¹². Therefore only very few teachers also opt for a career in research, so there is a lack of people with teaching practice at schools in university education research.
- The institutional funding for financing trips, publications, equipment, etc. is very low compared with the situation in Germany or Switzerland, for example, which is exacerbated even more by the low availability of third-party funds¹³. This restricts the options for international contacts, conference visits or open access publications, for example.

¹⁰<https://bildung.bmbwf.gv.at/schulen/schubf/se/aecc.html>

¹¹ This also applies for other massively attended subjects.

¹² This is not specific to education research.

¹³To illustrate: University managers assume that the costs for this will be settled via third-party funds. Professors typically receive about EUR 1,000 per year from their university for their travel costs. Travel funding for junior scientific staff has not been valorised for years in some places, although the costs for conferences have risen significantly.

The relationship between universities and university colleges of teacher education is partially perceived as difficult. The requirements for cooperation differ for the various education levels due to the respective responsibilities in teacher training: Primary education, secondary level vocational education and further teacher training are the primacy of the university colleges of teacher education. University colleges of teacher education and universities cooperate in secondary level general education, whereby the four regional development networks play a key role¹⁴. The interviewees that expressed an opinion on this topic emphasize that it is important the cooperation be systematically strengthened, especially in teacher training and in research.

A number of interviewees also saw a weak connection between research, teaching and teacher training. Although the development projects (e.g. IMST, education standards) named here in the “Strong points” chapter have provided stimuli and also already shown effects, they will however be terminated or discontinued without follow-up projects.

National and international studies and data management

The positive aspects of participating in different major international studies (PISA, TIMSS etc.) were illustrated in the “Strong points” chapter, and in particular the data situation connected with them. However, many interviewees believe this available data is underused. The access to this data available at BIFIE was evaluated very differently in the past, which is presumably due to the access regulations that changed over the years. In this context several interviewees criticized the fact that generally not enough data (including their own) is made available for secondary use, which also entails the danger of overburdening schools.

While the national education reports on the whole were positively rated as an evidence base and on the basis of their quality, there was also individual criticism, namely for the selection of people responsible for chapters and authors, which some interviewees find intransparent, while there was also criticism for the insufficient systematic following up of topics. It is also regretted that there is hardly any response from the political target groups.

Methodology

Education research is a wide-ranging field in which both different methodological approaches and different thematic foci exist alongside one another. The interviews demonstrated how the delimitation to other sub-areas or approaches is primarily specified via methodological issues. Several interviewees observed a growing influence of the quantitative-empirical methods to the detriment of qualitative and combined methods and are critical of this.¹⁵ Others believe there is little quantitatively oriented research in Austria, and that qualitative and theoretical approaches tend to dominate. Still more see the weak point in the fact that multi-method approaches that combine qualitative and quantitative methods in a mutually complementary way are not sufficiently applied. The statements do, however, show that the subdivision into qualitative and quantitative falls short, as different issues are dealt with in each of the topical areas and different standards are applied for choosing the methods for this. The question of data access is also an issue here, as it is influenced by different interests, both with the wide-ranging surveys as part of the major studies mentioned above and with primary surveys by researchers as part of their own projects.

Selected quotes:

“The framework conditions for vigorous education research are not as one

¹⁴ <https://bildung.bmbwf.gv.at/schulen/pbneu/ev/verbuende.html>

¹⁵ Negative experiences with technically incorrect interpretations of statistics by decision makers play a role here as well; see also the “Transfers” chapter.

would wish them.”

“It is increasingly more difficult for researchers. Stress limits are exceeded with many researchers. There are increasingly more students, but university staff is not increasing appropriately.”

“Empirical research is not developed enough to be internationally competitive.”

“Much of what is good is not internationally visible. Much of what happens on the international scene is not perceived here.”

“The insufficient breadth is a big problem. This is linked with the country’s small scale, but especially with the fact that there are no large, specific research programmes. In Germany, for example, there are these large scale education research programmes with numerous tenders for researchers and support for junior staff – there is no equivalent in Austria”.

“I don’t meet many other Austrians at conferences.”

“Very few publish in international media.”

5 “Key players”

“What people and institutions are key players in education research in Austria?”

Many interviewees were reserved on this point, especially with evaluative conclusions. The interviews made it clear that some universities are key players in top quality education research, however very few names are given or judgements specified – the observation is that a culture of mutual respect and a certain degree of caution is expressed here.

The universities with pedagogical and educational science institutes were generally named as institutional “key players”, so the universities in Graz, Innsbruck, Klagenfurt, Linz, Salzburg and Vienna. In addition to this the university colleges of teacher education are also key players, whereby their contribution to education research is currently growing, but is still small. Donauuniversität Krems was also named for higher education research, where the Upper Austria University of Applied Sciences also plays a role.

Many individual people were also named as key players, including retirees. This concurs with the observations on an important structural feature of Austrian education research illustrated above.

Institutions with unique structural features were frequently named:

- BIFIE because of its special position and task
- The four development networks, where the traditional boundaries between universities and university colleges of teacher education are transcended
- The Austrian Association for Education Research and Development (ÖFEB) as a central, connecting platform
- Austrian Educational Competence Centres (AECC) with their importance for the development of teaching methodology

Networking roles in specific sub-fields of education research are played by the “Österreichische Gesellschaft für Fachdidaktik” and the “Netzwerk Hochschulforschung”.

Other players were also named individually, especially non-university institutions that are active in sub-areas of education research, and some also in an advisory capacity:

- The “Institut für Höhere Studien” (IHS)
- The “Wirtschaftsforschungsinstitut” (WIFO)
- The “Institut für Bildungsforschung der Wirtschaft”

Individual interviewees also said that players that do not perform research themselves play or have played a decisive role, especially as principals or business partners, which include players from federal or state level education administration.

6 Innovation potential

“Do you know of any Austrian education research projects of recent years that have or could have high innovation potential for education institutions/players?”

Many interviewees at first found this question difficult, often commenting that they do not know many projects or not well enough. Nevertheless topics or circumstances were named, which must be categorised here. This often entails developments that have started (e.g. realignment of the university colleges of teacher education) or options that are still not used enough (e.g. use of available data). This topic is also closely connected with the topic of measures (for this see chapter 8).

University colleges of teacher education

The **development of the university colleges of teacher education** towards becoming actual research-active universities was named particularly frequently. Many interviewees believe there is major innovation potential here despite numerous weak points in the current situation, and especially for development-oriented education research. Positive stimuli are expected here from the parallel support by the “Qualitätssicherungsrat für Pädagoginnen- und Pädagogenbildung”¹⁶ (Quality assurance board for teacher training), provided it focuses accordingly on research. But more time for setting up and expanding research capacities is required so the potential connected with this development can actually be exploited:

“After ten years development work we now have the first international publications and appearances at international conferences.”

Data management

Several interviewees see significant innovation potential for education research in **data management**. This includes better access to available data and its more systematic use. This primarily applies to data from the major studies such as PISA, TIMSS, etc., but other data as well. There is also much potential for research in a more systematic, cooperative establishment of good cohorts and data records.

Cooperation and opening up

A number of people interviewed expect stimuli for the development of Austrian education research from both a thematic and methodology point of view with **stronger participation in the international discourse**. Some scientists from Austria are involved internationally as co-publishers of in-

¹⁶<https://www.qsr.or.at>

ternational magazines or panel members with funding programmes – further stimuli for innovation could be produced by building on this network.

A **stronger connection of the competencies** within education research and the cooperation with empirical competencies of other specialist areas (e.g. psychology) could open up new possibilities for education research. There are already good conditions here, for example, for both horizontal and vertical networking in the four regional development networks.

The strengthening of participative approaches in research was named with regard to the role of education research for the further development of the education system. It was also commented that there are numerous projects with innovative approaches, which, however, are not evaluated sufficiently. The innovation potential in such cases is hidden in structurally anchored feedback loops.

7 Transfers

“Do you see a systematic problem with the transfer of scientific findings of education research to practical application? And if so, why?”

In addition to general aspects of the transfer of scientific results of education research to practical application the transfer to the essential target groups was also discussed, i.e. firstly to the educational institutions and players in educational practice and secondly to the administrative and political decision makers.

Almost all interviewees believe the transfer of scientific findings to practical application is difficult and for different reasons. Some reasons are basic in nature (keyword: theory-practice-gap), others tend to be contingent or specific to the current education policy situation in Austria and could therefore also be essentially shaped accordingly (e.g. the current government policy, the resources, the low perceived importance that is attributed to the transfer in contrast to the focus on science). The interviewees also had very different experiences with the success or failure of transfer.

Many of them believe a basic limitation of the possibilities of transfer is a key factor: Scientific findings cannot be implemented 1:1 and nor do they include recommendations on their use. Furthermore they must be reflected and contextualised for the respective situation.

Transfer is not a priority for the researchers oriented on the values system of findings-oriented basic research, especially those at universities, and receives little or no acknowledgement in Austria; the importance and magnitude of relevant activities are mostly correspondingly low. Many interviewees regret this.

The ideas and communication requirements of scientists and practitioners are also very different and difficult to reconcile. Many scientists do not have the expertise required for the communication beyond their own world of expertise and only very few know the teaching practices at schools from own experience.

On the other hand the education research specialists are often not sufficiently recognised by the body politic, administration and the general public and anecdotal (own) practical experience is increasingly more trusted than empirical evidence. Education research also has hardly any easily accessible media and public presence. This is not just a question of one’s ability to mediate scientific content; it is basically also difficult, as the results of education research are mostly highly differentiated and therefore less “snappy” in their conveyance than many results in the natural and technical sciences.

Selected quotes:

“Oh yeah ..., EVERYONE is an expert in the public debate!”

“I’ve noticed that basic research in the area I work in is never purely basic research, because there is always a usage reference.”

“This is a structural problem, but it’s not specific to Austria. There aren’t enough interfaces where practice and research really come together. There is a tension field between obligation to collect and obligation to bring. The dialogue is not clearly established, spoken or written.”

“I have never seen an example where knowledge from research was applied in practice.”

“There is a balancing act between social relevance and international scientific career. (...) There is indeed the ‘third mission’ of the universities, but ‘third’ also refers to significance.”

“Transfer is only promoted at the normative level, but receives practically no appreciation! This is clearly different in Germany for example.”

7.1 Transfer to educational institutions and educational practice

The observations and experiences of our interviewees on the transfer to educational practice differ greatly and range from not seeing any transfers at all to successful development projects where transfer happens with joint research and development. Positive experiences with transfer were therefore mostly made with people that (also) work on the application-oriented side of education research, e.g. at university colleges of teacher education, in teaching methodology, in higher education research, or with action research and participative approaches in direct research cooperation with teachers; there are also examples of successful transfers at project level. The insufficient sustainability with standard project financing and the fragmentation due to small case numbers is difficult here, resulting in findings that are difficult to generalise. There is little regard for how findings could be applied broadly and under what circumstances this would be at all possible.

A possible path of the transfer of scientific findings to educational practice is further teacher training. This is the primacy of the university colleges of teacher education. Researchers at universities report that it is difficult to systematically transfer their findings on this path. There are also hardly any long-term concepts and no structured curricula for further teacher training. But a positive example was also named, namely the four-semester teaching and teaching methodology course for teachers¹⁷.

A number of interviewees met with scientific scepticism with practitioners in the educational system and found that a lot of teaching staff have insufficient expertise in handling scientific findings. School management and teaching staff are also sceptical in places; this affects the possible benefits of participation in knowledge transfer or in joint research, and many fear the additional work could outweigh the benefits. On the other hand, individual interviewees reported how schools and education researchers support one another in current, problematic developments in federal educational policy (keyword: German classes), in order to find locally feasible, evidence-based solutions.

Almost all those interviewed said that the transfer requires own resources, and these are mostly not available at the universities, beginning with the explicit “order” to contact and exchange with practical application, to the skills and work time required for this, through to the financing. Several people mentioned solutions in other countries where researchers are supported with the transfer or where own

¹⁷<http://pfl.aau.at/>

facilities are set up for the transfer of scientific results to practical application, such as Clearing House Class at TU Munich¹⁸ or in the “*what works clearing houses*” in the UK¹⁹ and the USA²⁰.

Selected quotes:

“University colleges of teacher education have a practice reference, the access to the schools and teaching staff (via the school-practical studies and via the further training of the teaching staff), but are still not active enough in education research. Universities on the other hand have a long research tradition, but they frequently do not have access to the schools.”

“As a researcher you should publish in top-quality journals, where a very particular language is spoken, which is even difficult for reviewers, and in English at that, which normal people cannot understand and you would have to translate it into school teacher’s own way of speaking, a “teacherese” so to say. This is not acknowledged at the university, so no one does it.”

“The potential of the university colleges of teacher education is here, they are not afraid to dirty themselves with practical application!”

“The cooperation of university colleges of teacher education with schools in the development area is also good. This is essential to bring innovation to practical application. It works quite well in the elementary schools, for example, but is often inspired by pedagogical reforms, with little research.”

“Transfer cannot be a banal thing, as in ‘science finds out, teachers implement’, for example, because implementation cannot be mechanistic. It requires professional ethos and responsibility, which makes it difficult, because it’s complex. Actually it is not transfer, but rather cooperation, reinventing, re-contextualising in one’s own space.”

7.2 Transfer to politics and administration

Most interviewees believe the transfer of scientific findings to administration and especially to the body politic is difficult – more difficult than to educational practice. However, there are positive experiences, mostly at regional level (federal state), where many of those interviewed maintain good relations with school administration. The transfer to decision makers in administration and the body politic depends heavily on the people it involves. On one hand the political and administrative representatives must be open to evidence-based decisions. On the other hand, science should not act as if it were “too good” for the discussion with these players.

Most interviewees observed that the current federal government has hardly any interest in evidence-based policy making and even previously open contact partners in administration are now less approachable. In some cases, decisions are made clearly contrary to the empirical evidence, in the regulations on German classes, for example, in the issue of special schools versus inclusive education and with the reintroduction of marks in the elementary schools. Plans are also often made in educational policies, on the topics of all-day schools, migration, multilingualism or the autonomy of schools, for example, even though the required evidence for sound planning and decision making is not (sufficiently) available. The ÖFEB is not listened to as a specialist organisation either. Most interviewees believe

¹⁸<https://www.clearinghouse.edu.tum.de/>

¹⁹<https://educationendowmentfoundation.org.uk/>

²⁰<https://ies.ed.gov/ncee/wwc/>

the topic of education is extremely normative and characterised as party political; political and ideological criteria mostly outweigh empirical evidence. They believe this is more prevalent in Austria than in other countries.

Significant obstacles for an evidence-based political cycle are the different time scales. It is often difficult to coordinate legislative periods and other political time frames on one hand and the patience required from the scientific point of view on the other. Many interviewees also believe it would be important to check the effects with hindsight in the relevant processes.

Most of those interviewed believe even contract research is rarely systematically incorporated into policy making. IMST was named as a positive exception. Contract research is often far more a funding in character, so without an interest in using the results from the contractor (and without a competitive process in particular). In many cases an implementation by the principal is therefore not even an issue; at best the results contribute to knowledge acquisition and qualification with the principal or serve as an information basis for ongoing or anticipated discussions. The principal often also places a publication ban on contract research studies or only “pleasing” results are published in extract form.

Selected quotes:

“Reform-oriented parts of science administration have been one of the motors of development since the 70s of something which back was still rather rudimentary. They were interested to some degree in legitimation, but also in consultation and therefore also became promoters of innovative research.”

“I don’t get the impression that educational policy is really bothered about research. Otherwise such decisions wouldn’t be made, for example, how to teach language in the best way possible, how to run schools well, how to create stimulating learning environments ..., there are certainly no research deficits here – there is an implementation problem. Research is not integrated into political decisions. Scientific results are available.”

“Politicians have little patience for a tidy policy cycle and have a very technical understanding of change – too fast, too little understanding for the transformation.”

“How interested is the educational policy in evidence? Expertise is rarely requested and only recognised in general. Decisions are made for other reasons.”

“Austria is in fact one of the countries where education is incredibly party political in the international comparison. (...) I am amazed time and again by the conservative images dominating education, even in the minds of people who themselves have suffered under it.”

“It really is a fundamental question: On one hand the understandable desire of the politicians to be able to show an effect, on the other the sui generis limits the possibility of proof.”

“Evidence-based policy is a buzzword, the glossing over of real processes – so it can’t be implemented at the moment like this.”

“In retrospect the measures would have to be evaluated here to produce some conclusions from this ..., how to shape it better to get the targeted results.”

8 Possible measures

With their proposals for possible measures most interviewees focused on the defined weak points and in part also on the potential for innovation.

Funding

The most frequently proposed was specific funding, often with reference to relevant examples in other countries, especially the current framework programme for empirical education research in Germany and the specific funding for the Swiss universities of teacher education after their transformation into research institutions.

Specific funding for education research should ...

- enable the setting of long-term key priorities
- both promote and support cooperation, especially across and beyond the various institution types and locations and between science and practical application. Interdisciplinary research and work in the methods mix (especially of qualitative and quantitative methods) should be funded.
- be awarded in competition via a fair and transparent selection process
- offer possibilities for specific and structured junior staff support
- also support applied research and development
- be awarded both for thematically open projects with structural goals and in tenders with core priorities, especially for current research requirements
- support both the participation in the international discourse and the work on specific problem solutions
- enable research and development projects over their different phases and therefore a longer period – from researching the basic situation to the development of measures, then accompanying the measures, through to the evaluation and analysis of the results.

An appropriate funding programme would therefore also have to work with a combination of tools and both set thematic priorities and allow bottom-up defined topics. Many interviewees also believe the establishment of specialist understanding and expertise with funding agencies for the specifics of education research is important, especially with their development and application-oriented aspect.

University colleges of teacher education

A number of those interviewed called for specific support for the university colleges of teacher education in their further development towards top class research institutions. There are two different possible paths here: While some interviewees call for complete autonomy for the university colleges of teacher education, others propose adjustment and flexibilisation within the existing legal framework. In any case they believe specific research funding and the systematic cultivation of the generation change towards stronger research orientation with increased recruiting of people with research experience and the corresponding arrangement options for their working time are required. Also to be critically examined are the points where the current legal situation, especially the partial legal capacity and employment legislation, restrict research at university colleges of teacher education and the access to and usage possibilities of existing funding. The corresponding regulations should also be amended, as should all relevant adverse formal regulations in national research funding.

Promoting young talent

Several interviewees believe a more systematic, more specific promotion of young talent is key for the development of education research. Doctoral schools in particular were named, whereby these should also be organised cross-regional and across and beyond the various types of institutions, especially

where fragmentation does not allow an own solution to be installed. University colleges of teacher education should also be integrated, whereby these could also contribute more and systematically to the training of their scientific young talent, even without any right to award doctorates.

Measures with which the research career for teachers can be more attractive and feasible should also be developed.

International connection

Several interviewees believe more and flexible (institutional) funds for informal international cooperation should be provided for better participation in the international discourse, e.g. for financing rooms, travel, invitations to guest researchers and for internationally visible publications (e.g. cost for open access, proof-reading).

Data management

Access to available data should be improved (further). This applies to data at BIFIE and beyond. The coordination in data acquisition and secondary usage of data should also be enabled and increased, e.g. with the use of AUSSDA²¹, for example.

Connection between science and practical application

Many of those interviewed propose more specific work on the connection between research and practical application, from the more systematic transfer of scientific findings to practical application through to joint research and development. Activities of this kind should be made an explicit part of the range of tasks of university researchers, and therefore also a criterion in recruiting, with the evaluation of performance and in allocating resources. The funding listed above should support activities at the interfaces of science and practice, as well as the required qualification on both sides. Some people also suggested that specific transfer tasks could be taken on by specially qualified specialists, e.g. the preparation of research results for non-scientific trained target groups.

Many interviewees called in this context for a debate on values, a rethinking of the paradigms of (education) research, especially at the universities, where they see and some actually experience an increasing orientation towards the scientific community discourse, which makes development-oriented research with partners from practice and transfer activities more difficult. They would also like to see a rethinking (at their own institutions as well) of how scientific work can be combined with orientation towards social relevance.

Selected quotes:

“Specific funding!”

“Stimuli must be provided to unite the people that were previously battling away alone, to address problems, where it can only be done together.”

“Stimuli must be provided for companies, schools, parents, students to cooperate step-by-step in improving the education system.”

“How can we make the theory-practice-transfer more feasible? How can we motivate teachers more for research? There’s no use being at the international top if society doesn’t benefit. Studies that no one can read have never been any use.”

²¹<https://aussda.at/>

Appendix A Lead questions for the interviews

1. Introduction: How is education research organised with you, with cooperation partners and target groups?
2. Where do you think Austrian education research's **strong points** are in the international comparison? What research topics, programmes, institutions or people does this involve?
3. Where do you think Austrian education research's **weak points** are in the international comparison? What's missing in education research and why?
4. What people and institutions are **key players** in education research in Austria?
5. Do you know of any Austrian education research projects of recent years that have or could have high **innovation potential** for education institutions/players?
6. Do you see a systematic problem with the **transfer** of scientific findings of education research to practical application? And if so, why?
 - i) For the educational institutions and players in educational practice?
 - ii) For the administrative and political decision makers?
7. What **measures** could be implemented to improve funding for innovative projects in education research at the highest international level in the future?

technopolis|group| Austria
Rudolfsplatz 12/11
A-1010 Vienna
Austria
T +43 1 503 9592 12
F +43 1 503 9592 11
E info.at@technopolis-group.com
www.technopolis-group.com

Determining the Status of Austrian Education Research

Background Report: Online Survey

Maria del Carmen Calatrava Moreno, Brigitte Tiefenthaler

Determining the Status of Austrian Education Research

Background Report: Online Survey

technopolis **group** March 2019

Maria del Carmen Calatrava Moreno, Brigitte Tiefenthaler

Table of Contents

1	Introduction.....	1
1.1	Background.....	1
1.2	Response.....	1
2	Thematic focus.....	1
3	Research funding.....	2
4	Communication: Publications and transfer.....	5
5	Employment and qualification.....	9
6	Opinions on the present and future of education research in Austria.....	13
7	Concluding remarks.....	16
	Appendix A Response tables.....	17

Figures

Figure 1	Research thematic foci of the respondents and their institution.....	2
Figure 2	Proportion of recipients and reasons for not receiving third-party funding in the last five years.....	3
Figure 3	Opinion on research funding of respondents who have not received third-party research funding in the last five years.....	3
Figure 4	Distribution of the share of third-party funding from contract research and research funding.....	4
Figure 5	Respondents' main source of third-party funding in the last five years.....	5
Figure 6	Publication activity of survey respondents in public universities and university college of education.....	6
Figure 7	Histograms of participants' share of publications in different languages.....	6
Figure 8	Formats of respondents' publications in the past five years.....	7
Figure 9	Research audiences of recipients and non-recipients of third-party research funding.....	7
Figure 10	Activities for the transfer of research results of recipients and non-recipients of third-party funding.....	8
Figure 11	Activities for the transfer of research results of researchers in different institutions.....	8
Figure 12	Distribution of participants' contractual working time and the actual time at work.....	9
Figure 13	Distribution of participants' working time into different activities.....	9
Figure 14	Distribution of the proportion of participants' mandatory teaching assignment.....	10
Figure 15	Career level of recipients and non-recipients of third-party research funding.....	10
Figure 16	Type of research activity of respondents in different kinds of institutions.....	11
Figure 17	Completed field of studies of participants in different types of institutions.....	11
Figure 18	Field of the degree of participants that completed a teaching degree.....	12
Figure 19	Field of the degree of participants that completed a doctor's degree or PhD.....	12
Figure 20	Participants' opinions on education research in Austria.....	14

Figure 21 Participants' opinions on the importance of measures for the positive development and strengthening of education research in Austria 14

Figure 22 Participants' opinion on the importance of measures to strengthen the link between education research and practice..... 15

1 Introduction

1.1 Background

The Austrian Science Fund FWF was commissioned by the Innovation Foundation for Education with the coordination of determining the status of Austrian education research. This is performed as an Informed Peer Review process by an evaluation committee consisting of international experts, who reflect the disciplinary breadth of the field. The commission is supported in its work with qualitative and quantitative background materials on education research in Austria, which include interviews, an online survey, bibliometrics and various data materials. Technopolis Group Austria was commissioned with performing the interviews and the online survey. In this report, we summarise the results of the online survey.

The online survey was communicated through a snowball system, i.e. it was e-mailed to 120 leading personalities (e.g. heads of university departments, rectors of university colleges of teacher education, directors of research institutes) in Austrian education research, covering the whole spectrum of thematic and institutional diversity, with an invitation to complete the survey and to forward it to other researchers in their teams or at partner institutions. The guiding questions had been defined by the principal, the final questionnaire was elaborated and programmed by Technopolis Group Austria, taking into account the findings of the interviews¹. The survey was open from Dec. 15, 2018 to Feb. 10, 2019.

1.2 Response

The survey was answered by 253 individuals, of which 115 (55.3%) conduct research at a university college of teacher education, followed by 78 (37.5%) researchers at public universities. A minor proportion of respondents conduct their research in universities of applied sciences (4; 1.9%) and non-university research organizations (4; 1.9%).

Regarding nationality, 80.8% are Austrians, and 8.2% have a different nationality, German being the second most frequent. 73.9% of respondents have based their research career in Austria without spending more than one year abroad. 20.29% of all participants confirmed that they have spent more than one year in a different country, mostly in Germany, the United Kingdom and the United States. The age of the participants ranged from 30 or younger to 65, with the largest group of respondents being between 56-60 years old (18.3%). This might be explained by the fact that the survey was first sent to leading personalities. The age of the second largest group of respondents was 51-55 (16.4%), followed by 41-45 (12.9%). Younger researchers are also represented in the sample: 8.7% of participants are 30 or younger and 11% are between 31 and 35 years old. Regarding their academic titles, 64.9% of participants have at least a doctor's or a PhD degree and 32.6% are habilitated.

The following sections elaborate on the information provided by the participants on their thematic focus, research funding, communication of research results, employment and qualification, as well as their opinions on the present and future of education research in Austria. Summary tables with the answers to each survey question are listed in Appendix A.

2 Thematic focus

Respondents were asked to indicate their own research thematic focus and that of their institutions by selecting a maximum of three thematic areas. As it can be observed in Figure 1, for both institutions and researchers the 4 most often selected themes are 'teaching methodology', 'teachers', 'learning' and 'education research and theory'. Overall, respondents associated a higher number of themes to the

¹ Tiefenthaler, B., Warta, K. (2018): Determining the Status of Austrian Education Research. Background Report: Interviews.

institutions than to themselves, however, there is a strong significant correlation ($r = .60$, $p = .01$) between the thematic focus of the institutions and that of the individuals.

Figure 1 Research thematic foci of the respondents and their institution

Source: Technopolis Group

3 Research funding

Nearly half of the respondents indicated that they have received third-party research funding in the last 5 years, while the other half has not received it (see Figure 2). In particular, 56% of respondents in public universities and 45% in university colleges of teacher education have received third-party funding. The remaining 6% of all respondents did not know or did not provide an answer.

Among those that did **not** receive third-party research funding, 64% acknowledged that they did not apply for it, 8% had their proposals rejected and 13% gave other reasons. Amongst the other reasons, 6 participants elaborated on the obstacles that make third-party research funding unattractive, namely not having received information or not fitting into the requirements, too less suitable funding opportunities for certain subjects (e.g. applied didactics), or the reduction of support channels (e.g. the termination of the Sparkling Science programme). Three of them noted third-party funding is less attractive when working at university colleges of teacher education because the employment of project-specific personnel is not possible. One respondent explained in the following way: *‘it is unattractive to raise third-party funds. The largest part of the project budget is normally for personnel costs. Since we have no authority to employ personnel and we cannot confer doctoral degrees, applying for third-party funds to not bring me anything’*. Another participant offered a similar perspective on this matter: *‘Third-party funds can only be used to a limited extent at our university college of teacher education (for example, there is no employment for project staff). The implementation of third-party funded projects is time-consuming and involves many bureaucratic hurdles’*. Further reasons for not applying for third-party funding were that participants had only very recently started to work in science or at their institution and that the task to secure research funding falls out of the scope of their professional activities.

Figure 2 Proportion of recipients and reasons for not receiving third-party funding in the last five years

Source: Technopolis Group

Figure 3 Opinion on research funding of respondents who have not received third-party research funding in the last five years

Source: Technopolis Group

As illustrated in Figure 3, respondents that have not received third-party funds were asked to assess a set of statements about research funding. A higher level of consensus was reached on not having much time for research (73%), as well as not having enough experience in preparing proposals (66%). Furthermore, 62% of participants stated that it does not apply that their supervisors prepare proposals for them. Conversely, significant discrepancies among respondents were found when asked about their need for project funding to cover the cost of research activities, or whether there are suitable sources of third-party funding for the kind of research they conduct.

Concerning those who have received third-party funding in the last year, 41.88% could tell their share of contract research (i.e. remuneration of research done for a client) vs. research funding (i.e. grant for self-defined research projects), and 40.17% did not know. As it can be observed in the histograms in Figure 4, most participants receive 0-20% of their third-party funding from contract research and 80-100% from research funding.

Figure 4 Distribution of the share of third-party funding from contract research and research funding

Source: Technopolis Group

Concerning the sources of third-party funding, the Federal Ministry of Education was identified by the survey participants as the main source of funding – it was selected by 38.3% respondents as one of their most important sources in the last five years. It is followed in importance by Federal State Authorities, which were selected by 31.3% participants. We have also analysed these answers in relation to the type of institution where the participant is conducting research (i.e. public university, university college of teacher education)² revealing interesting insights on the relevance of sources of funding for different institutions. As illustrated in Figure 5, the Federal Ministry of Education has been a source of funding for a higher proportion of researchers in public universities than in university colleges of teacher education. Instead, for the latter group, the Federal State Authorities have funded a significantly higher share of projects than for public universities. This can be explained by the educational competencies of the Austrian provinces. Two particularly competitive funding sources, the European Framework Programme for Research and the Austrian Science Fund, have been identified by 25% of respondents affiliated to public universities, while only 12% of respondents from university colleges of teacher

² The analysis of survey questions in relation to the type of institution of participants is only calculated for public universities and university colleges of teacher education. The number of respondents working in other types of institutions (i.e. university of applied sciences, non-university organisation, companies, etc.) is not high enough to deliver statistically significant results.

training have received such funding. This can be ascribed to the fact that the research mission of the latter is relatively young and hence they are not yet fully competitive, especially in basic research.

Figure 5 Respondents' main source of third-party funding in the last five years

Source: Technopolis Group

4 Communication: Publications and transfer

Most respondents (90.5%) have been active at publishing in the last five years. When comparing the publication activity of respondents in different kinds of institutions, it can be observed that 86% of participants in public universities and 95% in university colleges of higher education have published research results in the last five years (see Figure 6).

Figure 6 Publication activity of survey respondents in public universities and university college of education

Source: Technopolis

Written communication is mostly published in German. As it can be observed in Figure 7, most respondents publish 80-100% of their publications in German, while most individuals publishing in English only do so in less than 20% of their publications. The most common forms of publication are professional journals with peer review and edited volumes (see Figure 8). These two forms of publications have been used by the majority of participants, and most participants have published there several times. Instead, more than half of the respondents have written monographs, but only on a few occasions (e.g. theses). Other forms of publications used by respondents are school books, presentations and workshops, conference papers with proceedings, poster presentations and online writings (i.e. newsletters).

Figure 7 Histograms of participants' share of publications in different languages

Source: Technopolis Group

Figure 8 Formats of respondents' publications in the past five years

Source: Technopolis Group

The communication of research results is targeted mostly to the education system and to a similar extent by both recipients and non-recipients of third-party funding (see Figure 9). However, recipients of third-party funding, in contrast to non-recipients, communicate a higher proportion of their results to the scientific community and politic bodies. The general public is the less frequently addressed by both groups of researchers (both recipients and non-recipients of funding).

Figure 9 Research audiences of recipients and non-recipients of third-party research funding

Source: Technopolis Group

In general, recipients of third-party research funding have conducted more activities to transfer research results to practice (see Figure 10). The most common approaches to transfer results of education research are conference presentations, contributions in publications and contributions to teacher training. The first two are used by a higher percentage of individuals in public universities, while respondents at university colleges of teacher education contribute more often to teacher training (see Figure 11). These three approaches have been used by more than 60% of non-recipients of third-party funding and more than 68% of the recipients. Other activities such as consulting services for

practitioners, science-based higher education courses, project for teaching or schools, and participatory research projects are used to a lesser extent by respondents.

Figure 10 Activities for the transfer of research results of recipients and non-recipients of third-party funding

Source: Technopolis Group

Figure 11 Activities for the transfer of research results of researchers in different institutions

Source: Technopolis Group

5 Employment and qualification

A permanent contract was the most common employment situation among the participants (up to 67.1%), followed by a fixed-term contract (30%). Regarding the contractual hours per week, 74.6% had a full-time contract (40h or more) and 25.4% a contract of less than 40h. Most participants have contracts of 30-40 working hours (see Figure 12). Although only 2 participants have a contract of 50 weekly working hours, 50 participants stated that they worked more than 50h per week in the last year.

Figure 12 Distribution of participants' contractual working time and the actual time at work

Source: Technopolis Group

Figure 13 Distribution of participants' working time into different activities

Source: Technopolis Group

The proportion of respondents' working time dedicated to different activities is illustrated in Figure 13. There, it can be observed that most participants have their working time distributed across different activities. It is common among the respondents to have 0-20% of their working time allocated to research and development, as well as to management and administration. It is interesting to observe that the number of respondents with more time allocated to such activities is lower for each further interval (20-40%, 40-60%, 60-80%...). This pattern is not observed in teaching and training: a high number of respondents teach/train 20-40% of their time, but several respondents also teach 60-80% of their time.

Participants were also asked to provide information on their contractual working time for teaching and training. When compared to the actual working time dedicated to this activity, differences can be observed (turquoise chart in Figure 13 vs. Figure 14). According to the contracts, more respondents have a teaching assignment with 0-20% and 80-100% of their time allocated to teaching.

Figure 14 Distribution of the proportion of participants' mandatory teaching assignment

Source: Technopolis Group

The job position of 80.3% of the respondents is financed by institutional funding (e.g. general university funds). Therefore, the institutions are the main source of funding for most participants, followed by third-party funding, which supports 6.9% of respondents. As illustrated in Figure 15, the share of recipients of third-party research funding is higher among the senior researchers, either leader or established researchers. Instead, there is a lower proportion of recipients of third-party funding among 'first stage researchers' (i.e. up to the point of PhD) and 'recognised researchers' (i.e. PhD holders who are not yet fully independent).

Figure 15 Career level of recipients and non-recipients of third-party research funding

Source: Technopolis Group

Applied research is the most common research activity conducted by respondents, followed by basic research, and experimental development. Figure 16 shows that there are differences in the type of research activity of individuals working in public universities and university colleges of teacher education. While basic research is conducted by a significantly higher number of researchers in public universities, applied research and experimental development is more common among researchers in university colleges of teacher education.

Figure 16 Type of research activity of respondents in different kinds of institutions

Source: Technopolis Group

Regarding the professional background of individuals, differences could also be observed according to the kind of institution where they work (see Figure 17). A significantly higher proportion of respondents in university colleges of teacher education completed a teaching degree or a degree in education science. To a lesser extent, a degree in psychology was also more common among respondents from university colleges of teacher education. Instead, degrees in psychology and natural or technical sciences were more common among individuals in public universities. Additionally, it should be noted that 41.3% of respondents in public universities and 62.3% in university colleges of teacher education have completed more than one degree of studies in different fields.

Figure 17 Completed field of studies of participants in different types of institutions

Source: Technopolis Group

Among those who completed a teaching degree, their most common field of study was in humanities and cultural studies, followed by primary school and natural sciences (see Figure 18).

Figure 18 Field of the degree of participants that completed a teaching degree

Source: Technopolis Group

Regarding those holding a doctor's or PhD degree, their thesis was in most cases in the field of education sciences, especially for individuals working in university colleges of teacher education (see Figure 19). Again, the number of individuals who conducted research in natural or technical sciences and in psychology during their doctoral studies/PhD is higher in public universities. Nevertheless, it should be noted that the proportion of individuals who conducted doctoral research on teaching is similar in both types of institutions.

Figure 19 Field of the degree of participants that completed a doctor's degree or PhD

Source: Technopolis Group

6 Opinions on the present and future of education research in Austria

Survey participants were asked to assess their agreement to a set of statements, listed in Figure 20, about education research in Austria. Some statements regarding the support and funding for education research reached a high level of consensus. For instance, 74.3% fully or rather agreed that it is difficult to implement structure-forming long-term projects in education research in Austria. Regarding funding, 71.5% regarded that it is not enough for the development of education research in Austria. Similarly, the support of young researchers in education research was regarded as too little by 68.7% of the respondents. Another 68.9% of them did **not** agree that the transfer of research results into education administration and politics works well. Most participants (71.5%) also agreed on the low societal appreciation for education research in Austria.

Conversely, respondents were rather divided in their assessment of whether education research in Austria is too small and fragmented to be internationally competitive (47.7% agreed – 33.2% disagreed). A greater discordance was found on whether the networking of education actors is a strength of education research in Austria (39.3% agreed – 40.2% disagreed). Neither was there was consensus on whether the transfer of research results into educational institutions works well (34.1% agreed – 54.7% disagreed).

Respondents were also asked to assess the importance of measures for the positive development and strengthening of education research in Austria. As it can be observed in Figure 21, participants shared similar opinions in all but one statement, which referred to the foundation of large, non-university institutes (e.g. modelled on the examples of the Max Planck Society or the Leibniz Association in Germany). Participants dissented on whether this kind of institutions would strengthen the Austrian education research (45.6% agreed – 33.6% disagreed). Among the other statements, the two that reached the highest level of agreement referred to funding: (i) better conditions for education research within the existing framework (91.6% agreed); (ii) special funding for education research (91.1% agreed).

The importance of measures to strengthen the link between education research and practice was also assessed by respondents. As shown in Figure 22, there was a significant agreement on the importance of four statements: three related to funding (for knowledge transfer, research cooperation and education research itself) (each of them assessed by more than 86% participants as very important or rather important), and one suggesting a stronger anchoring and recognition of cooperation with practice as the task of educational researchers (83.6% very/rather important – 7% (rather) unimportant). The remaining two statements were assessed as having more moderate importance. One of them suggested organising training on science communication for educational researchers (rated as very rather important by 67.3% of the respondents), and the other proposed a debate on values on about the paradigms of education research and their social relevance. The latter was rated as very/rather important by 63.1% of the respondents, which makes it the least important statement in their opinion.

Figure 20 Participants' opinions on education research in Austria

Source: Technopolis Group

Figure 21 Participants' opinions on the importance of measures for the positive development and strengthening of education research in Austria

Source: Technopolis Group

Figure 22 Participants' opinion on the importance of measures to strengthen the link between education research and practice

Source: Technopolis Group

7 Concluding remarks

The results of this survey complement other background materials provided to the expert committee. Participation has been high, especially from researchers from university colleges of teacher education, and there was also a substantial response from researchers at public universities. Researchers from other types of institutions are less represented, in line with the smaller number of such institutions. Thematic foci of respondents “converge” around issues related to the school system (in contrast to e.g. adult education, higher education with relatively few respondents).

The results of the survey confirm and illustrate key findings from the interviews (see Tiefenthaler, Warta (2018):

- Many researchers have high teaching obligations
- Main differences between university colleges of teacher training and public universities are also confirmed in quantitative terms, e.g.:
 - The more applied focus of research at the university colleges of teacher training
 - The higher significance of very competitive third-party funding sources for public universities
 - Research communication in public universities mainly via conferences and journals, and a higher focus on teacher training activities in university colleges of teacher training.
- Opinions on the present and future of education research in Austria agree with interview findings in several critical issues, in particular regarding:
 - the difficulty to implement structure-forming long-term projects in education research
 - the lack of funding for the development of education research
 - the lack of support of young researchers in education research
 - the difficulty of the transfer of research results into education administration and politics
 - the low societal appreciation for education research in Austria.
- Conversely, and like in the interviews, some issues seem to be rather debated, e.g. whether education research in Austria is too small and fragmented to be internationally competitive, whether the networking of education actors is a strength of education research in Austria, or whether the transfer of research results into educational institutions works well. Assessment on these issues seems to be very much determined by personal experience.

Appendix A Response tables

A.1 Thematic focus

A.1.1 What are the thematic foci in education research at your institution? *(Multiple answers possible)*

Answer choices	Responses (absolute)	Responses (%)
Teaching methodology	175	69.17%
Education research and theory	152	60.08%
Didactics (general)	120	47.43%
Vocational education and training	81	32.02%
Learning	158	62.45%
School system	119	47.04%
Adult education	69	27.27%
Higher education research	113	44.66%
Early childhood education	72	28.46%
Social pedagogy	42	16.60%
Students / Pupils	124	49.01%
Special needs education	83	32.81%
Teachers	174	68.77%
E-Learning	96	37.94%
Psychological aspects of education	79	31.23%
Not specified	5	1.98%
Other field of research	37	14.62%
Number of respondents	253/253	

A.1.2 What is your own thematic focus in research? Please select up to three research areas that describe your focus most appropriately. *(Multiple answers possible, up to three)*

Answer choices	Responses (absolute)	Responses (%)
Teaching methodology	92	36.36%
Education research and theory	69	27.27%
Didactics (general)	33	13.04%
Vocational education and training	19	7.51%
Learning	62	24.51%
School system	37	14.62%

Answer choices	Responses (absolute)	Responses (%)
Adult education	25	9.88%
Higher education research	44	17.39%
Early childhood education	12	4.74%
Social pedagogy	7	2.77%
Students / Pupils	43	17.00%
Special needs education	14	5.53%
Teachers	84	33.20%
E-Learning	28	11.07%
Psychological aspects of education	31	12.25%
Not specified	0	0.00%
Other fields of research	51	20.16%
Number of respondents	253/253	

A.2 Research funding

A.2.1 Have you received any third-party research funding during the past five years?

Answer choices	Survey logic	Responses (absolute)	Responses (%)
Yes	Go to A.2.2	117	46.03%
No	Go to A.2.5	122	48.41%
I don't know	Go to A.3.1	10	3.97%
Not specified	Go to A.3.1	4	1.59%
Number of respondents		252/253	

A.2.2 Do you know how large the shares of contract research on the one hand and research funding on the other are in the total third-party funds acquired by you?

Answer choices	Survey logic	Responses (absolute)	Responses (%)
Yes	Go to A.2.3	49	41.88%
No	Go to A.2.4	47	40.17%
Not specified	Go to A.2.4	21	17.95%
Number of respondents		117/117	

A.2.3 Considering the total of third-party funding for research you have acquired: Please give an estimate of the shares you have received during the past five years.

Answer choices	Responses (per interval)
Contract research, i.e. remuneration of research you did for a client (%)	[0 – 20%]: 15 (20 – 40%]: 2 (40 – 60%]: 5 (60 – 80%]: 1 (80 – 100%]: 4
Grant funding, i.e. grant for your self-defined research projects (%)	[0 – 20%]: 3 (20 – 40%]: 3 (40 – 60%]: 6 (60 – 80%]: 8 (80 – 100%]: 18
Allocation to these categories unknown / not clear (%)	[0 – 20%]: 4 (20 – 40%]: 5 (40 – 60%]: 0 (60 – 80%]: 1 (80 – 100%]: 1
Number of respondents	43/49

A.2.4 Which have been your main sources of third-party funding during the past five years? (Multiple answers possible)

	Responses (absolute)	Responses (%)
Austrian Science Funds (FWF)	17	14.78%
Jubiläumsfonds of the Austrian Central Bank (OeNB)	9	7.83%
Austrian Academy of Sciences (ÖAW)	2	1.74%
Ludwig Boltzmann Society (LBG)	0	0.00%
Federal Ministry of Education	44	38.26%
Other Federal Ministries	13	11.30%
Federal state authority	36	31.30%
Municipality	6	5.22%
Austrian Research Promotion Agency (FFG)	10	8.70%
Regional funding agency (e.g. WWTF, Tiroler Wissenschaftsfonds)	9	7.83%
European Framework Programme for Research (including European Research Council, ERC)	18	15.65%
Other European Programmes	20	17.39%

	Responses (absolute)	Responses (%)
Non-profit Foundation	7	6.09%
Other non-profit organisation	12	10.43%
Private company	10	8.70%
Don't know	3	2.61%
Not specified	1	0.87%
Other	20	17.39%
Number of respondents	115/117	

A.2.5 Why did you not receive third party research funding during the past five years?

Answer choices	Responses (absolute)	Responses (%)
I did not apply for third party funding	74	63.79%
My proposals or offers for third party funding have been rejected	10	8.62%
Not specified	17	14.66%
Other reason	15	12.93%
Number of respondents	116/122	

A.2.6 Please indicate if the following statements apply to you.

	It applies	It somewhat applies	If rather does not apply	It does not apply	I cannot / do not want to judge that
I have no / too little time for research	32 (27.59%)	53 (45.69%)	22 (18.97%)	9 (7.76%)	0 (0.00%)
I do not need project funding for my research. it is funded through institutional funds	15 (12.93%)	31 (26.72%)	33 (28.45%)	26 (22.41%)	11 (9.48%)
There are no suitable sources of third-party funding for the kind of research I do	12 (10.34%)	32 (27.59%)	31 (26.72%)	10 (8.62%)	31 (26.72%)
I think that the selection procedures of the funding organisations are not impartial	10 (8.62%)	13 (11.21%)	20 (17.24%)	19 (16.38%)	54 (46.55%)
I think that only mainstream research will receive funding	18 (15.52%)	29 (25.00%)	18 (15.52%)	10 (8.62%)	41 (35.34%)
The risk of proposals being rejected is too high in relation to the effort of preparing a proposal	29 (25.00%)	38 (32.76%)	12 (10.34%)	6 (5.17%)	31 (26.72%)
The requirements for scientific qualification are too high for me	3 (2.59%)	23 (19.83%)	38 (32.76%)	42 (36.21%)	10 (8.62%)
My supervisor prepares grant proposals for me	2 (1.72%)	7 (6.03%)	14 (12.07%)	58 (50.00%)	35 (30.17%)
I think. the funding available is too low	8 (6.90%)	13 (11.21%)	20 (17.24%)	16 (13.79%)	59 (50.86%)
I do not have enough experience in preparing proposals	35 (30.17%)	42 (36.21%)	16 (13.79%)	9 (7.76%)	14 (12.07%)
Other reasons	0 (0.00%)				
Number of respondents	116/117				

A.3 Communication: Publications and transfer

A.3.1 Who are the key audiences for your research results? (Multiple answers possible)

Answer choices	Responses (absolute)	Responses (%)
Science	176	72.43%
Education system	192	79.01%
Politic bodies	86	35.39%
General public	85	34.98%
Not specified	3	1.23%
Other	16	6.58%
Number of respondents	243/253	

A.3.2 Have you published during the past five years?

Answer choices	Survey logic	Responses (absolute)	Responses (%)
Yes	Go to A.3.3	220	90.53%
No	Go to A.3.5	20	8.23%
Not specified	Go to A.3.5	3	1.23%
Number of respondents		243/253	

A.3.3 In which types of publications have you published during the past five years? Please indicate the respective number of publications. (Multiple answers possible)

Answer choices	Responses (absolute)	Responses (%)
Professional Journal with peer review	160	81.22%
Professional Journal without peer review	135	68.53%
Monograph	100	50.76%
Edited volume	159	80.71%
Study, e.g. policy papers, contract research, expertise (here you can also count those works which have not (completely) been published by the client, provided that the client has accepted them).	93	47.21%
Publications for the general public, e.g. newspapers	80	40.61%
I have not published in the past five years	0	0.00%
Other	63	31.98%
Number of respondents	197/220	

A.3.4 In which languages have you published during the past five years? Please indicate estimate shares (by numbers of publication) per language.

Answer choices	Responses (per interval)
German (%)	[0 – 20%]: 12 (20 – 40%): 8 (40 – 60%): 16 (60 – 80%): 32 (80 – 100%): 128
English (%)	[0 – 20%]: 63 (20 – 40%): 19 (40 – 60%): 11 (60 – 80%): 8 (80 – 100%): 14
Other (%)	[0 – 20%]: 25 (20 – 40%): 2 (40 – 60%): 0 (60 – 80%): 0 (80 – 100%): 0
Number of respondents	206/220

A.3.5 Which are your main activities for transferring results of your research to practice? (Multiple answers possible)

Answer choices	Responses (absolute)	Responses (%)
One- or multi-year science-based higher education and university courses (further education)	76	33.19%
Contributions to teacher training in shorter formats	151	65.94%
One- or multi-year science-based project for the development of teaching or schools	73	31.88%
Contributions to conferences with scientific speakers. specifically addressing target groups from practice	167	72.93%
Contributions in publications (e.g. newsletters, journals, brochures) which specifically address target groups from practice	159	69.43%
Participatory research projects together with actors from practice (e.g. action research)	70	30.57%
Transfer via consulting services for practitioners	78	34.06%
No activities	4	1.75%
Not specified	5	2.18%
Other	14	6.11%
Number of respondents	229/253	

A.4 On the present and future of education research in Austria

A.4.1 Perceptions of education research in Austria: The following list contains pointed statements on the situation of educational research in Austria. Please indicate to what extent you agree or disagree with these statements

	I fully agree	I rather agree	I rather disagree	I don't agree at all	I cannot / do not want to judge that
Education research in Austria is too small and fragmented to be internationally competitive.	25 (11.68%)	77 (35.98%)	51 (23.83%)	20 (9.35%)	41 (19.16%)
Austrian education research has developed positively in recent years.	34 (15.89%)	102 (47.66%)	32 (14.95%)	7 (3.27%)	39 (18.22%)
One of the strengths of education research in Austria is the good networking among the players.	22 (10.28%)	62 (28.97%)	66 (30.84%)	20 (9.35%)	44 (20.56%)
The current public research funding is sufficient for the positive further development of education research in Austria.	1 (0.47%)	18 (8.41%)	61 (28.50%)	92 (42.99%)	42 (19.63%)
Young researchers in education research receive too little systematic support and development.	65 (30.37%)	82 (38.32%)	27 (12.62%)	7 (3.27%)	33 (15.42%)
It is difficult to implement structure-forming long-term projects in education research in Austria.	80 (37.38%)	79 (36.92%)	17 (7.94%)	8 (3.74%)	30 (14.02%)
The transfer of research results into education administration and politics works well.	3 (1.40%)	30 (14.02%)	60 (28.04%)	87 (40.65%)	34 (15.89%)
The transfer of research results into educational institutions works well.	9 (4.21%)	64 (29.91%)	78 (36.45%)	39 (18.22%)	24 (11.21%)
Societal appreciation for education research in Austria is too low.	71 (33.18%)	82 (38.32%)	24 (11.21%)	9 (4.21%)	28 (13.08%)
Number of respondents	214/253				

A.4.2 Which measures would be particularly important for the positive development and strengthening of education research in Austria?

	Very important	Rather important	Rather unimportant	Unimportant	I cannot / do not want to judge that
Special research funding for education research.	138 (64.49%)	57 (26.64%)	6 (2.80%)	1 (0.47%)	12 (5.61%)
Better conditions for education research within the framework of existing research funding.	120 (56.07%)	76 (35.51%)	4 (1.87%)	1 (0.47%)	13 (6.07%)
Specific measures to promote young researchers (e.g. doctoral programmes).	124 (57.94%)	64 (29.91%)	10 (4.67%)	3 (1.40%)	13 (6.07%)
Measures to improve international orientation and cooperation.	105 (49.07%)	84 (39.25%)	14 (6.54%)	1 (0.47%)	10 (4.67%)
Special funding for research cooperation with educational practice.	107 (50.00%)	79 (36.92%)	16 (7.48%)	4 (1.87%)	8 (3.74%)
Improving access to existing data.	87 (40.65%)	78 (36.45%)	26 (12.15%)	6 (2.80%)	17 (7.94%)
Improving the framework conditions for research at the university colleges of teacher education.	130 (60.75%)	35 (16.36%)	11 (5.14%)	9 (4.21%)	29 (13.55%)
Foundation of large, non-university institutes, modelled on the examples of the Max Planck Society or the Leibniz Association in Germany.	42 (19.63%)	55 (25.70%)	46 (21.50%)	26 (12.15%)	45 (21.03%)
A better link between education research and practice.	114 (53.27%)	64 (29.91%)	27 (12.62%)	4 (1.87%)	5 (2.34%)
Other measures	32 (12.62%)				
Number of respondents	214/253				

A.4.3 What measures would be particularly important to strengthen the link between education research and practice? Please rate the following measures.

	Very important	Rather important	Rather unimportant	Unimportant	I cannot / do not want to judge that
Special funding for measures to transfer knowledge from science to practice.	128 (59.81%)	67 (31.31%)	8 (3.74%)	1 (0.47%)	10 (4.67%)
Special funding for research cooperation with educational practice.	110 (51.40%)	81 (37.85%)	10 (4.67%)	1 (0.47%)	12 (5.61%)
Trainings on science communication for education researchers.	63 (29.44%)	81 (37.85%)	42 (19.63%)	13 (6.07%)	15 (7.01%)
Stronger anchoring and recognition of cooperation with practice as the task of educational researchers.	106 (49.53%)	73 (34.11%)	18 (8.41%)	5 (2.34%)	12 (5.61%)
Stronger funding of educational research itself.	121 (56.54%)	65 (30.37%)	11 (5.14%)	4 (1.87%)	13 (6.07%)
A debate on values about the paradigms of education research and their social relevance.	61 (28.50%)	74 (34.58%)	38 (17.76%)	15 (7.01%)	26 (12.15%)
Other measures	14 (6.54%)				
Number of respondents	214/253				

A.5 Employment and qualification

A.5.1 What is your current employment situation?

Answer choices	Survey logic	Responses (absolute)	Responses (%)
Permanent contract	Go to A.5.2	143	67.14%
Fixed-term contract	Go to A.5.2	64	30.05%
Retired	Go to A.5.3	1	0.47%
Not specified	Go to A.5.3	2	0.94%
Other	Go to A.5.3	3	1.41%
Number of respondents		213/253	

A.5.2 Which is the main funding source for your position?

Answer choices	Responses (absolute)	Responses (%)
Institutional funding (e.g. general university funds)	163	80.30%
Third-party funding	14	6.90%
I don't know	6	2.96%
Not specified	17	8.37%
Other	3	1.48%
Number of respondents	203/207	

A.5.3 Which career level have you reached? Please select the career level classification that describes your current position best. If you have already retired: What was your last career level before retirement? For a more detailed definition please see: EURAXESS (<https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/europe/career-development/training-researchers/research-profiles-descriptors>)

Answer choices	Responses (absolute)	Responses (%)
R1 = First Stage Researcher (Up to the point of PhD)	56	26.92%
R2 = Recognised Researcher (PhD holders or equivalent who are not yet fully independent)	28	13.46%
R3 = Established Researcher (Researchers who have developed a level of independence)	45	21.63%
R4 = Leading Researcher (Researchers leading their research area or field)	48	23.08%
Not specified	31	14.90%
Number of respondents	208/253	

A.5.4 Please name your main location of research. If you have already retired: What was your main location of research before retirement?

Answer choices	Responses (absolute)	Responses (%)
Public University	78	37.50%
Private university	0	0.00%
University college of teacher education	115	55.29%
University of applied science	4	1.92%
Non-university research organisation	4	1.92%
Company	0	0.00%
Not specified	7	3.37%
Other	0	0.00%
Number of respondents	208/253	

A.5.5 Which of the following descriptions characterizes your research activities best?

Answer choices	Responses (absolute)	Responses (%)
Basic research... is primarily aimed at gaining new scientific knowledge without being oriented towards practical applicability (= increase of knowledge without primary orientation towards a practical goal)	28	13.46%
Applied research... is aimed at gaining new scientific knowledge. but differs from basic research in that applied research is primarily directed towards a specific objective or a specific practical application (= increase of knowledge with primary focus on a practical goal)	151	72.60%
Experimental development... uses scientific knowledge to arrive at new or substantially improved products, concepts, processes or services (= systematic use of knowledge with the aim of producing new or substantially improved materials, devices, products, processes or systems)	24	11.54%
Not specified	5	2.40%
Number of respondents	208/253	

A.5.6 What is your current contractual working time per week?

Answer choices	Responses (per interval)	Responses (absolute)	Responses (%)
Hours per week	[0 – 10h]: 6 (10 – 20h): 21 (20 – 30h): 18		

Answer choices	Responses (per interval)	Responses (absolute)	Responses (%)
	(30 – 40h]: 147 (40 – 50h]: 5		
More than 39h		147	74.62%
Less than 39h		50	25.38%
Number of respondents	197/253		

A.5.7 What has been your average weekly working time in the past year?

Answer choices	Responses (per interval)
Hours per week	[0 – 10h]: 5 (10 – 20h]: 7 (20 – 30h]: 11 (30 – 40h]: 49 (40 – 50h]: 64 (50 – 60h]: 39 (60 – 70h]: 6 (70 – 80h]: 5
Number of respondents	186/253

A.5.8 What shares of your working time do you dedicate to the following activities on an annual average, approximately? The following classification is also used by Statistik Austria in the full surveys among R&D performing institutions.

Answer choices	Responses (per interval)
Research and development (%)	[0 – 20%]: 80 (20 – 40%]: 69 (40 – 60%]: 34 (60 – 80%]: 10 (80 – 100%]: 1
Teaching and training (%)	[0 – 20%]: 39 (20 – 40%]: 84 (40 – 60%]: 28 (60 – 80%]: 30 (80 – 100%]: 5
Management and administration (%)	[0 – 20%]: 89 (20 – 40%]: 54 (40 – 60%]: 20 (60 – 80%]: 11 (80 – 100%]: 2
Other	[0 – 20%]: 77

Answer choices	Responses (per interval)
	(20 – 40%]: 2 (40 – 60%]: 1 (60 – 80%]: 0 (80 – 100%]: 0
Number of respondents	194/253

A.5.9 What is your mandatory teaching assignment? Please indicate as a share of your total contractual working hours (%).

Answer choices	Responses (per interval)
Teaching assignment (% of total contractual working hours)	[0 – 20%]: 62 (20 – 40%]: 45 (40 – 60%]: 26 (60 – 80%]: 15 (80 – 100%]: 19
Number of respondents	167/253

A.5.10 Please indicate your age.

Answer choices	Responses (absolute)	Responses (%)
30 or younger	18	8.65%
31-35	23	11.06%
36-40	20	9.62%
41-45	27	12.98%
46-50	24	11.54%
51-55	34	16.35%
56-60	38	18.27%
61-65	15	7.21%
66 or older	0	0.00%
Not specified	9	4.33%
Number of respondents	208/253	

A.5.11 Please indicate your gender.

Answer choices	Responses (absolute)	Responses (%)
Female	18	8.65%

Answer choices	Responses (absolute)	Responses (%)
Male	23	11.06%
No information	20	9.62%
Other	27	12.98%
Number of respondents	208/253	

A.5.12 Please indicate your citizenship.

Answer choices	Responses (absolute)	Responses (%)
Austrian	168	80.77%
Not specified	17	8.17%
Other	23	11.06%
Number of respondents	208/253	

A.5.13 Which field(s) of study did you complete? (Multiple answers possible)

Answer choices	Survey logic	Responses (absolute)	Responses (%)
Teaching degree	Go to A.5.14	118	56.73%
Education sciences	Go to A.5.15	74	35.58%
Psychology	Go to A.5.15	24	11.54%
Other social science subject (ÖFOS 5)*	Go to A.5.15	37	17.79%
Other humanities subject (ÖFOS 6)*	Go to A.5.15	39	18.75%
Natural or technical science subject (ÖFOS 1-4)*	Go to A.5.15	23	11.06%
Not specified	Go to A.5.15	9	4.33%
Other	Go to A.5.15	25	12.02%
Number of respondents		208/253	

*Austrian taxonomy of fields of science. Further information can be found here:

<https://www.fwf.ac.at/fileadmin/files/Dokumente/Antragstellung/wiss-disz-201708.pdf>

A.5.14 In which fields have you completed your teaching degree(s)? (Multiple answers possible)

Answer choices	Responses (absolute)	Responses (%)
Humanities and Cultural Studies	54	45.76%
Primary school	43	36.44%

Answer choices	Responses (absolute)	Responses (%)
Agriculture and forestry	0	0.00%
Natural sciences	35	29.66%
Theology	6	5.08%
Economics	4	3.39%
Not specified	6	5.08%
Number of respondents	118/118	

More information about this classification of the Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research can be found here: <https://www.studienwahl.at/studien/lehramtsstudien/>

A.5.15 Do you hold a doctor's degree or PhD?

Answer choices	Survey logic	Responses (absolute)	Responses (%)
Yes	Go to A.5.16	135	64.90%
No	Go to A.5.19	71	34.13%
Not specified	Go to A.5.19	2	0.96%
Number of respondents		208/253	

A.5.16 When did you complete your (first) doctor's degree / PhD?

Answer choices	Responses (per interval)
Year	[1973, 1982]: 2 (1982, 1991]: 11 (1991, 2000]: 24 (2000, 2009]: 37 (2009, 2018]: 50
Number of respondents	124/135

A.5.17 What is the main field of research of your doctor's degree / PhD?

Answer choices	Responses (absolute)	Responses (%)
Teaching degree	12	8.89%
Education sciences	54	40.00%
Psychology	9	6.67%
Other social science subject (ÖFOS 5)*	20	14.81%
Other humanities subject (ÖFOS 6)*	23	17.04%
Natural or technical science subject (ÖFOS 1-4)*	14	10.37%

Answer choices	Responses (absolute)	Responses (%)
Not specified	4	2.96%
Other	14	10.37%
Number of respondents	135/135	

*Austrian taxonomy of fields of science. Further information can be found here:
<https://www.fwf.ac.at/fileadmin/files/Dokumente/Antragstellung/wiss-disz-201708.pdf>

A.5.18 Have you habilitated?

Answer choices	Responses (absolute)	Responses (%)
Yes	44	32.59%
No	84	62.22%
Not specified	7	5.19%
Number of respondents	135/135	

A.5.19 Have you continuously spent more than a year during your research career in a country different from the country where you studied?

Answer choices	Responses (absolute)	Responses (%)
Yes	42	20.29%
No	153	73.91%
Not specified	12	5.80%
Number of respondents	207/253	

technopolis |group| Austria
Rudolfsplatz 12/11
A-1010 Wien
Austria
T +43 1 503 9592 12
F +43 1 503 9592 11
E info.at@technopolis-group.com
www.technopolis-group.com